

ANNUAL SCIENTIFIC REPORT

**CENTER FOR CARBON RESEARCH IN TROPICAL AGRICULTURE
(CCARBON)/USP**

**RESEARCH, INNOVATION AND DISSEMINATION CENTERS
(CEPID)- FAPESP**

**AUGUST
2024**

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(CEPID)- FAPESP**

Annual Scientific Report
submitted to The São Paulo
Research Foundation (FAPESP),
as part of the requirements for the
activities performed in Process:
2021/10573 - Period from
September 1st 2023 to August 31th
2024

**AUGUST
2024**

SUMMARY

1 Introduction	7
2 Research scope results.....	8
2.1 Soil.....	13
2.1.1 Are the Brazilian agricultural soils acting as C sinks or sources?	13
2.1.1.1 Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri.....	13
2.1.1.2 Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho.....	18
2.1.1.3 Principal Investigator: Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni.....	18
2.1.2 How changes on the composition and activity of the soil microbiome can be related to the capacity of C sequestration in agriculture systems?.....	20
2.1.2.1 Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote.....	20
2.1.3 Are there synergies between soil carbon sequestration and soil health and other ecosystem services?.....	22
2.1.3.1 Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin.....	22
2.1.4 How to transform degrade soils into climate-smart solutions (upland and wetlands)?.....	29
2.1.4.1 Principal Investigator: Tiago Osório Ferreira.....	29
2.1.5 How to measure the carbon consumed by enhanced weathering (EW) of silicate rock powders (SRP) applied to soil with sufficient certainty for the c capture certification/ carbon credit market?.....	31
2.1.5.1 Principal Investigator: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo.....	31
2.2 Plant	32
2.2.1 This study aims to answer the question: to what extent do restoration and commercial tree plantations mitigate GHG emissions from agriculture?	32
2.2.1.1 Principal Investigator: Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez.....	32
2.2.2 How to restore and measure tropical forest multifunctionality and resilience?	34
2.2.2.1 Principal Investigator: Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion.....	35
2.2.3 How to boost the efficiency and rate of carbon fixation by plants?.....	35
2.2.3.1 Principal Investigator: Helaine Carrer.....	35
2.2.4 How to exploit the interplay of soil plant insect pest microbiomes in pest management to enhance carbon accumulation, mineralization and sequestration?	36
2.2.4.1 Principal Investigator: Fernando Luis Cônsoli	36
2.2.5 Are the agri-food systems prepared to address the changing demands for healthy, low-C emission, and sustainable ingredients in food?.....	36
2.2.5.1 Principal Investigator: Thais Maria Ferreira de Souza Vieira	36

2.3	Animal.....	37
2.3.1	How grazing management may help to mitigate GHG emissions in pastoral systems of animal production?.....	37
2.3.1.1	Principal Investigator: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira	37
2.3.2	How manipulating the microbiome profile in the rumen through feed biomass can mitigate enteric methane in grazing ruminants under tropical conditions?.....	38
2.3.2.1	Principal Investigator: Adibe Luiz Abdalla	38
2.3.3	Which are the impacts of the inclusion of several flint corn ethanol by products available in Brazil, of genetically modified flint corn grain high in alpha amylase, and of flint corn processed through different processing methods in diets containing flint corn for feedlot cattle on beef production and GHG emissions?	39
2.3.3.1	Principal Investigator: Flávio Augusto Portela Santos	39
2.4	Atmosphere	40
2.4.1	Which are the possible impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops? .	40
2.4.1.1	Principal Investigator: Fabio Ricardo Marin.....	40
2.4.2	Which are the possible impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops? .	40
2.4.2.1	Principal Investigator: Heitor Cantarella	40
2.5	Digital Tools.....	42
2.5.1	What are the socio-economic impacts of new technologies related to low C agriculture? / What are the economic and environmental impacts of new technologies in the Brazilian agriculture and livestock sectors?	42
2.5.1.1	Principal Investigator: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho.....	42
2.5.2	How can geotechnologies assist on the diagnostic of carbon impacts on agriculture, environment and climate?	43
2.5.2.1	Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê.....	43
3.	Dissemination	48
4.	Innovation.....	67
5.	First International Scientific Advisory Board Meeting.....	70
6.	Final Considerations.....	71
	Appendix 1 Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri.....	73
	Appendix 1.1	21
	Appendix 1.2.....	22
	Appendix 2 Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho	24
	APPENDIX 2.1	27
	Appendix 3 Principal Investigator: Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni	28
	Appendix 4 Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote	30
	Appendix 5 Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin.....	32

Appendix 5.1.....	42
Appendix 5.2.....	42
Appendix 5.3.....	43
Appendix 5.4.....	44
Appendix 5.5.....	44
Appendix 5.6.....	45
Appendix 6 Principal Investigator: Tiago Osório Ferreira.....	45
Appendix 6.1.....	50
Appendix 6.2.....	51
Appendix 7 Principal Investigator: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo.....	52
Appendix 7.1.....	54
Appendix 8 Principal Investigator: Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez.....	56
Appendix 8.1.....	59
Appendix 9 Principal Investigator: Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion.....	60
Appendix 10 Principal Investigator: Helaine Carrer.....	61
Appendix 11 Principal Investigator: Fernando Luis Cónsoli.....	64
Appendix 12 Principal Investigator: Thais Maria Ferreira de Souza Vieira.....	65
Appendix 12.1.....	66
Appendix 13 Principal Investigator: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira.....	66
Appendix 14 Principal Investigator: Adibe Luiz Abdalla.....	67
Appendix 15 Principal Investigator: Flávio Augusto Portela Santos.....	70
Appendix 16 Principal Investigator: Fabio Ricardo Marin.....	72
Appendix 17 Principal Investigator: Heitor Cantarella.....	75
Appendix 17.1.....	79
Appendix 18 Principal Investigator: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho.....	82
Appendix 19 Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê.....	82
Appendix 19.1.....	107

ABSTRACT

Brazil is one of the world's largest producers and exporters of food, feed, fiber, and (bio)fuels. Estimates indicate that the country would need to increase food production by 40% to meet global demand by 2050. Meanwhile, tropical agricultural systems need to be important allies in sequestering carbon (C) and reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and consequently, contributing to mitigating climate change. Therefore, the challenge is to increase agricultural production while reconciling environmental, social, and economic sustainability. In this context, the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON) was created, based at ESALQ/USP, one of the most respected Agricultural Schools in the world. To achieve CCARBON's goals, strategic, multidisciplinary, and innovative research lines cover five main areas: soil, plants and animals, atmosphere, and digital tools. The center is also incorporated into a large innovation ecosystem to support discoveries and new technologies through institutional-public-private partnerships. We designed several strategies to actively disseminate knowledge and innovations, contributing to farmers and stakeholders adopting more sustainable practices, as well as raising public awareness about low C and supporting public policy development. We expect our world-class research center to keep identifying key challenges and develop and implement solutions to increase sustainable agri-food production from tropical agro-ecosystems, reducing GHG emissions and increasing C sequestration through climate-smart management practices. The objective of this report is to present all the activities carried out in the first year of CCARBON's operation, corresponding to the period from September 1st 2023 to August 31th 2024. The report is divided into three main sections: i) research and development, ii) technological innovation and iii) dissemination. The research and development section highlights the themes of the research lines and their significant scientific advances. The technological innovation section describes the advances in this area, mainly related to the establishment of R&DI partnerships with world class players in the sector. Finally, the dissemination section details activities to promote and share research and innovation through a large set of national and international initiatives.

1 Introduction

In CCARBON's first year of operations, significant advances were made in research, innovation and scientific outreach, laying a solid foundation for the center's future development. In the area of research, CCARBON focused on deepening knowledge about the role of tropical agriculture in carbon capture and mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions. This effort resulted in the publication of several relevant scientific articles, human resources training, and the establishment of strategic partnerships.

The center's research strategy is based on five macro-programs — SOIL, PLANT, ANIMAL, ATMOSPHERE and DIGITAL TOOLS — involving more than 40 researchers, 100 (undergraduate and graduate) students and postdoctoral researchers. Scientific advances in these areas are guided by 19 challenging questions that address complex subjects related to carbon and the climate agenda in the agricultural sector. In its first year of operation, several studies were conducted to better understand the role of tropical agricultural systems in carbon sequestration and greenhouse gas mitigation. These studies have resulted in the publication of articles in high-impact international scientific journals, enhancing CCARBON's reputation as a center of excellence in low-carbon agricultural research. Strategic partnerships with national and international institutions are being established, strengthening the collaboration network and enabling the development of innovative research projects.

In the innovation front, actions strategies include promoting (i) R&DI partnerships with world class players in the sector and (ii) Innovation Ecosystems, (iii) Discovery and Technology, (iv) Entrepreneurship, and (v) Public-Private Partnerships. The innovation activities have been developed in conjunction of the research activities described above, aiming at optimizing the use of knowledge and technologies generated by research projects to solve practical problems of the agricultural sector. Although CCARBON had accomplished an important start with some promising innovation initiatives, the results are still in the early stages. However, CCARBON remains committed to investing efforts in these projects and expects significant contributions to low-carbon tropical agriculture and climate change mitigation in the coming years.

As part of its mission to disseminate knowledge, CCARBON is implementing a comprehensive Scientific Dissemination Plan (SDP) aimed at promoting engagement and awareness on carbon and environmental issues. This includes producing documentaries, organizing events, and creating a multilingual project website. The SDP also involves training courses for teachers, competitions for students, and online courses for rural producers.

Additionally, CCARBON starts the establishment an international network for collaboration, produce podcasts, e-books, and webinars, and publish scientific papers and technical bulletins. The plan also includes advocacy efforts to influence public policy and decision-making, with activities such as virtual meetings with government bodies and participation in international forums.

2 Research scope results

This section aims to present the structure and research lines, as well as the academic activities and researchers and students involved in the first year of CCARBON. Structurally, the research pillar is based on the five macro-programs: SOIL, PLANT, ANIMAL, ATMOSPHERE and DIGITAL TOOLS (Figure 1). Within each program, the specific advances obtained by the Principal Investigators and their team were presented.

Figure 1. Research action strategy from Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture

Table 1 presents the research structure, including its macro-programs - SOIL, PLANT, ANIMAL, ATMOSPHERE and DIGITAL TOOLS - research lines, Principal Investigators, and their respective students. The students highlighted in bold receive scholarships directly from CCARBON. It is important to note that, being the first year of the center's operation, research planning and scholarship allocation are still in progress. The expectation is that scholarships will continue to be implemented in the second year of operation. On the other hand, it is worth noting that most students have external funding, not directly from CCARBON's budget, which reflects the strong tradition of the scientific team in securing other

sources of funding. As CCARBON will need to sustain itself with its own budget in the future, it is important to highlight that, from the first year, the researcher's ability to sustain itself through external funds in addition to CCARBON's funding has been evident.

Table 1. Research structure

SOIL	
Are the Brazilian agricultural soils acting as c sinks or sources?	
Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	Jorge Luiz Locatelli (PhD student FAPESP: 2022/15778-6) Evandro Henrique Figueiredo Moura da Silva (Post-Doc FAPESP: 2022/16715-8) Daniel Aquino De Borba (PhD student) Caroline Andreatto Zanoli (Undergraduate student FAPESP: 2024/06008-8) Gustavo Vicentini Popin (PhD student FAPESP: 2022/07695-3) João Marcos Villela (Post-Doc FAPESP: 2023/09533-3) Marcelo Trybek (Master student FAPESP: 2024/05184-7) Arnold Barbosa de Oliveira (PhD student, no scholarship associated) Valéria Cherubim (Technical Training FAPESP: 2024/05817-0) José Igor Almeida Castro (PhD student - CNPq)
João Luis Nunes Carvalho	Fernanda Palmeira Gabetto (Doctorate – CAPES) Dr Amanda Ronix (Pós-Doc – CNPq)
Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni	Mariana Pezzatte Pollo, MSc. student (grant: FAPESP 2023/04271-0) Tamires Maiara Ercole, Ph.D. Student (grant: FAPESP 2023/14904-0) Bruno Stella, undergraduate student (grant: FAPESP 2024/03712-6)
How changes on the composition and activity of the soil microbiome can be related to the capacity of c sequestration in agriculture systems?	
Fernando Dini Andreote	Ph.D. Student Nariane de Andrade, FAPESP (2022/09977-6) Ph.D. Student Rafael Santana Mendonça (CAPES) Ms Student Alberto Vinicius Sousa Rocha (FAPESP 2022/10276-2) Post-doc. Dr. Felipe Martins do Rêgo Barros, FAPESP (2023/04352-0)
Are there synergies between soil carbon sequestration and soil health and other ecosystem services?	
Maurício Roberto Cherubin	Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior (Postdoctoral – FAPESP # 2023/11337- 8) Graciele Angnes (Postdoctoral - FUSP) Martha Lustosa Carvalho, PhD Candidate (FAPESP Project - #2022/13531-3) Victória Santos Souza (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2022/16368-6) Beatriz da Silva Vanolli, PhD Candidate, FAPESP Project - 2022/14212-9 Chukwudi Nwaogu - Pós-doc FAPESP - 2021/11757-1 Lucas Pecci Canisares (Postdoctoral - FAPESP # 2023/04329-9) Antonio Yan Viana Lima (PhD student – FAPESP # 2024/03722-1) Lucas Tadeu Greschuk (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2023/00438-8) Bruna Emanuele Schiebelbein (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2023/10897-0) Viviana Meneghini (MSc student – FAPESP # 2024/02508-6) Dr. Guilherme Martinelli Sanches (Post Doc candidate - FAPESP # 2024/11109-8)
How to transform degrade soils into climate-smart solutions (upland and wetlands)?	

Tiago Osório Ferreira	Dr Francisco Ruiz (post-doctoral researcher) / grant: FAPESP 2023/06841-9) Douglas Gomes Viana (Post-Doctorate FAPESP 2023/16382-1) Beatriz Marchese Silva (Dr student CAPES 88887.902748/2023-00) Thomas dos Santos Trentin (Dr student CNPq 400761/2021-1)
How to measure the carbon consumed by enhanced weathering (EW) of silicate rock powders (SRP) applied to soil with sufficient certainty for the c capture certification/ carbon credit market?	
Antonio Carlos de Azevedo	Luis Fernando Vieira da Silva (DR student, CAPES) Juliana C. do Nascimento (Dr Student, CAPES) Raissa Razera MSc, FAPESP 2022/15186-1 Aline Vitti Secco (MSc. CAPES) Leonardo Fontoura Trivelim (IC, FAPESP 2024/05622-4)
PLANT	
To what extent do restoration and commercial tree plantations mitigate GHG emissions from agriculture?	
Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez	PD researcher Jomil Costa Abreu Sales (2024/14444-2) DR student Giulia Domingues Pedro (2024/113393-5) MSc student Davi Faiani D'Lippi MSc student Leonardo Costa Peres MSc student Jose Jorge Monteiro Junior
How to restore and measure tropical forest multifunctionality and resilience?	
Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion	PD researcher Juliano van Melis PD researcher Laura Vedovato (2024/03424-0) PD researcher Fábio Matos (2024/07707-7) DR student Ana Paula Ferez IC student João Paulo Oliveira (2024/09791-5)
How to boost the efficiency and rate of carbon fixation by plants?	
Helaine Carrer	Felipe Georgete Scola, MSc student (grant: CAPES) Pedro Boscariol Ferreira, post-doctoral researcher (grant: FAPESP 2022/09094-7) Giovana Carolyn Domingues Saito, MSc student (grant: CAPES) Adolfo Andretto Repache(IC FAPESP 2024/05716-9).
How to exploit the interplay of soil plant insect pest microbiomes in pest management to enhance carbon accumulation, mineralization and sequestration?	
Fernando Luis Cònsoli	Tatiane Aparecida Domingues da Silva (Dr student FAPESP 2023/16516-8) Ana Flávia Freitas Gomes (Post-doctorate FAPESP 2024/10455-0)
Are the agri-food systems prepared to address the changing demands for healthy, low-c emission, and sustainable ingredients in food?	
Thais Maria Ferreira de Souza Vieira	Camila Maria Gonzales (Post-doctorate FAPESP)
ANIMAL	
How grazing management may help to mitigate GHG emissions in pastoral systems of animal production?	
Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira	Dra Alyce Raiana Monteiro dos Santos (Pós doc - FAPESP 2024/00033-0)
How manipulating the microbiome profile in the rumen through feed biomass can mitigate enteric methane in grazing ruminants under tropical conditions?	
Adibe Luiz Abdalla	Pdh Thaynã Gonçalves Timm (PD FAPESP 2024/06301-7) MSc student Jeraldine B. Vasconez (PPG CENA/USP) Laura Bertolaso De Vecchi (DR FAPESP 2024/03777-0)
Which are the impacts of the inclusion of several flint corn ethanol by products available in Brazil, of genetically modified flint corn grain high in alpha amylase, and of flint corn processed through	

different processing methods in diets containing flint corn for feedlot cattle on beef production and GHG emissions?	
Flávio Augusto Portela Santos	Larissa de Melo Coelho (Dr student FAPESP 2023/16439-3) Livia Marques Benez (MS student) Daiana dos Santos Oliveira (Dr student)
ATMOSPHERE	
Which are the possible impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops?	
Fabio Ricardo Marin	Emily Leite (MSc student – CAPES) Dr Henrique Baubab Brunetti (Pós-Doc – FAPESP 2024/02021) Tais Souza (MSc student – CAPES)
DIGITAL TOOLS	
What are the socio-economic impacts of new technologies related to low c agriculture? / What are the economic and environmental impacts of new technologies in the Brazilian agriculture and livestock sectors?	
Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho	<i>in recruiting</i>
Heitor Cantarella	Denizart Bolonhezi (researcher in charge)
How can geotechnologies assist on the diagnostic of carbon impacts on agriculture, environment and climate?	
José Alexandre Melo Demattê	Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín (Post-doc– FAPESP 2023/17508-9) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais (Post-doc– FAPESP 2022/14935-0) Tadeu Fim Rosas (Post-doc– FAPESP 2023/17876-8) Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino (Post-doc– FAPESP 2021/05129-8) Uemeson José dos Santos (Post-doc.) Nicolas Augusto Rosin (PhD student – FAPESP 2021/10063-6) Merylyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim (PhD student – FAPESP 2022/11034-2) Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch (PhD student – FAPESP 2023/11350-4) Borges Marfrann Dias Melo (PhD student – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00) Letícia Guadagnin Vogel (Master student – CAPES 88887.907957/2023-00) Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa (Master student – CAPES 88887.823854/2023-00) Fernando Yutaro Makino (Scientific initiation – FAPESP 2023/13708-3) Matheus Carraco Cardoso (Scientific initiation – CNPq PIBIC -2023) Matheus Fatori (Scientific initiation) Miguel Neves (Scientific initiation – PUB 2973/2023) Samuel Silva de Moraes (Scientific initiation) Aron Müller de Oliveira (Scientific initiation – PUB 3128/2023 Benefício: 83-1)

CCARBON supports some students through scientific initiation scholarships and technical training (Table 2). These projects are still in the early stages (less than 5 or 6 months) and have not yet produced substantial results. However, the work in progress is promising and is expected to contribute significantly to CCARBON's objectives.

Table 2. Scholarships (IC and TT-3) with CCARBON's budget.

Principal Investigator	Scientific Initiation
Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	Caroline Andreatto Zanoli
Fabio Ricardo Marin	Clara Maria de Souza Brandão Fernandes
Principal Investigator	TT-3
Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	Valéria Cherubim
Adibe Luiz Abdalla	Paula Rachel Sprovieri
João Luís Nunes Carvalho	Luiza Cordeiro Boff

CCARBON also collaborates with the following associate professors: Alan Joseph Franzluebbbers, Antonio Augusto Franco Garcia, Carlos Alexandre Costa Crusciol, Carlos Augusto Colombo, Catarina Barbosa Careta, Celso Omoto, CIMÉLIO BAYER, Durval Dourado Neto, Edmilson Moutinho dos Santos, Ernani Pinto Junior, Gerd Sparovek, Italo Delalibera Júnior, Jean Pierre Henry Balbaud Ometto, João Roberto Spotti Lopes, Klaas Metselaar, Leidivan Almeida Frazão, Luis Eduardo Aranha Camargo, Miguel Cooper, Newton La Scala Júnior, Paulo Mazzafera, Ricardo Ribeiro Rodrigues, Sila Carneiro da Silva, Silvia Regina Galleti, Stoécio Malta Ferreira Maia, Suzana Caetano da Silva Lannes, Thiago Libório Romanelli and Tsai Siu Mui.

As part of the CCARBON's activities, we have already held five ordinary meetings of the CCARBON Management Committee, several meetings of the Research, Dissemination and Innovation Directorates and also a productive annual meeting of the International Scientific Advisory Board, which was attended by 11 of the total 12 members of said Committee. During the aforementioned meetings, we identified the need to include some researchers with the current composition of CCARBON team members. Such inclusions of researchers (in the PP and PA categories) and graduate students, if approved by FAPESP, will enable CCARBON activities to function even more intensively for the next years.

Each macro-program and its structure will be presented in more detail below. In this case, the research sublines represented by research questions will be presented first, followed by the Principal Investigator and their subprojects, as well as the research outcomes related to academic publications and other academic activities

2.1 Soil

2.1.1 Are the Brazilian agricultural soils acting as C sinks or sources?

2.1.1.1 Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Main objective:

The main objective is to evaluate soil C removals (C sink) and GHG emissions (C source) due to different land use types and adoption of best agricultural management practices across the country. To do so, we are taking into account assessments under annual crops (soybeans, corn, wheat), semi-perennial crops (sugarcane) and perennial crops (coffee, citrus, pasture). For that, existing long-term experiments and chronosequence-based strategies are being adopted under the main edaphoclimatic conditions in Brazil. In this subsection, the 10 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 1**.

Subproject 1.1 – “What is the impact of cropping intensification strategies on soil organic matter (SOM) dynamics and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the Brazilian Cerrado biome?” is being conducted by *Jorge Luiz Locatelli (PhD student FAPESP: 2022/15778-6)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The objective of this subject is to evaluate the effect of the intensification of agroecosystems in the soil carbon (C) balance and the quality of SOM in the Brazilian Cerrado. Results suggest that diversified cropping systems are a promising strategy for increasing SOC sequestration, and they offer valuable guidance for enhancing current management practices in the region.

As a result, there are two advanced drafts (**Appendix 1.1**):

Jorge Luiz Locatelli, Gustavo Vicentini Popin, Rafael Silva Santos, Wanderlei Bieluczyk, Letícia Thomaz Cipriani, Maurício Roberto Cherubin, Carlos Eduardo Cerri. **A comprehensive assessment of greenhouse gas emissions research in the Cerrado region, Brazil**. Catena (under review)

Jorge Luiz Locatelli, Catherine Stewart, Felipe Bertol, Gustavo Vicentini Popin, João Luís Nunes Carvalho, Matheus Bortolanza Soares, Maurício Roberto Cherubin, Rafael Silva Santos, Sarah Tenelli, Stephen Del Grosso, Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri. **Cropping diversification strategies promote soil aggregation, carbon sequestration and composition changes in the Brazilian Cerrado**. (under preparation)

Subproject 1.2- “How can the CENTURY-based module coupled with DSSAT be improved through detailed evaluation of soil GHG emissions predictions to enhance future simulations of the effects of sustainable agricultural practices on GHG reduction and soil carbon sequestration?” is being conducted by *Evandro Henrique Figueiredo Moura da Silva (Post-*

Doc FAPESP: 2022/16715-8). It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The main goal is to evaluate and improve the predictions of GHG emissions from DSSAT in tropical environments under several crop management to allow the effect of sustainable agricultural practices to be evaluated on reducing GHG emissions from crop fields. Overall, the study confirms the effectiveness of the DSSAT-GHG model in simulating methane emissions and crop performance under varying irrigation practices in a subtropical environment, providing valuable insights for optimizing water use and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in paddy rice cultivation.

As a result, there is an advanced draft, an abstract submission and a poster acceptance (**Appendix 1.2**):

Evandro H Figueiredo Moura da Silva, Gerrit Hoogenboom, Kenneth J Boote, Santiago Vianna Cuadra, Cheryl H Porter, Walkyria Bueno Scivittaro, Silvio Steinmetz, Carlos E. Pellegrino Cerri. **Implications of water management on methane emissions and grain yield in paddy rice: A case study under subtropical conditions in Brazil using crop modeling** (advanced draft)

Evandro Figueiredo Moura da Silva, , Gerrit Hoogenboom , Kenneth J. Boote , Cheryl H. Porter, Carlos E Pellegrino Cerri, . **Performance of the DSSAT in Simulating Greenhouse Gases Emissions Under Soybean-Cotton Cropping Sequence**. CSSA, SSSA International Annual Meeting (abstract submission).

Poster Acceptance Notification - 5th Global Food Security Conference Towards equitable, sustainable and resilient food systems. Title: **Implications of water management on methane emissions and crop yield in paddy rice: A case study in Brazil using the CSM-CERES-Rice** Authors: Evandro Figueiredo Moura da Silva, Santiago Vianna Cuadra, Gerrit Hoogenboom, Kenneth Boote, Cheryl Porter, Walkyria Bueno Scivittaro, Silvio Steinmetz, Carlos Pellegrino Cerri Presenter author: Evandro Figueiredo Moura da Silva

Subproject 1.3 – “Impacts of land use change on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter in production systems under pasture and regenerative agriculture in the subtropical and tropical regions of Brazil” is being conducted by *Daniel Aquino De Borba (PhD student, scholarship from CAPES)*. It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The main goal is to evaluate the impacts of land use change on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter throughout the soil profile in production systems under pasture and regenerative agriculture in the subtropical and tropical region of Brazil. Soil samples were collected in all study areas following an experimental design using a grid sampling method, covering 1 hectare with nine points spaced 50 meters apart. For a more in-depth understanding of the partial results, to facilitate the formulation of hypotheses, it is necessary to submit the results to analysis of

variance and comparison of means, which have not been carried out to date. It is important to highlight that the main objective of the work is subject to adjustments and analyzes throughout the doctorate.

Subproject 1.4 – “Land-use change effects on soil greenhouse gas emissions in the Matopiba region: the new Brazilian agricultural frontier” is being conducted by *Caroline Andreatto Zanoli* (*Undergraduate student FAPESP: [2024/06008-8](#)*). This student has a scholarship from CCARBON’s budget.

Brazil has experienced an accelerated agricultural expansion process in recent decades, with emphasis in the so-called Matopiba region. The objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of land-use change on soil GHG emissions in areas of agricultural expansion in the Matopiba region. The study will be conducted in multiple locations, under the use of native forest and annual crops; the latter under different levels of crop diversification (i.e., successional and rotational systems). The GHG emissions will be monitored for a period of nine months, during the first and the second crop seasons. The fluxes of CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄ gasses will be measured using static chambers, and the daily fluxes will be used to calculate the accumulated emissions. Additionally, the yield-scaled emissions will be calculated based on the system's production history. The data will be submitted to analysis of variance, and when significant, to the Tukey test ($p < 0.05$).

Subproject 1.5 – “Land-use change and agricultural intensification: impacts on carbon and nitrogen distribution in soil profiles of the Amazon-Cerrado frontier” by *Gustavo Vicentini Popin* (*PhD student FAPESP: [2022/07695-3](#)*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

We hypothesized that land-use change and agricultural intensification, such as the double cropping system, alter the vertical distribution of soil C and N stocks in the Amazon-Cerrado frontier by causing significant changes to soil C and N biochemistry in the surface 1 m, consequently altering the large C and N stocks stored from 2 m to 8 m. We sampled in native forest, pasture, soybean cropland, soybean-maize cropland, and an area of forest that was deforested and maintained cleared but never pastured or cropped. We hope that our findings can support decision-makers, politicians, and scientists in international forums, such as COP/UN and help develop strategies to increase soil carbon sequestrations on topsoil and in the deep layers, e.g., achieve Brazilian goals assumed during the COP 21 – Paris agreement.

Subproject 1.6 -“Selection of potential areas and pasture management practices for sequestering carbon in Brazilian soils: a modeling approach” is being conducted by *João Marcos Villela* (*Post-Doc FAPESP: 2023/09533-3*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

This project aims to evaluate different pasture recovery scenarios through mathematical modeling (DayCent and LandSHIFT models), aiming to enhance carbon sequestration in the main agricultural regions of Brazil. To achieve this goal, the following secondary objectives are proposed (achieved in this first year of the project):

- ✓ Develop a geospatial database with data on soil organic carbon stocks (SOC^{stocks}), socioeconomic data and other data that support the construction of pasture recovery scenarios predicted by the proposed modeling approach;
- ✓ Conduct a meta-analysis with data related to SOC^{stocks} in order to measure the effects of pasture management practices on soil carbon accumulation;
- ✓ Select study areas that include the data the models require and preferably located in regions with extensive areas of degraded pastures.

Subproject 1.7 – “Does the conversion of degraded pasture to agriculture based on regenerative practices increase the stock and quality (molecular complexity) of organic carbon in soil aggregates?” is being conducted by *Marcelo Trybek* (*Master student FAPESP: 2024/05184-7*). This student has a scholarship from CCARBON’s budget.

The main goal is to evaluate the impact of land use change by converting degraded pasture into regenerative agriculture on the sequestration and quality of intra-aggregate carbon, glomalin content, and soil health in the Brazilian Cerrado region. This project is in its initial phase, and as such, we do not yet have preliminary results. However, we believe that this work will be pioneering in its detailed study of the soil organic matter (SOM) fractions within aggregate classes, particularly in the context of certified regenerative agriculture. The study will focus on Brazil’s primary agricultural region, which holds particular significance as these areas are agricultural frontiers located in the Cerrado Biome. The strategies and insights generated by this work will have the potential to guide national public policies that are based on a decarbonized economy, such as the ABC+ Program. Furthermore, the results are expected to inspire the widespread adoption of regenerative agriculture, especially for producers interested in the carbon market.

Subproject 1.8 – “Co-inoculation of soybeans with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum*, and inoculation with *Azospirillum* in the corn-brachiaria consortium in succession increase the contribution of C and N to the soil and favor the GHG balance?” is being conducted by *Arnold Barbosa de Oliveira (PhD student, Researcher from Embrapa, no scholarship associated)*

The main goal is to quantify the benefits of continued inoculation and co-inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* in SPD with soybeans, corn and brachiaria in terms of: i) the contribution of C and N to the soil and its effects on the quality and agronomic performance of the system; and ii) the reduction of GHG emissions. The highlights are: 1) The routine establishment of cover crops with brachiaria on corn in succession to soybeans, and inoculations and co-inoculations with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* on these crops can have an impact on enzymatic activity, and the contribution of C and N to the soil, as well as GHG emissions., 2) Inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and co-inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* in soybeans can result in increased yields of soybeans and corn intercropped with brachiaria; 3) Intercropping corn with brachiaria and inoculation with *Azospirillum* can result in increased yields of corn intercropped with brachiaria and soybeans in succession.

Subproject 1.9 – “Support for field measurements on greenhouse gas (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) fluxes in pasture systems in Brazil” is being conducted by *Valéria Cherubim (Technical Training FAPESP: 2024/05817-0)* This student has a scholarship from CCARBON’s budget.

The main objective of this work plan is to support the measurement of greenhouse gas emissions associated with degraded pastures and after their recovery or reform practices under field conditions in Brazil. The results generated here will improve the quality of the default values (IPCC Tier 1 approach), enhancing reliability and accuracy (reducing uncertainties) of this key-category of the Brazilian GHG emission inventory, as well as forming an important basis for national climate policy to achieve the mitigation targets presented at the NDC under the Paris Agreement.

Subproject 1.10 – “C sequestration potential in Brazilian pastures: meta-analysis” is being conducted by *José Igor Almeida Castro (PhD student, scholarship from CNPq)* It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The main objectives of this research are to evaluate the impact of different pasture management systems on SOC stocks in Brazil by conducting a comprehensive systematic review and meta-analysis of existing studies, to analyze the effectiveness of recovering poorly managed pastures in increasing SOC sequestration over time and identify key factors influencing SOC variability in well-managed and integrated production systems. Additionally, the study aims to assess the

role of improved pasture systems in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions in Brazilian pastoral landscapes with C management factor estimates.

2.1.1.2 Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho

In this subsection, the 2 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 2**.

Additional question: Can biochar be a feasible strategy to increase soil C sequestration and mitigate N₂O emissions in tropical soils?

Subproject 1 – “Evaluating the potential of biochar from crop residues as a strategy to mitigate N₂O emissions and boost carbon sequestration in tropical soils” is being conducted by *Fernanda Palmeira Gabetto (Doctorate – CAPES)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The project aims to characterize the physicochemical properties of biochar from different feedstocks and evaluate its effects on soil N₂O emissions, C storage, and soil microbial community diversity.

As a result, there is an advanced draft:

Carvalho, J. L. N.; Gabetto, F.; Tenelli, S.; Netto-Ferreira, J.; Almeida, O.; Martins Junior, J.; Lamas, M.; Strauss, M. **Biochar from crop residues mitigates N₂O emissions and boosts carbon sequestration in tropical soils..** *Journal of Cleaner Production* (under review).

Subproject 2 – “Using process-based models to assess the long-term effects of biochar application on soil carbon sequestration in Brazil” is being conducted by *Dr Amanda Ronix (Post-Doc, scholarship from CNPq)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The project aims to assess the potential of process-based models as a strategy to evaluate the long-term effects of biochar application on soil carbon sequestration.

As a result, there is an advanced draft:

Cerri, C. E. P.; Ronix, A.; Carvalho, J. L. N. **Biochar input in biogeochemical models to simulate soil carbon stocks and changes: a review.** *Biochar* (under review)

To consult the details of advanced drafts **Appendix 2.2**.

2.1.1.3 Principal Investigator: Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni

In this subsection, the 3 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 3**.

Subproject 1 - “Impact of ambient temperature variations on chemical and biological attributes of a soil contaminated by zinc and cadmium and remediated with biochar”, which is being conducted by *Mariana Pezzatte Pollo, MSc. student (grant: FAPESP 2023/04271-0)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

We investigated how temperature and the type of biochar affect the ability to retain toxic substances in mining waste. By varying the temperature and using biochars produced at 350°C and 750°C, we found that temperature played a key role in the mobility of toxic substances. Increases in temperature lead to an increase in the amount of soluble toxic substances and decreased the tailing's ability to retain zinc. Biochar produced at 350°C was less efficient at retaining toxic substances, but it was more resistant to temperature changes. On the other hand, biochar produced at 750°C had a more organized structure and retained more toxic substances, although more sensitive to temperature increases. Biochar produced at 350°C reduced carbon dioxide emissions, while biochar produced at 750°C increased these emissions. These results are important for understanding how biochar can be used to treat mining waste and reduce the associated environmental risks. The information obtained can help to develop more effective strategies to clean up areas contaminated by mining

Subproject 2 - “Chemical and Biological Attributes of Soil and Plant Nutrition in Conventional Pastures and Integrated Crop-Livestock-Forest Systems”, which is being conducted by *Tamires Maiara Ercole, Ph.D. Student (grant: FAPESP 2023/14904-0)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The areas studied have already reached stability and can provide consistent data on the changes caused by land use, considering pasture management types, the presence of trees, and the changes in the soils’ chemical and biological attributes associated with management practices. Furthermore, it is expected that the results will contribute to a better understanding of nutrient availability and cycling in integrated livestock-forest, crop-livestock and crop-livestock-forest (ICLF) systems both eucalyptus and native plants. Similarly, advances in understanding the soil microbial community and its ecosystem functions are anticipated. Finally, the influence of eucalyptus in ICLF systems on soil chemical and biological attributes will also be assessed (undergoing analyses).

Subproject 3 - “Enzymatic activity and CO₂ emission by soil microbiota as a function of ambient temperature variation in an Oxisol under degraded pasture and under crop-livestock-forest integration”, which is being conducted by *Bruno Stella, undergraduate student (grant: FAPESP 2024/03712-6)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

We are evaluating soils collected from long-term experiments; so, it is believed that there is a great chance of obtaining consistent results for changes due to increased ambient temperature (from 20°C to 30°C). It is expected that soils under native forests and crop-livestock-forest integration systems will contain higher amounts of soil carbon, making them more susceptible to CO₂ losses to the atmosphere as temperature increases. In contrast, it is expected that degraded pasture will have a less pronounced response to climate change due to its lower soil carbon content (undergoing analyses).

Publications and Activities:

- Scientific communication:

Mariana Pezzatte Pollo's master's project and Tamires Maiara Ercole's doctoral project were highlighted in the weekly newsletter of SolloAgro, the Program for Continuing Education in Sustainable Agriculture at ESALQ/USP. This publication not only promotes projects related to CCarbon but also highlights the works that have been done to advance sustainability in agriculture, in connection with climate change.

- Master thesis finished:

Pollo, MP. 2024. Master thesis in Soils and Plant Nutrition. **Variations of ambient temperature impacting chemical and biological attributes of a sediment contaminated with zinc and cadmium and remediated with biochar.**

- Poster presented in national scientific event:

Pollo, M. P.; Soares, M. B; Alleoni, L. R. F. **Variation in ambient temperature and immobilization of Zn and Cd in a Technosol amended with sugarcane straw biochar** – 1st CCarbon Symposium. December 8th, 2023, Piracicaba - SP.

Ercole, T. M.; Pollo, M. P.; Stella, B.; Alleoni, L. R. F. **Soil enzymatic activity under conventional pasture and under crop-livestock-forest integration system - CCarbon Soil Health Symposium: from the field to the socioeconomical & political perspectives**, April 24th, 2024, Piracicaba - SP.

2.1.2 How changes on the composition and activity of the soil microbiome can be related to the capacity of C sequestration in agriculture systems?

2.1.2.1 Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote

In this subsection, the 4 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 4**.

Main objective:

How changes in the soil microbiome composition and activity can interfere in the capacity of soil to store carbon? Several links can be proposed in this issue, which must be properly investigated to improve soil management, through the best-possible usage and promotion of microbial activities in soils used for agriculture.

Subproject 1 – “Understand the differential activity of the soil microbial community with the processes of decomposition of organic matter and consequent stabilization of C in different management systems” is being conducted by *Ph.D. Student Nariane de Andrade, FAPESP (2022/09977-6)*, currently developing a BEPE Project at Rothamsted Institute (FAPESP 2024/01300-2). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 2 – “Understand the effects of management variations on productivity gains (and consequent carbon accumulation) attributed to the use of inoculants” is being conducted by *Ph.D. Student Nariane de Andrade, FAPESP (2022/09977-6)* and *Ph.D. Student Rafael Santana Mendonça, CAPES*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 3 – “Determine the participation of microbial necromass in carbon stabilization in soils under different management” is being conducted by *Ms Student Alberto Vinicius Sousa Rocha Mestrado FAPESP (2022/10276-2)* and *Ph.D. Student Rafael Santana Mendonça, CAPES*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 4 – “Explore the interaction between nematodes and bacteria in production systems, and their interconnections with carbon emissions from soils” is being conducted by *Post-doc. Dr. Felipe Martins do Rêgo Barros, FAPESP (2023/04352-0)*, with approved BEPE project to be conducted at Indiana University, in the period of Nov/24 to Oct/25 (FAPESP 2024/07113-0). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

As a result, there is a master thesis publication:

Rocha, AVS. 2024. Master thesis in Soils and Plant Nutrition. **Microbial necromass, carbon and agriculture: combining living and dead microbes to reveal carbon dynamics under agroforestry in the Amazon**

A scientific paper to be submitted:

Rocha, AVS, Buckeridge KM, Alves, AF, Barros, FNR, Melo, ATM, Pimpinato, RF, Tornisielo, VL, Cerri, CEP, Cherubin, MR, Andreote, FD. **Microbial necromass, carbon and agriculture: combining living and dead microbes to reveal carbon dynamics under agroforestry in the Amazon**. Soil Biology and Biochemistry (In final preparation).

And an abstract in international scientific event:

Rocha, AVS, Alves, AF, Melo, ATM, Buckeridge, KM, Cherubin, MR, Andreote, FD. **Necromass, carbon and agriculture: how microbial death is related to persistent carbon in Amazon agroforestry?** 19th ISME Meeting, Cape Town, South Africa, August 2024.

2.1.3 Are there synergies between soil carbon sequestration and soil health and other ecosystem services?

2.1.3.1 Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

In this subsection, the 12 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 5**.

Main objective:

We hypothesize that intensified and diversified agricultural systems that enhance C sequestration (the main focus of CCARBON), improve soil health and have a synergic effect on the provision of other key ecosystem services and of human wellbeing. Although a variety of conceptual frameworks and models have been proposed around the world, a universal approach for evaluating soil health and soil-related ecosystem services under different environmental conditions is still inexistent. In this context, in the CEPID timeframe we will design and develop a multilevel framework for assessing soil health and selected ecosystem services in agricultural systems under contrasting conditions across the country.

Research line: 1 Effect of land use change and sugarcane management on soil C changes, GHG emissions, soil health and associated ecosystem services

Subproject 1.1 – “Effect of land use change and sugarcane management practices on soil C, soil health and associated ecosystem services: an evidence synthesis” is being conducted by *Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior (Postdoctoral – FAPESP # 2023/11337- 8)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Increasing biofuel production to accelerate the energy transition has been widely recognized as the main pathway to achieving net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Given this scenario, Brazil stands out as the world's largest producer of sugarcane and the second-largest producer of bioethanol. This project aims to evaluate the effect of land use changes and sugarcane management practices on soil carbon, soil health and associated ecosystem services, from an evidence synthesis study. Ultimately, we hope that these findings will be useful in guiding decision-making by farmers, investors, stakeholders, and policymakers, promoting progress toward sustainable bioenergy production that contributes to a low-carbon economy and climate change mitigation.

As a result, there is a publication:

Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Canisares, L. P., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). **Soil carbon stocks in sugarcane cultivation: An evidence synthesis associated with land use and management practices.** *GCB Bioenergy*, 16, e13188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.13188> (**Appendix 5.1**).

And an advanced draft:

Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Canisares, L. P., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. **Bioenergy production from sugarcane straw: Implications for soil-related ecosystem services.** (*under review*)

Subproject 1.2 – “Regional N₂O emissions factors in bioethanol crops in Brazil” is being conducted by *Graciele Angnes (Postdoctoral - FUSP)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The challenge of assessing greenhouse gas (GHG) impacts to mitigate emissions in Brazil is particularly significant for the agricultural sector. We conducted a systematic review, analyzing data from 322 measurements across 56 field studies on sugarcane and corn crops in various regions of Brazil, to identify the average N₂O emission factors (EF) and provide a comprehensive overview of EF studies in the country. The global EF values (sugarcane and corn) observed in our study were lower than those reported in other countries, such as India, Costa Rica, Australia, China, and Thailand.

As a result, there is an advanced draft:

Angnes, G., Carvalho J.L.N., Cherubin, M.R. **Regional N₂O emissions factors in bioethanol crops in Brazil: A review.** (*under final preparation*)

Research line: 2 Biodiversification of cropping production systems (cover crops and integrated systems)

Subproject 2.1 – “Soil health and soil-related ecosystem services provision in Brazilian subtropical cropping systems” is being conducted by *Martha Lustosa Carvalho, PhD Candidate (FAPESP Project - #2022/13531-3)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Conventional agricultural systems simplify natural ecosystems to prioritize the production of a single ecosystem service (food, feed, fiber, or fuel production), often at the expense of other services. So far, preliminary results indicate that systems with cover crops during wintertime presented higher cumulative GHG emissions overall, however, we aim to compare treatments by a ratio of total emissions per yield and total energy produced.

As a result, there is an advanced draft:

Carvalho, M.L., Scholten, R.S., Canisares, L.P., Cherubin, M.R. **Cover crops biomass and nutrients inputs in Brazilian agriculture.** (*under review*)

Subproject 2.2 – “Balanço de carbono e saúde do solo em resposta às plantas de cobertura no Cerrado brasileiro” being conducted by *Victória Santos Souza (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2022/16368-6)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Mitigating climate changes and combating food insecurity are the main challenges for humankind in the next decades. Our overall objective is to evaluate the medium- and long-term impact of crop biodiversification using cover crops after soybean cultivation on soil C balance, soil health and crop yields in two key regions of the Brazilian Savannah (Cerrado region). These findings emphasize the role of diversified agroecosystems in improving soil health through soil biological processes with consequences for yield and yield stability in the Brazilian Savannah.

As a result, there is a publication:

Souza, V. S., Vanolli, B. S., Schiebelbein, B. E., Bortolo, L. S., Carvalho, M. L., Mendes, I. C., Cherubin, M. R., 2024. **Cover crops and soil health in Brazilian agricultural systems.** In *Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil (3rd ed., Vol. 3, pp. 1-432)*. John Wiley & Sons. (**Appendix 5.2**).

And an advanced draft:

Souza, V. S., Canisares, L. P., Schiebelbein, B. E., Santos, D. de C., Menillo, R. B., Cherubin, M. R. **Biodiversification enhances soil health, crop yield and resilience.** (*under review*)

Subproject 2.3 – “The role of soil macrofauna in regulating carbon dynamics in integrated agricultural systems” is being conducted by *Beatriz da Silva Vanolli, PhD Candidate, FAPESP Project - 2022/14212-9*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the role of soil macrofauna in regulating carbon dynamics in integrated agricultural systems (IAS) across various regions of Brazil. From these data, we intend to deepen our understanding of the role of macrofauna in soil aggregation, aggregate formation, and carbon storage. These final results, to be completed next semester, will provide additional insights into the complex role of macrofauna in soil carbon sequestration within integrated systems.

Subproject 2.4 – “Assessment of Soil Carbon Stocks in Integrated Agricultural Systems in Brazil: A Geoinformatics Approach” is being conducted by *Chukwudi Nwaogu - Pós-doc*

FAPESP - 2021/11757-1. It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The soil organic carbon (SOC) has the highest terrestrial carbon stock with approximately 1550 Pg of C, equivalent to more than two times the quantity of C stock in vegetation or in the atmosphere. This SOC is vulnerable to diverse activities and land use changes which can either increase or decrease its stock in Brazil due to diverse human activities coupled with the issues of environmental changes. A sustainable system is needed to enhance SOC stocks, increase food security, minimize GHG emissions and mitigate climate change. Integrated agricultural systems (IAS) such as climate-smart agriculture (CSA) including integrated crop-livestock (iCL), and integrated crop-livestock-forestry (iCLF)] are promising agricultural conservation practices for recovering the degraded pasture areas, increase C sequestration, and reduce conversion of native vegetation to agriculture.

As a result, the following publications have been produced (**Appendix 5.3**):

(a) **Integrated agricultural systems: The 21st century nature-based solution for resolving the global FEEES challenges.** published in *Advances in Agronomy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2024.02.003>

(b) **Crop-Livestock-Forest System as Nature-Based Solutions to Combating Climate Change and Achieving SDGs in Brazil.** Published in *Springer Nature*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98067-2_124-1;

(c) **Integrated Agricultural Systems for Enhancing Carbon Stocks and Climate Change Mitigation: Nigeria and Brazil.** Published in *Springer Nature*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98067-2_91-1;

And articles *under review*:

(d) Mapping the research landscape of conservation agriculture as a panacea for achieving soil health and sustainable development goals using scientometrics. Submitted to *Discover Sustainability*;

(e) Soil organic carbon stocks as driven by land use in Mato Grosso State: The Brazilian Cerrado agricultural frontier. Submitted to *Discover Sustainability*;

(f) Land use and Soil C stock changes: a 3-decade State-scale appraisal in São Paulo, Brazil. Submitted to the *International Journal of Environmental Research*.

Subproject 2.5 – “The MONS Project: Mechanisms of Nitrous Oxide Emission in Tropical Soil aims to address critical issues related to the sustainability of tropical agriculture” is being conducted by *Lucas Pecci Canisares (Postdoctoral - FAPESP # 2023/04329-9)*. It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The focus is on the importance of increasing food production sustainably, with a particular emphasis on mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This study examined how the composition of cover crops determines the abundance of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) and archaea (AOA) in agroecosystems, and how different abundances alter N₂O emissions. These findings suggest that cover crop selection influences key microbial groups and N₂O emissions, emphasizing the importance of considering cover crop species in agroecosystems to optimize nitrogen cycling and improve sustainability.

As a result, there is an advanced draft:

Canisares, L.P., Hazard, C., Nicol, G., Bouskill, N., Cherubin, M.R. **Cover crop groups influence the abundance of ammonia-oxidizing microorganisms of agricultural soils.**

Research line: 3 Soil health in the semi-arid environment (desertification, restoration, integrated systems)

Subproject 3.1 – “Soil health assessment in desertified drylands in Brazil” is being conducted by *Antonio Yan Viana Lima (PhD student – FAPESP # 2024/03722-1)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The project addresses the degradation of drylands in northeastern Brazil, particularly in desertification nuclei, due to land use changes and the advance of climate change. The results will provide valuable data to develop strategies and policies against desertification, reducing climate vulnerability and improving food security. Previous studies have shown that reclaimed areas in the Irauçuba desertification nucleus have seen a significant increase in soil health to levels similar to those in areas of native Caatinga vegetation, indicating that the adoption of techniques adapted to the reality of the Brazilian Semiarid region is the key to increasing the productivity and sustainability of these areas.

As a result, the following publications have been produced

Lima, A.Y.V., Cherubin, M.R., Silva, D.F., Mota, J.C.A., Silva, F.G.M., Araujo, A.S.F., Melo, V.M.M., Verma, J.P., Pereira, A.P.A. **Grazing exclusion restores soil health in Brazilian drylands under desertification process**, *Applied Soil Ecology*, v. 193, 105107, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2023.105107> (Appendix 5.4).

Araujo, A.S.F., Pereira, A.P.A., Pereira, A.P.A., Lima, A.Y.V., Melo, V.M.M., Medeiros, E.V., Mendes, L.W. **A desertificação e a saúde do solo no bioma Caatinga**. In: Nogueira, T.A.R., Cherubin, M.R., Pereira, A.P.A., Tiecher, T. (Org.). *Tópicos em Ciência do Solo (XII)*. 1 ed. Viçosa: Sociedade Brasileira de Ciência do Solo, 2023, v. 1, p. 7-23

The following article under review:

Lima, A.Y.V., Cherubin, M.R., Greschuk, L.T., Muniz, G.A.M., Cavalcante, D.M., Pereira, A.P.A. **Unrevealing soil health research in the Brazilian Semi-arid region: a bibliometric approach**. *Experimental Agriculture*, 2024 (under review).

And an advanced draft (*under review*):

Lima, A.Y.V., Greschuk, L.T., Villela, J.M., Muniz, G.A.M., Cherubin, M.R. **Effectiveness of degradation recovery techniques in drylands: a meta-analysis approach**. Advanced draft.

Subproject 3.2 – “Soil carbon sequestration under integrated agricultural systems in Brazilian drylands” is being conducted by *Lucas Tadeu Greschuk (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2023/00438-8)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Land use change and soil organic matter (SOM) loss in agricultural areas are the activities that contribute most to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Brazil. The objective of this project is to evaluate the change in soil C stock in integrated agricultural systems in the Brazilian dryland region, providing recommendations for land management and the development of public policies. The main findings were that there is a possibility of increasing SOC stock through the recovery of degraded pastures in the study region. There are no observations of studies that evaluated SOC stock in semi-arid climate areas. Future results will be derived from analyzing data collected in the field and modeling for future scenarios.

And an advanced draft (*under review*):

Greschuk, L.T., Villela, J. M., Maia, S. M. F., Pinheiro Junior, C. R.; Tonucci, R. G., Signor, D., Frazão, L. A., Lima, A. Y. V., Canisares, L. P., Queiroz, H. M., Cerri, C. E. P., Cherubin, M. R. **Soil carbon storage in Brazilian drylands: A review**. Advanced draft. (**Appendix 5.5**).

Research line: 4 Methodological advances in soil health for application in agriculture

Subproject 4.1 – “Development of on-farm and computational tools for assessing soil health in Brazilian croplands” is being conducted by *Bruna Emanuele Schiebelbein (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2023/10897-0)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Evaluating and enhancing soil health is essential for ensuring agricultural systems are more productive and resilient. To conduct comprehensive soil health assessments in Brazil, it is imperative to develop on-farm and advanced computational approaches. In this project, our goal is to develop tools (on-farm and computational approaches) to assess soil health in Brazilian agricultural areas. The analysis revealed significant variances in soil health indicators across different Brazilian biomes, based on the integration of five soil health indicators: soil

carbon, phosphorus, potassium, bulk density, and pH. SMAF's findings underscore the inherent influence of climate and soil characteristics on soil health. These insights highlight Brazil's central role in promoting soil health and advocating for sustainable agricultural practices globally.

As a result, the following publications have been produced:

Schiebelbein, B. E.; Cherubin, M. R. Method for assessing soil health and its use. Application Number: BR 10 2024 015629 3. Filing Date: 30 Jul. 2024

Schiebelbein, B. E.; Cherubin, M. R. Field User Guide for the SOHMA Soil Health Kit. University of São Paulo. Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391557>. 2024. Available at: <https://www.livrosabertos.abcd.usp.br/portaldelivrosUSP/catalog/book/1311> (**Appendix 5.6**).

Subproject 4.2 – “Avaliação da saúde do solo em áreas agrícolas no Sul do Brasil: uma abordagem utilizando múltiplas metodologias e escalas de aplicação” is being conducted by *Viviana Meneghini* (*MSc student – FAPESP # 2024/02508-6*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Climate change adaptation management solutions that improve soil health are key strategies for achieving production stability and making the productive environment more resilient. The SOHMA Soil Health Kit is a simple tool that can be applied in the field. This study seeks to evaluate soil health in agricultural areas in southern Brazil with contrasting management systems using multiple methodologies and application scales. In addition, management practices that improve soil health are expected to result in greater productivity.

Subproject 4.3 – “STRATIFICATION OF SOIL SAMPLING USING SPATIO-TEMPORAL SOIL AND PLANT MAPPING TECHNOLOGIES: bases for defining the uncertainties and scalability of the assessment (baseline and monitoring) of soil carbon stocks” is being conducted by *Dr. Guilherme Martinelli Sanches* (*Post Doc candidate - FAPESP # 2024/11109-8*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Assessing soil carbon stocks (SCE) to characterize the baseline and then monitoring (MRV - monitoring, registration and verification) the impacts of the management practices adopted is a process that requires intensive soil sampling in the field, making the process time-consuming, expensive and not very scalable. The main objective of this research project is to assess whether the design of homogeneous management zones (HMZ) allows for adequate stratification of the crop for characterizing the soil C stocks (baseline and monitoring), bringing improvements

in estimates (reduction of uncertainties) and economic advantages compared to traditional sampling methodologies in dense grids.

2.1.4 How to transform degrade soils into climate-smart solutions (upland and wetlands)?

2.1.4.1 Principal Investigator: Tiago Osório Ferreira

In this subsection, the subprojects of the 2 areas (Blue Carbon and Climate Smart Soils) will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 6**.

Blue Carbon

Research Question:

How will climate change and deforestation impact blue carbon soil dynamics?

Main objective:

To investigate the nature and stability of interactions between iron and organic matter in preserved mangroves and mangroves impacted by extreme climate events.

Subproject 1 – “Impact of Extreme Weather on Iron-Mediated Organo-Mineral Interactions in Mangrove Soils”

Dr Francisco Ruiz (post-doctoral researcher) / grant: FAPESP 2023/06841-9). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

All laboratory analyses have been completed, including carbon and nitrogen determination, isotopic analyses, wet-chemical fractionation, differential calorimetry, Rock-Eval thermal analysis, and pyrolysis coupled with gas chromatography and mass spectrometry. A comprehensive dataset on iron (Fe) and soil organic carbon (SOC) from mangroves along the Brazilian coast has been compiled. Modeling shows that Fe-SOC associations contribute significantly to total SOC (10-40%) and that the SOC associated with reactive Fe is a labile pool, subject to constant recycling. However, these associations are highly vulnerable to land-use changes, which can alter Fe geochemistry and reduce the Fe-SOC pool.

Scientific Publications (Appendix 6.1):

One paper is currently under review in Nature Communications (doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4650556/v1).

Two additional papers are in the final stages of editing and will be submitted soon (targeted journals: Nature Communications/ Nature Geoscience/ STOTEN).

CLIMATE SMART SOILS

How to transform degraded soils into climate-smart solutions?

Main objective:

To evaluate different types of waste for the restoration of degraded areas, aiming to restore soil functioning, including plant production and soil carbon sequestration.

Subproject 2 – “Iron mining tailings as a soil amendment and in the construction of smart-C soils: smart agriculture against climate change and soil degradation” (*FAPESP Research Program on Global Climate Change / PFPMCG - Research Project - Regular - Climate Change: Land Use - 2023/02429-6*).

Subproject 2.1 – “The use of mining waste and construction waste for the creation of smart soil: a sustainable approach to mitigate climate change.”
Douglas Gomes Viana (Post-Doctorate FAPESP 2023/16382-1) It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 2.2 – “Technosols as a nature-based solution: integrating solid waste for regenerative agriculture and climate change mitigation”
Beatriz Marchese Silva (Dr student CAPES 88887.902748/2023-00) It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Project Progress Summary: The project aims to evaluate the initial establishment of organic matter stabilization mechanisms in Technosols constructed from a mixture of iron mining tailings and civil construction waste in different proportions where the tropical grass species *Urochloa brizantha* cv. Marandu was cultivated. The Technosols were compared to natural soil (Haplic Ferralsol) to assess the ability of the artificial soils to promote ecosystem services.

Publications (Appendix 6.2):

The group has already submitted a manuscript in Land Degradation and Development.

Subproject 2 – “Exploring the organic carbon stabilization mechanisms of remineralizers: strategies to sequester carbon and benefit soil organic matter in agricultural systems”
Thomas dos Santos Trentin (Dr student CNPq 400761/2021-1). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Project Progress Summary: The project aims to explore the processes of organic carbon stabilization via organo-mineral interactions with different rock powders (RPs) in order to

outline their uses in agricultural systems as enhancers of carbon sequestration in the soil, through two experimental approaches. The first consists of measuring, in laboratory, the nature and potential of RPs to promote carbon stabilization and the impact of the rhizosphere in this context of rock weathering and carbon sequestration, and the second tests, in greenhouse, the potential for increases in the stabilization of C in soils of different textural classes conditioned RP. Thus, an update on the conduct of the work follows:

2.1.5 How to measure the carbon consumed by enhanced weathering (EW) of silicate rock powders (SRP) applied to soil with sufficient certainty for the C capture certification/ carbon credit market?

2.1.5.1 Principal Investigator: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo

In this subsection, the 3 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 7**.

Research Question:

How to measure the carbon consumed by enhanced weathering (EW) of silicate rock powders (SRP) applied to soil with sufficient certainty for the C capture certification/ carbon credit market?

Main objective:

Improve Measurement, Report and Verification (MRV) in the Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW) path for inorganic Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR). In addition, increase the public awareness for climate change and carbon economy via the establishment of an Educational Station, the EDUCARBON Project, both in formal (schools) and non-formal environments.

Subproject 1 – “Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) using Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW) of in basic rocks” is being conducted by *Luis Fernando Vieira da Silva (DR student, CAPES)* and *Juliana C. do Nascimento (Dr Student, CAPES)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 2 – Increase of the resilience of sandy soils towards the climate change using K-clays from mine waste is being conducted by *Raissa Razera MSc, FAPESP 2022/15186-1; BEPE 2023/12915-5 University of Newcastle – UK*, *Aline Vitti Secco (MSc. CAPES)* and *Leonardo Fontoura Trivelim (IC, FAPESP 2024/05622-4)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 3 –EDUCARBON: expanding public awareness about climate change and carbon economy

As a result, the following publications have been produced (**Appendix 7.1**):

Manning, D. A. C., de Azevedo, A. C., Zani, C. F., & Barneze, A. S. (2024). **Soil carbon management and enhanced rock weathering: The separate fates of organic and inorganic carbon.** *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(4), e13534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13534>

Santos, R. A., Reis, B. R., Azevedo, A. C., & Sermarini, R. A. (2023). **Potential Errors in Cation Exchange Capacity Measurement in Soils Amended with Rock Dust: Two Case Studies.** *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 55(3), 329–342. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00103624.2023.2268650>

Azevedo, A. C; Manning, D. A. C.(2024) **A proposal to clarify the use of Sum of Bases in the Brazilian Remineralizer Regulation and in Soil Science.** *Rev. Bras. Ciênc. Solo*.2023;47:e0220053. DOI: 10.36783/18069657rbc20220053

2.2 Plant

2.2.1 This study aims to answer the question: to what extent do restoration and commercial tree plantations mitigate GHG emissions from agriculture?

2.2.1.1 Principal Investigator: Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez

In this subsection, the 8 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 8**.

Main objective:

The main objective is to understand the processes underlying agriculture's greenhouse gas emissions and determine whether restoration and commercial tree plantations contribute positively to the net balance as a carbon sequestration subsystem.

Subprojects

One doctoral student and one post-doc researcher are being recruited to work on subprojects directly funded by CCARBON. Two parallel research strategies have been used to examine related questions regarding the role of forest plantations as provisioners of ecosystem services: supplementary studies financed by FAPESP, and related studies supported by other funding sources.

Directly funded by CCARBON.

Subproject 1

Development of Decision Support Systems for Conflicting Objectives to Improve Governance of Production, Conservation, Restoration, and Sustainable Ecosystem Services: The project aims to evaluate global multicriteria forest plantation management approaches that identify consensus solutions for diverse stakeholders and adapt these decision support systems to

PD

researcher

In recruiting phase

Brazilian contexts, emphasizing ecosystem services and carbon sequestration.

Subproject 2

Using Active and Passive Sensors from Ground and Orbital Platforms for Estimating Aboveground Biomass and Carbon: the main objective is to evaluate the potential of remote sensing approaches to derive precise estimates of the aboveground biomass of forest plantations.

DR student

In recruiting phase

Supplementary studies funded by FAPESP.

Linked to Thematic Project 2021/00833-9 (DecisionES-BR) Decision Support for the Supply of Ecosystem Services under Global Change

Subproject 3

New approaches to support the decision-making process for stakeholders and policymakers involving forests, water, and biodiversity: the main objective is to model decision-support systems capable of dealing with the interaction between forests and hydrological processes under the impacts of climate and land-use change, mainly in the State of São Paulo, Brazil.

PD researcher

Jomil Costa
Abreu Sales
(2024/14444-2)
15/Oct/2024 a
14/Jun/2028

Subproject 4

Accounting for hydrological services on the design and development of decision support systems for forest managers and policymakers: the main objective is to model decision support systems capable of dealing with the interaction between forests and hydrological processes under the impacts of climate and land-use change, mainly in the State of São Paulo, Brazil.

DR student

Giulia
Domingues
Pedro
(2024/13393-5)
01/Sep/2024 a
29/Feb/2028

Subproject 5

Modeling Decision Support Systems for Ecosystem Services of Forests Under Global Change: the doctoral candidate awarded this grant will focus on modeling decision support systems to manage the complexity of large-scale restoration program planning across various ecosystems, primarily in the state of São Paulo, Brazil.

DR student

In recruiting phase
[Link to the call for candidates](#)

Related studies supported by other funding sources.

Subproject 6

Identifying Hotspots for Afforestation, Reforestation, and Regeneration Projects in Brazil: this master student work seeks to identify the most favorable types of forests and locations in Brazil for developing afforestation, reforestation, and regeneration projects, driven by a clear market demand for high-quality credits.

MSc student

Davi Faiani
D'Lippi
14/Jul/2023 a
15/Set/2025

Subproject 7

Using Unconventional Methods and LiDAR for Calculating Planted Tree Volume: The work of this master student aims to test the following hypotheses: Can models that estimate tree volume using cross-sectional area at heights above breast height (DBH) provide results that are statistically equal to or better than conventional models? Are LiDAR data reliable estimators of dendrometric variables and volume in commercial plantations?.

MSc student

Leonardo
Costa Peres
15/Jul/2022 a
16/Set/2024

Subproject 8

Impact of Precipitation Pattern Changes on Total Area and Biomass of

MSc student

Jose Jorge

the Atlantic Forest and Caatinga: This master's student uses publicly available GEDI LiDAR data from the International Space Station, multispectral data from Sentinel-1 and -2 satellites, and precipitation data to evaluate how above-ground vegetation structure varies with rainfall changes, transitioning from Atlantic Forest to semiarid regions. Monteiro Junior 08/Fev/2022 a 14/Out/2024

Scientific publications (Appendix 8.1):

Papers

Nobre, Silvana, Marc McDill, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez, and Luis Diaz-Balteiro. 2023. "A General Rule-Based Framework for Generating Alternatives for Forest Ecosystem Management Decision Support Systems" *Forests* 14, no. 9: 1717. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14091717>

Nobre, Silvana, Marc McDill, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez, and Luis Diaz-Balteiro. 2024. "Reframing the Model I, II and III harvest scheduling formulations in the context of managing forests for ecosystem services". *In review*

Participation in an international conference

McDill M; Nobre SR; Rodriguez LC; Diaz-Balteiro L (2024) Model N: A New Linear Programming Formulation for Forest Ecosystem Management Planning. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 62.

Nobre SR; Guerin N; Zakia MJ; von Glehn HC; Rodriguez LCE (2024) Simulation and multicriteria analysis to generate multispecies combinations to support ReflorestaSP program: An Essential Component of São Paulo's Climate Action Plan. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 67.

Nobre SR; McDill M; Rodriguez LC; Diaz-Balteiro L (2024) Evaluating Formulations and Efficacy of Models I, II, and N in Ecosystem Services Management. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 68.

Ferraz SFB; Franzoni A; Rodriguez LCE; Nobre SR (2024) Sustainable Management of Eucalyptus Plantations in Brazil: Balancing Economics and Water-Related Ecosystem Services. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 38.

Ferreira MP (2024) Estimating aboveground biomass of individual urban tree with hyperspectral and LiDAR data. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 39.

Nascimento N; Brancalion P (2024) Assessing Fire Risk in the Brazilian Atlantic Forest: A Bayesian Spatial Analysis Approach. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 66.

These contributions were orally presented at the 20th Symposium on Systems Analysis in Forest Resources (SSAFR 2024) held in Hondarribia, Basque Country, Spain, and can be accessed at <https://decisiones.ctfc.cat/SSAFR2024/program-map-abstracts/>

2.2.2 How to restore and measure tropical forest multifunctionality and resilience?

2.2.2.1 Principal Investigator: Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion

In this subsection, the research will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 9**.

Main objective:

To understand the socio-ecological drivers of forest multifunctionality recovery by different reforestation approaches

Students: PD researcher Juliano van Melis, PD researcher Laura Vedovato (2024/03424-0), PD researcher Fábio Matos (2024/07707-7), DR student Ana Paula Ferez and IC student João Paulo Oliveira (2024/09791-5). It is important to note that these researcher's scholarship are funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Highlights

- 1- conclusion of field data collection, analysis, and organization of nearly 800 30x30m plots established in forests restored by different methods (natural regeneration, restoration plantations, agroforestry, monocultures with regeneration, monocultures without regeneration, degraded forests, conserved forests, agropastoral land uses);
- 2- conclusion of lidar data collection, analysis, and organization of nearly 500.000 ha
- 3- DAG models (example Fig.1) prepared preliminary results obtained for different research lines (carbon, water, soil, timber production, biodiversity)

2.2.3 How to boost the efficiency and rate of carbon fixation by plants?

2.2.3.1 Principal Investigator: Helaine Carrer

In this subsection, the 4 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 10**.

Main objective:

To manipulate and exploit the biochemical potential of plants to improve efficiency of photosynthesis to increase crop yield while maintaining atmospheric carbon balance.

The Subproject 1 - is "Functional Genomics of genes related to the Light-dependent reactions (Photosystems I and II) to improve photosynthesis efficiency". This subproject has not been initiated yet since it depends on a student who will be selected to analyze the data produced by *Prof. Marcos Buckeridge (IB-USP)*.

The Subproject 2 - "Point mutations in the *rbcL* gene in the chloroplast genome aiming the improvement of photosynthesis efficiency", which is being conducted by *Felipe Georgete Scola, MSc student (grant: CAPES) and Pedro Boscarior Ferreira, post-doctoral researcher*

(grant: FAPESP 2022/09094-7).). It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The Subproject 3 - "Genetic Pathways from extremophile plants to improve abiotic stress tolerance and photosynthesis efficiency in cultivated plants", which is being conducted by *Giovana Carolyn Domingues Saito, MSc student (grant: CAPES) and Pedro Boscarior Ferreira (mentioned in the Subproject 2 above)*. It is important to note that these scholarships are funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

The Subproject 4 - "Duckweed Biomass Production", which is being conducted by *Pedro Adolfo Andretto Repache, Agronomy student (IC FAPESP 2024/05716-9)*. It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

2.2.4 How to exploit the interplay of soil plant insect pest microbiomes in pest management to enhance carbon accumulation, mineralization and sequestration?

2.2.4.1 Principal Investigator: Fernando Luis Cônsoli

In this subsection, the 4 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 11**.

Main objective:

Identify how pest management strategies can affect carbon accumulation, mineralization and sequestration

Subproject 1 – Interação multinível da microbiota do solo - planta - herbívoro no sistema milho e lagarta-do-cartucho sob o efeito de inseticidas com atividade antimicrobiana
Student Name: Tatiane Aparecida Domingues da Silva (Dr student FAPESP 2023/16516-8) - started 01/02/2024. This student has a scholarship from CCARBON's budget.

Subproject 2 – A interferência de inseticidas contaminantes do solo na diversidade e abundância das comunidades de solo e no pool de carbono associado
Student Name: Ana Flávia Freitas Gomes (Post-doctorate FAPESP 2024/10455-0) – started 01/08/2024. This student has a scholarship from CCARBON's budget.

2.2.5 Are the agri-food systems prepared to address the changing demands for healthy, low-C emission, and sustainable ingredients in food?"

2.2.5.1 Principal Investigator: Thais Maria Ferreira de Souza Vieira

In this subsection, the subproject will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 12**.

Main objective:

Development of processes for the recovery of bioactive compounds from agro-industrial waste, considering all stages of the process—from the extraction of bioactive compounds using environmentally friendly technologies to the application of novel ingredients in food systems.

Subproject 1 – The objective of the overall project is to develop sustainable processes for recovering active compounds from avocado processing waste.

Student: *Camila Maria Gonzales (Post-doctorate FAPESP)*. This student has a scholarship from CCARBON's budget.

Progress:

The phenolic compounds present in the extracts after optimization were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The identified compounds were gallic acid, catechin, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, 3,4-hydroxybenzoic acid, caffeic acid, and p-coumaric acid. The extracts obtained under the previously described conditions were microencapsulated and analyzed for their physicochemical, morphological, and antioxidant capacity characteristics. Application tests in lipid systems indicated the efficiency of the microparticles in preventing the progression of oxidation in the samples during accelerated tests. The results obtained indicate that the aqueous optimization strategy followed by the encapsulation of the extracts allowed for the adjustment of process parameters that enabled the protection of active compounds using sustainable and low-cost technologies.

Scientific Publications (Appendix 12.1):

Optimizing byproduct processing for clean label foods: Avocado and MSM-Tambaqui with a focus on zero waste. *Journal of Food Safety*. DOI: 10.1111/jfs.13160

2.3 Animal

2.3.1 How grazing management may help to mitigate GHG emissions in pastoral systems of animal production?

2.3.1.1 Principal Investigator: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira

In this subsection, the subproject will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 13**.

Main objective:

To better understand the impact on GHG emissions and C sequestration in the intensive ruminant production systems, including improved pasture management practices.

Subproject 1 – “Resilience of integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems to climate change in the Amazon Biome”

Dra Alyce Raiana Monteiro dos Santos (Pós doc - FAPESP 2024/00033-0). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

This project is linked to the Animal as a “Projeto Balcão”, and we will use data from a field experiment conducted in the Amazon biome, evaluating four systems: livestock, livestock-forestry, crop-livestock, and crop-livestock-forestry. Global circulation models and Representative Concentration Paths will be used to create climate change scenarios. The APSIM model will be used to simulate forage, soybean, and maize production scenarios. System resilience will be evaluated considering aspects of productivity and production resistance. With model validation and simulations of future climate scenarios, we will propose practical guidelines that can inform new public policies for the agricultural sector.

2.3.2 How manipulating the microbiome profile in the rumen through feed biomass can mitigate enteric methane in grazing ruminants under tropical conditions?

2.3.2.1 Principal Investigator: Adibe Luiz Abdalla

In this subsection, the 3 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 14**.

Main objective:

To evaluate the potential of innovative strategies involving the use of biomass, tropical algae, and biochar in reducing the environmental impact of ruminant livestock production by mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, enhancing feed efficiency, conserving ecosystems, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices

Subproject 1 – Stable isotopes in the determination of greenhouse gasses from integrated systems: in vivo and in vitro approaches is being conducted by *Thaynã Gonçalves Timm (PD FAPESP 2024/06301-7* - This student has a scholarship from CCARBON’s budget.) and collaborated closely with *MSc student Jeraldine B. Vasconez (PPG CENA/USP* - It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON) on the project titled “Impact of tithonia diversifolia inclusion on ruminant rumen microbiota: an approach using in vitro continuous rumen fermentation technique”. Together, they have been developing a long-term in vitro incubation system, with progress presented at the 58th Annual Meeting of the Brazilian Society of Animal Science (August 12–16, 2024).

Subproject 2 – Forage biomass of *Tithonia diversifolia* associated with different agro-industrial co-products in sheep feed: potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions is being conducted by *Laura Bertolaso De Vecchi (DR FAPESP 2024/03777-0)*. It is important to note

that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 3 – Manipulation of rumen fermentation through supplementation with cultivated seaweeds is being conducted by FEALQ 896 Research project: The objective of this research is to investigate tropical macroalgae cultivated along the Brazilian coast for their potential use in ruminant production systems.

This research is financially supported by Instituto BKK (iBKK) under the Cooperation Agreement “Acordo de Cooperação Acadêmica Nacional entre a Universidade de São Paulo e o Instituto Bkk – Bonfarto Kaj Konservado.”

2.3.3 Which are the impacts of the inclusion of several flint corn ethanol by products available in Brazil, of genetically modified flint corn grain high in alpha amylase, and of flint corn processed through different processing methods in diets containing flint corn for feedlot cattle on beef production and GHG emissions?

2.3.3.1 Principal Investigator: Flávio Augusto Portela Santos

In this subsection, the 3 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 15**.

Main objective:

The main objective of this project is to evaluate if and how strategies to increase the energy density of diets for finishing beef cattle, such as the feeding of flint corn ethanol byproducts, the feeding of genetically modified flint corn grain high in alpha amylase and grain processing methods, affect the efficiency of nutrient utilization, the performance of beef cattle and the emissions of GEE.

Subproject 1 – “Inclusion of dried distillers' *grains* with solubles (DDGS) in feedlot diets containing flint corn: metabolism and performance of finishing Nellore bulls” is being conducted by *Larissa de Melo Coelho (Dr student FAPESP 2023/16439-3)*). It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON. is important to note that these researcher's scholarship are funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 2 – “Inclusion of dried distillers' *grains* with solubles in feedlot diets containing flint corn and citrus pulp: metabolism and performance of finishing Nellore bulls” is being conducted by *Livia Marques Benez (MS student)*). It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 3 – Comparison of genetically modified high amylase flint corn (Enogen Flint Corn) with conventional flint corn on “in vitro” rumen fermentation, dry matter disappearance, gas and methane production is being conducted by *Daiana dos Santos Oliveira (Dr student)*). It is important to note that this researcher's scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

2.4 Atmosphere

2.4.1 Which are the possible impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops?

2.4.1.1 Principal Investigator: Fabio Ricardo Marin

In this subsection, the 3 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 16**.

Main objective:

To analyze and quantify the potential impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops, identifying key vulnerabilities and adaptation strategies to ensure sustainable agricultural productivity in the future.

Subproject 1 – “Impact assessment of climate change on sugarcane yield in Brazil” is being conducted by *Emily Leite (MSc student – CAPES)*. The project aims to analyze the global sensitivity of genotype and soil parameters in a sugarcane model across diverse production environments in Brazil.). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 2 – “Impact assessment of climate change on pastures growth and development in Brazil” will be conducted by *Dr Henrique Baubab Brunetti (Pós-Doc – FAPESP 2024/02021-0)* - Not yet started, but the scholarship holder has been hired and began activities in September 2024.). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 3 – “Impact assessment of climate change on maize growth and development in Brazil” is being conducted by *Tais Souza (MSc student – CAPES)*.). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

2.4.2 Which are the possible impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops?

2.4.2.1 Principal Investigator: Heitor Cantarella

In this subsection, the subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 17**.

Main objective:

Study the effect of crop rotation in Bioenergy crops and its contributions fo overall system sustainability

Subproject 2. “No-tillage for Sugarcane-Peanut Crop Rotation System”

Denizart Bolonhezi (researcher in charge)

Peanut is the second cash crop cultivated in the renovation of sugarcane fields. Despite the many benefits of peanuts, soil erosion is the most important challenge in this rotation because of soil disturbance at planting. In the peanuts cycle, the highest soil strength values were observed in no-tillage measured before planting, at flowering, and before and after harvesting, compared with conventional tillage. In the present research, no differences were verified in soil bulk density and porosity. The differences in soil penetration resistance among the treatments diminished from planting to the end of the cycle. Furthermore, conservation practices with low soil disturbance and maximum straw soil cover significantly increased available water capacity and reduced the incidence and severity of virus (GRSV) on peanut plants.

Publications:

Martini, A. F.; Valani, G. P.; Silva, L. F. S.; Paula, S.; Bolonhezi, D.; Cooper, M. (2023) Soil physical quality response to management systems in a long-term sugarcane trial. *Land Degradation & Development*, v. 34, p. 17

Oliveira, I.N.; Souza, Z.M.; Bolonhezi, D.; Totti, M.C.V.; Moraes, M.T.; Lovera, L.H.; Lima, E.S.; Esteban, D.A.A.; Oliveira, C.F. (2022). Tillage systems impact on soil physical attributes, sugarcane yield, and root system propagated by pre-sprouted seedlings. *Soil & Tillage Research*, v. 223, p. 105460.

De Lima, C.C.; De Maria, I.C.; Guimarães Júnnyor, W. S.; Figueiredo, G.C.; Dechen, S.C.F.; Bolonhezi, D. (2022). Root parameters of sugarcane and soil compaction indicators under deep strip tillage and conventional tillage. *Scientific Reports*, v. 12, p. 18537.

Martini, A. F.; Valani, G. P.; Silva, L. F. S.; Bolonhezi, D.; Prima, S. Di; Cooper, M. (2021). Long-term trial of tillage systems for sugarcane: Effect on topsoil hydrophysical attributes. *Sustainability*, v. 13, p. 3448.

Cantarella, H., Leal Silva, J. F., Nogueira, L. A. H., Maciel Filho, R., Rossetto, R., Ekbom, T., Souza, G. M., and Mueller-Langer, F. (2023). Biofuel technologies: Lessons learned and pathways to decarbonization. *GCB Bioenergy* **15**, 1190-1203.

Cherubin, M. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Cerri, C. E. P., Nogueira, L. A. H., Souza, G. M., and Cantarella, H. (2021). Land use and management effects on sustainable sugarcane-derived bioenergy. *Land* **10**, 72.

Galdos, M. V., Soares, J. R., Lourenço, K. S., Harris, P., Zeri, M., Cunha-Zeri, G., Vargas, V. P., Degaspari, I. A. M., and Cantarella, H. (2023). Multi-experiment assessment of soil nitrous oxide emissions in sugarcane. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* **127**, 375-392.

Oliveira, B. G., Lourenço, K. S., Carvalho, J. L. N., Gonzaga, L. C., Teixeira, M. C., Tamara, A. F., Soares, J. R., and Cantarella, H. (2023). New trends in sugarcane fertilization:

Implications for NH₃ volatilization, N₂O emissions and crop yields. *Journal of Environmental Management* **342**, 118233.

Rossetto, R., Ramos, N. P., Pires, R. C. d. M., Xavier, M. A., Cantarella, H., and Landell, M. G. d. A. (2022). Sustainability in sugarcane supply chain in Brazil: Issues and way forward. *Sugar Tech* **24**, 941-966.

Presentation in International Conferences (Appendix 17.1):

Bolonhezi, D.; Cantarella, H.; Betiol, O.; Ruiz, F.F.; Oliveira, I.N.; Noronha, R.H.; Souza, Z.M.; Furlani, C.E.A. (2024). Direct transplanting of pre-sprouted seedlings under straw of soybean and cover crop: impact on yield and soil organic carbon. In: 9th. World Congress On Conservation Agriculture, **Abstract...** Western Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa (21-31 July 2024).

Betiol, O.; Bolonhezi, D.; Ruiz, F.F.; Michelotto, M.D.; Leal, E.R.P.; Valochi, R.; Cantarella, H.; Furlani, C.E.A. (2024). No-tillage for sugarcane-peanut crop rotation system. In: 9th. World Congress On Conservation Agriculture, **Abstract...** Western Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa (21-31 July 2024). **Best Poster Award**

2.5 Digital Tools

2.5.1 What are the socio-economic impacts of new technologies related to low C agriculture? / What are the economic and environmental impacts of new technologies in the Brazilian agriculture and livestock sectors?

2.5.1.1 Principal Investigator: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho

In this subsection, will describe the research line, with further details provided in **Appendix 18**.

The main objective:

To develop an integrated economic model of the Brazilian economy to assess the impacts of new technologies linked to carbon management.

The highlights

- How the second crop system in Brazil (initially for soybean/corn) can contribute to the fulfillment of the Brazilian commitments of the INDC.
- How economic policies can affect carbon storage in soils in Brazil, as well as the potential for this mechanism to help Brazil fulfill the INDC targets.

The planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle are the allocation of students to the two research lines proposed, and the development of the model. Two studies will be produced, aiming for papers for publication.

2.5.2 How can geotechnologies assist on the diagnostic of carbon impacts on agriculture, environment and climate?

2.5.2.1 Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

In this subsection, the 17 subprojects will be briefly described, with further details provided in **Appendix 19**.

Main objective:

Quantify and map, in high spatial resolution, all soil properties by geotechnologies, and gain knowledge of its impact on carbon dynamics

During the period, the geotechnologies line developed a series of subprojects. The focus of the activities is to generate the largest number of thematic maps of soil attributes and organic matter throughout Brazil by means of remote and field sensors, associated with artificial intelligence. The data will form the basis for all other lines of research at CCARBON. In addition to mapping, the fundamentals of these attributes and their relationship to carbon are also being studied.

During the period, trips were made to sign agreements with: Aristotle University (Greece), University of Florida (USA), University of Prague (Czech Republic), GFZ Spatial Science (Germany), University of Sydney (Australia), Tel Aviv University (Israel).

Subproject 1 – “Carbon Balance Mapping of the Brazilian Agricultural Areas by Geotechnologies: A New Approach” is being conducted by *Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín* (*Post-doc– FAPESP 2023/17508-9*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 2 – “Levantamento de dados e avaliação detalhada da qualidade do solo em áreas piloto: bases para a validação do mapa de qualidade dos solos do Brasil” is being conducted by *Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais* (*Post-doc– FAPESP 2022/14935-0*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 3 – “Mapa de perdas de solo, P, N e C do mundo” is being conducted by *Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas* (*Post-doc– FAPESP 2023/17876-8*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 4 – “The Global Soil Health Map: Implications for Global Society” is being conducted by *Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino* (*Post-doc– FAPESP 2021/05129-8*). It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 5 – “Mapeamento de locais propensos à erosão do solo através de SIG e sensoriamento remoto” is being conducted by *Uemeson José dos Santos (Post-doc. – without scholarship)*

Subproject 6 – “Mapeamento espaço-temporal 2.5D do estoque de carbono orgânico dos solos do Brasil” is being conducted by *Nicolas Augusto Rosin (PhD student – FAPESP 2021/10063-6)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 7 – “Mapeamento Digital da Produtividade de Soja com ênfase em Solos inseridos via Sensoriamento Remoto em Modelos de Simulação (Regiões Sudeste e Centro-Oeste do Brasil)” is being conducted by *Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim (PhD student – FAPESP 2022/11034-2)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 8 – “Global mapping of hydromorphic soils via machine learning” is being conducted by *Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch (PhD student – FAPESP 2023/11350-4)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 9 – “Projeto Carbono Brasil (CABRAL)” is being conducted by *Borges Marfrann Dias Melo (PhD student – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 10 – “Digital mapping of water available in the soil in agricultural areas in Brazil” is being conducted by *Letícia Guadagnin Vogel (Master student – CAPES 88887.907957/2023-00)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 11 – “Soil health as a factor in the analysis of anthropogenic pedosphere degradation” is being conducted by *Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa (Master student – CAPES 88887.823854/2023-00)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 12 – “Mapeamento detalhado de hematita e goethita de solos brasileiros através de dados espectrais e aprendizado de máquina” is being conducted by *Fernando Yutaro Makino (Scientific initiation – FAPESP 2023/13708-3)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 13 – “Biblioteca Brasileira de Espectros de Solos via Satélite para Avaliação e Monitoramento da Saúde do Solo” is being conducted by *Matheus Carraco Cardoso (Scientific initiation – CNPq PIBIC -2023)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 14 – “Mapeamento de Voçorocas (SySI)” is being conducted by *Matheus Fatori (Scientific initiation)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 15 – “Avaliação da saúde do solo na região de Piracicaba via geotecnologias” is being conducted by *Miguel Neves (Scientific initiation – PUB 2973/2023)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 16 – “Projeto Carbono Brasil (CABRAL)” is being conducted by *Samuel Silva de Moraes (Scientific initiation)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Subproject 17 – “Soil Health Diagnosis in Brazilian Pastures: A Spatial and Temporal Analysis by Biome” is being conducted by *Aron Müller de Oliveira (Scientific initiation – PUB 3128/2023 Benefício: 83-1)*. It is important to note that this researcher’s scholarship is funded by external resources, rather than those allocated to CCARBON.

Published articles see Appendix 19.1.

FALCIONI, Renan; OLIVEIRA, Roney Berti de; CHICATI, Marcelo Luiz; ANTUNES, Werner Camargos; DEMATTÊ, José Alexandre M.; NANNI, Marcos Rafael. **Estimation of Biochemical Compounds in Tradescantia Leaves Using VIS-NIR-SWIR Hyperspectral and Chlorophyll a Fluorescence Sensors**. *Remote Sensing*, v. 16, n. 11, p. 1910, 26 maio 2024. MDPI AG. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs16111910>.

NOVAIS J.J., ROSIN N.A., ROSAS J.T.F., POPPIEL R.R., DOTTO A.C., PAIVA A.F.S., BELLINASSO H., ALBARRACÍN H.S.R., AMORIM M.T.A., BARTSCH B. DOS A., VOGEL L.G., MELLO D.C., FRANCELINO M.R., ALVES M.R., FALCIONI R., DEMATTÊ J.A.M., **Brazilian Soil Spectral Library (VIS-NIR-SWIR-MIR) data opening**. *Dokuchaev Soil Bulletin*, 2024, V. 119, pp. 92-116 <http://dx.doi.org/10.19047/0136-1694-2024-119-92-116>

MELLO, Danilo César de; VELOSO, Gustavo Vieira; MOQUEDACE, Cassio Marques; OLIVEIRA, Isabelle de Angeli; FRANCELINO, Márcio Rocha; OLIVEIRA, Fabio Soares de; SOUZA, José João Lelis Leal de; GOMES, Lucas Carvalho; SCHAEFER, Carlos Ernesto Gonçalves Reynaud; FERNANDES-FILHO, Elpídio Inácio. **Chemical weathering detection in the periglacial landscapes of Maritime Antarctica: new approach using geophysical sensors, topographic variables and machine learning algorithms**. *Geoderma*, v. 438, out. 2023. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116615>.

MELLO, Danilo César de; VELOSO, Gustavo Vieira; MOQUEDACE, Cássio Marques; OLIVEIRA, Isabelle de Angeli; OLIVEIRA, Fabio Soares de; GOMES, Lucas Carvalho; SOUZA, José João Lelis Leal de; FRANCELINO, Márcio Rocha; FERNANDES-FILHO, Elpídio Inácio; SCHAEFER, Carlos Ernesto Gonçalves Reynaud. **Radiometric and magnetic susceptibility characterization of soil profiles: geophysical data and their relationship with antarctic periglacial processes, pedogenesis, and lithology**. *Catena*, v. 232, nov. 2023. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2023.107427>.

PAVÃO, Quésia Sá; RIBEIRO, Paula Godinho; MACIEL, Gutierre Pereira; SILVA, Sérgio Henrique Godinho; ARAËJO, Suzana Romeiro; FERNANDES, Antonio Rodrigues; DEMATTÊ, José Alexandre Melo; SOUZA FILHO, Pedro Walfir Martins e; RAMOS, Silvio Junio. **Texture prediction of natural soils in the Brazilian Amazon through proximal sensors**. *Geoderma Regional*, , v. 371,, p. e00813, jun. 2024. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00813>.

ROSAS, Jorge Tadeu Fim; DEMATTÊ, José A.M.; ROSIN, Nicolás Augusto; BARTSCH, Bruno dos Anjos; POPPIEL, Raul Roberto; RODRIGUEZ-ALBARRACIN, Heidy Soledad; NOVAIS, Jean Jesus Macedo; PAVINATO, Paulo Sergio; MA, Yuxin; MELLO, Danilo César de; FRANCELINO, Marcio Rocha; ALVES, Marcelo Rodrigo. **Geotechnologies on the phosphorus stocks determination in tropical soils: General impacts on society**. Science of The Total Environment, v. 938, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173537>.

ROSIN, Nicolás Augusto; DEMATTÊ, José A.M.; CARVALHO, Hudson Wallace Pereira de; RODRIGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, Heidy Soledad; ROSAS, Jorge Tadeu Fim; NOVAIS, Jean Jesus; DALMOLIN, Ricardo S.D.; ALVES, Marcelo Rodrigo; FALCIONI, Renan; TZIOLAS, Nikolaos. **Spatializing soil elemental concentration as measured by X-ray fluorescence analysis using remote sensing data**. Catena, v. 240, p. 107988, maio 2024. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2024.107988>.

LIMA, Bruna Coelho; SANTOS, Carlos H., TIRITAN, Carlos S., DEMATTÊ, José A.M.; GOMEZ, Andres M.R.; ALBARRACÍN, Heidy S.R.; BARTSCH, Bruno A. **Analysis of organic and mineral nitrogen, total organic carbon and humic fractions in Ferralsols: an approach using Vis-NIR-SWIR, MIR and X-ray fuorescence spectroscopy**, Discover Environment, v. 2, n. 79, 16 July 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44274-024-00097-3>.

PINHEIRO JUNIOR, Carlos Roberto; TAVARES, Tiago Rodrigues; PEREIRA, Marcos Gervasio; FURQUIM, Sheila Aparecida Correia; TERRA, Fabrício da Silva; ANJOS, Lúcia Helena Cunha dos; DEMATTÊ, José Alexandre Melo; AZEVEDO, Antônio Carlos de; OLIVEIRA, Fábio Soares de. **Pedogenesis on Jurassic formations in the Araripe Basin, northeastern Brazil: weathering and parent material**. Catena, [S.L.], v. 223, p. 106952, abr. 2023. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2023.106952>.

SOUSA, Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de; BELLINASO, Henrique; ROSAS, Jorge Tadeu Fim; MELLO, Danilo César de; ROSIN, Nicolás Augusto; AMORIM, Merylyn Taynara Accorsi; BARTSCH, Bruno dos Anjos; CARDOSO, Matheus Carraco; MALLAH, Sina; FRANCELINO, Márcio Rocha. **Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon**. Soil Advances, [S.L.], v. 2, p. 100011, out. 2024. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100011>.

RODRÍGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, Heidy Soledad; DEMATTÊ, José A.M.; ROSIN, Nicolás Augusto; CONTRERAS, Aquiles Enrique Darghan; SILVERO, Nélica E.Q.; CERRI, Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino; MENDES, Wanderson de Sousa; TAYEBI, Mahboobeh. **Potential of soil minerals to sequester soil organic carbon**. Geoderma, [S.L.], v. 436, p. 116549, ago. 2023. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116549>.

RODRÍGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, Heidy Soledad; DEMATTÊ, José A.M.; ROSIN, Nicolás Augusto; AMORIM, Merylyn Taynara Accorsi; CONTRERAS, Aquiles Enrique Darghan; ANDREOTE, Fernando Dini; ROSAS, Jorge Tadeu Fim. **Soil organic carbon sequestration potential explained by mineralogical and microbiological activity using spectral transfer functions**. Science Of The Total Environment, [S.L.], v. 947, p. 174652, out. 2024. Elsevier BV. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174652>.

Poster presentation V Encontro paulista de ciência do Solo - V EPCiS

Consistency assessment of the open-access Brazilian soil spectral library

Jean Jesus Macedo Novais; Nicolas Augusto Rosin; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Merilyn Taynara Arccosi Amorim; Leticia Guadagnin Vogel; José Alexandre de Melo Demattê

Spatial distribution and agricultural implications of phosphorus stocks in Brazilian biomes: a machine learning approach

Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; José A.M. Demattê; Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch; Nicolas Augusto Rosin; Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa; Paulo Sergio Pavinato.

Revealing the spatio-temporal dynamic of soil organic carbon stock in Brazil by earth observation

Nicolas Augusto Rosin; José A. M. Demattê; Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Raul Roberto Poppiel; Heidy Soledad Rodriguez-Albarracín

Antarctica soil characterization by proximal sense

Miguel Neves Magalhaes de Paula Mendes; José Alexandre Melo Demattê; Borges Mello Marfrann; Danilo César de Mello; Marcio Rocha Francelino; Tiago Osório Ferreira; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Carlos Ernesto Gonçalves Reynaud Schaefer

Soybean yield productivity modelling by remote sensing data, in-situ soil attributes, machine learning and human experience association

Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim; Danilo César de Mello; Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa; Letícia Guadagnin Vogel; Andre V. Zabini; José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Mapping soil health in Germany: towards a sustainable agricultural development index

Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa; Sabine Chabrilat; Robert Milewski; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Maurício Roberto Cherubin; José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Soil health assessment through remote sensing: a systematic review

Borges Marfrann Dias Melo; Gabriel Nogueira Bonelli; Luiza Pecci Canisares; Yuri Soares de Mello⁴, José Alexandre Melo Demattê¹, Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Oral Presentation V Encontro Paulista de ciência do solo - V EPCiS

Is it possible to detect and map enzyme activities from the whole agriculture Brazilian area by a sensor located 800 km from the target?

Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín; José A. M. Demattê; Nicolas Augusto Rosin; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Fernando Dini Andreote; Nariane de Andrade; Alberto Vinicius S. Rocha; Elaine Reis Pinheiro Lourente; Letícia G. Vogel; Matheus C. Cardoso. First place award in the category of best oral presentations at the “V ENCONTRO PAULISTA DE CIÊNCIA DO SOLO V EPCiS ” realized in Botucatu, SP, August 13 and 14, 2024.

Poster presentation CCarbon Soil Health Symposium – 24 april 2024

Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, Vagner Fernando Nolasco Junior, Letícia Guadagnin Vogel, Asa Gholizadeh, Borůvka Lubos, Lucas Tadeu Greschuk, Maurício Roberto Cherubin, José Alexandre Melo Dematte. **A strategy to determine the Czech Republic's soil health from space.** 24/04/2024, Piracicaba, São Paulo, Brazil. CCarbon Soil Health Symposium 2024. (First place award in the category of best oral presentations)

Miguel Neves Magalhaes de Paula Mendes; José Alexandre Melo Demattê; Borges Mello Marfrann; Danilo César de Mello; Marcio Rocha Francelino; Tiago Osório Ferreira; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Carlos Ernesto Gonçalves Reynaud Schaefer. **antartic soil characterization by proximal sensing** 24/04/2024, Piracicaba, São Paulo, Brazil. CCarbon Soil Health Symposium 2024.

Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch; Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa'; Letícia Guadagnin Vogel'; Borges Marfrann Dias Melo'; Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim'; Matheus Carraco Cardoso'; Jean de Jesus Novais'; José Alexandre Melo Demattê. **Carbon determination from space** 24/04/2024, Piracicaba, São Paulo, Brazil. CCarbon Soil Health Symposium 2024.

3. Dissemination

Dissemination initiatives are divided into five subareas (Figure 2) that aim to promote initial discussions on research activities to be addressed both in person and in digital format. Its strategies include encouraging **publications** in scientific journals, books, eBooks, as well as semi-annual technical bulletins. The **advocacy** subarea focuses on promoting annual meetings between universities and competent bodies, creating partnerships, as well as booklets for municipalities, disseminating good practices to the general population. Another objective of CCARBON/USP's dissemination is to hold in-person and online courses and **training** through panels, field days, benchmarking with farmers and professionals, symposiums with experts, podcasts, eBooks and booklets. These activities will be supported by **social media** such as Instagram, LinkedIn and YouTube. The **public awareness** subarea aims to generate public recognition, through the participation of its researchers on events, media exposure, as well as the production of documentaries, monthly releases and the creation of an informative website.

Figure 2. Dissemination action strategy from Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture

In addition to its contribution and encouragement to the scientific community, CCARBON/USP's dissemination division has a major impact on the lay public and society in general. Its importance has become increasingly evident in encouraging sustainable agricultural production practices and in influencing stakeholder's behavior regarding awareness of the need to mitigate and adapt to climate change. Its strategies are strictly aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Since CCARBON/USP was officially launched by USP/FAPESP in September 2023, it developed the center's visual identity, followed by activities under the previously mentioned dissemination initiatives, such as publications, advocacy, training, social media and public awareness. Below are listed their activities within each of these fields of activity, as well as future strategies to broaden the dissemination of our objectives.

Publications

Several papers have been published by researchers from CCARBON/USP since its establishment last year. Publications included scientific papers, book chapters, e-books and one book.

Scientific Papers

Five scientific papers were published in scientific journals of international relevance indexed in databases. Below is a list of papers and their respective citation numbers in Google Scholar up to the date of preparation of this report and the impact factors of the journals:

1. BIELUCZYK, W.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; CERRI, C.E.P.; SIQUEIRA-NETO, M.; ABDALLA-FILHO, A.L.; CASTRO, J.I.A.; LOCATELLI, J.L.; TSAI, S.M.; CAMARGO, P.B. (2024). **Greenhouse gas fluxes in Brazilian climate-smart agricultural and livestock systems: A systematic and critical overview**, Journal of Cleaner Production, Volume 464, 142782, ISSN 0959-6526, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142782> . N° of citations: 0; IF: 3.7
2. CARVALHO, M.L.; MACIEL, V.F.; BORDONAL, R.O.; CARVALHO, J.L.N.; FERREIRA, T.O.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2023) **Stabilization of organic matter in soils: drivers, mechanisms, and analytical tools – a literature review**. Rev Bras Cienc Solo. 47:e0220130. <https://doi.org/10.36783/18069657rbc20220130> . N° of citations: 1; IF: 0.974
3. PEREIRA, A.P.A.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; DE ARAUJO, A.S.F.; SANTANA, M.C.; DE MEDEIROS, E.V.; DA COSTA, D.P.; DE SOUZA, A.J.; LIMA, A.Y.V.; DA SILVA, D.F.; ESTRADA, P.A.C.; et al. (2024) **Soil Quality Evaluation in Mono and Mixed Eucalypt Plantation**. Sustainability. 16, 2534. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062534> N° of citations: 0; IF: 3.9.
4. PINHEIROJUNIOR, C.R.; CARVALHO, J.L.N.; CANISARES, L.P.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024). **Soil carbon stocks in sugarcane cultivation: An evidence synthesis associated with land use and management practices**. GCB Bioenergy, 16, e13188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.13188> N° of citations: 0; IF: 5.9.
5. QUEIROZ, H.M.; FERREIRA, T.O.; CERRI, C.E.P.; PEREIRA, G.A.G.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024), **Advancing the agave-soil nexus approach: A systematic review**. Biofuels, Bioprod. Bioref. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.2625> N° of citations: 0; IF: 4.102.

Book chapters

Five book chapters were published in 2024 by CCARBON/USP researchers. The topics cover sustainable practices in agriculture with the aim of improving soil health, increasing carbon sequestration and improving conditions to face the challenges of climate change. Below is listed each book chapter published by our researchers since the establishment of CCARBON/USP:

1. CERRI, C.E.P.; MELLO, F.F.D.C.; RENTERIA, N.B.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024). **Public Policies and Initiatives to Promote Soil Health and Carbon Sequestration in Brazil**. In Soil Health Series: Volume 3 Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil (eds I.C. Mendes and M.R. Cherubin). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch12>
2. CHERUBIN, M.R.; DA LUZ, F.B.; DE LIMA, R.P.; TENELLI, S.; BORDONAL, R.O.; DE OLIVEIRA, B.G.; GONZAGA, L.C.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CARVALHO, J.L.N.

- (2024). **Soil Health in Sugarcane Production Systems**. In Soil Health Series: Volume 3 Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil (eds I.C. Mendes and M.R. Cherubin). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch5>
3. NWAOGU, C.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024). Integrated agricultural systems: **The 21st century nature-based solution for resolving the global FEEES challenges**. *Advances in Agronomy*, 185, 1-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2024.02.003>
 4. SOUZA, V.S.; DA SILVA VANOLLI, B.; SCHIEBELBEIN, B.E.; DE SOUZA BORTOLO, L.; CARVALHO, M.L.; MENDES, I.C.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024). **Cover Crops and Soil Health in Brazilian Agricultural Systems**. In Soil Health Series: Volume 3 Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil (eds I.C. Mendes and M.R. Cherubin). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch4>
 5. VEZZANI, F.M.; ANGHINONI, I.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; MENDES, I.C. (2024). **Soil Health and Modern Brazilian Agriculture**. In Soil Health Series: Volume 3 Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil (eds I.C. Mendes and M.R. Cherubin). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch1>

Books

In addition to the book chapters, a book covering the topic of soil health and sustainability was published this year by one of the center's researchers.

1. MENDES, I.C.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024) **Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil**. ISBN: 978-0-891-18743-1. March 2024. 432 pages <https://www.wiley.com/enus/Soil+Health+and+Sustainable+Agriculture+in+Brazil-p-9780891187431>

eBooks

In order to provide guidelines for enabling soil management practices, promoting improvements in soil health and agricultural sustainability, eBooks were published as practical guides for their users. Below are the two eBooks published and their respective numbers of downloads up to the time of the present report:

1. SCHIEBELBEIN, B.E.; CHERUBIN, M.R. **Guia do usuário de campo do Kit SOHMA de saúde do solo**. Universidade de São Paulo. Escola Superior de Agricultura Luiz de Queiroz, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391557> Disponível em: www.livrosabertos.abcd.usp.br/portaldelivrosUSP/catalog/book/1311 . Accessed em 14 agosto. 2024. Nº of downloads: 1.111
2. CHERUBIN, M.R. **Guia prático de plantas de cobertura: espécies, manejo e impacto na saúde do solo**. Universidade de São Paulo. Escola Superior de Agricultura Luiz de Queiroz, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391618> Disponível em: www.livrosabertos.abcd.usp.br/portaldelivrosUSP/catalog/book/1340 . Accessed em 14 agosto. 2024. Nº of downloads: 2.703.

Advocacy

Two important initiatives related to advocacy were implemented. One of them was the creation of a partnership called the *Brazilian Soil Health Partnership* and the other was an agreement with the Forest Foundation for the *Integrated Mangrove Management Program*. Furthermore, CCARBON representatives participated in meetings with national and international government agencies.

1. Brazilian Soil Health Partnership

The Brazilian Soil Health Partnership was created and launched, an initiative involving 50 researchers (Fig. 2), promoting a national soil health agenda, enabling connections between scientists, farmers and stakeholders. The initiative was launched on 04/24/2024 at the CCARBON/USP Soil Health Symposium and aims to establish a scientific collaboration network to promote soil health in agricultural production areas in Brazil. <https://www.esalq.usp.br/eventos/ccarbon-soil-health-symposium-field-socioeconomical-and-political-perspectives>

Figure 3. Diagram of researchers involved in the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership and their respective research institutions

2. Forest Foundation Agreement

The CCARBON/USP also celebrated a partnership with the Forestry Foundation for Integrated Mangrove Management Program (<https://fflorestal.sp.gov.br/programa-manguezais/>). The Program highlights the leading role of the mangrove ecosystem in protecting marine biodiversity and combating climate change. In this sense, the program is in line with national frameworks for recognizing the importance of coastal-marine ecosystems, and is aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) number 13 (Climate Action) and number 14 (Life Below Water). The Forestry Foundation is implementing this program with the intention of having a baseline for carbon stocks for public policy purposes. Through a partnership with this institution, CCARBON/USP is obtaining these mangrove samples from different regions, which will be analyzed by its researchers (Fig. 3). The Integrated Mangrove Management Program was established by the Forestry Foundation via Normative Ordinance FF/DE 445/2024 (<https://smastr16.blob.core.windows.net/fundacaoflorestal/2024/07/Portaria-Normativa-FF-445-2024-Manguezais.pdf>).

Figure 4. Image of the 1st Training Meeting for Mangrove Monitoring that took place at Itinguçu State Park in Peruíbe – SP

3. Participation in meetings with national and international government agencies

Meeting	Date	Place
Legislative Assembly	October 16, 2023	São Paulo/SP
Brazilian Ministry of Agriculture (MAPA)	October 8, 2023	Piracicaba/SP
Brazilian Ministry of Economy	September 23, 2023	São Paulo/SP
Brazilian Ministry of Science and Technology (MCTI)	April 24, 2024	Brasília/DF
Brazilian Ministry of Environment	June 11, 2024	Brasília/DF
Brazilian Intelligence Agency (ABIN)	September 21, 2023	São Paulo/SP
Brazilian Export and Investment Promotion Agency (APEX)	February 27, 2024	São Paulo/SP
Federal Courts Accounts – Brazil (TCU)	February 26, 2024 and May 03, 2024	Videoconference
Revised version of the Brazilian NDC (Intended Nationally Determined Contribution)	May 07, 2024	São Paulo/SP
Carbon Footprint of the Brazilian beef	August 06, 2024	Videoconference
Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA) – “Living Soils of the Americas”)	July 23, 2024	Videoconference
Ministère de L’Agriculture et de La Souveraineté Alimentaire	August 22, 2024	Paris/France
Food Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) – 3 rd Webinar (Organic Matter Management Webinar Series) – “Options to contribute to sustainable production systems and SDGs”	January 08, 2024	Videoconference
University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P) – Fair Transitions	September 7, 2023	Marocco
British Embassy	June 10, 2024	Brasília/DF
United States of America Embassy	March 05, 2024	Brasília/DF
COP28	March 05, 2024	Dubay/Emirates

Training

Two symposia and one online course were held by CCARBON/USP collaborators. Both seminars reached the expected audience. The online course is accessible to farmers and operational staff focusing on how to use sustainable techniques for greater productivities. Below are detailed descriptions of each of these activities:

1. 1st CCARBON/USP Symposium: Integrating scales, expertise and scientific approaches in carbon studies

The 1st CCARBON Symposium (<https://www.esalq.usp.br/eventos/1st-carbon-symposium>) brought together prominent scientists in carbon research from agricultural and the environmental sciences. It was a significant milestone in introducing CCARBON to the scientific community, professionals and society, outlining the objectives of the Center for Carbon Studies in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP): to generate knowledge, technology, innovation, train human resources and disseminate carbon-based solutions for tropical agricultural systems, aiming to reconcile the growing demand for food, fiber and energy with sustainability in its environmental, economic and social aspects. Thus, the 1st CCARBON Symposium brought together prominent scientists specializing in carbon science in soil and plant research in order to:

- Present advanced research findings: highlight innovative research, cutting-edge technologies, and discoveries related to the carbon cycle in agricultural and natural ecosystems;
- Discuss sustainable practices: explore practices that promote carbon protection and sequestration, contributing to improving agricultural sustainability;
- Facilitate collaborations and partnerships: foster networking among participants, encouraging collaborations and partnerships that contribute to global initiatives in tackling climate change.

Coordinators: Prof. Dr. Maurício Roberto Cherubin; Prof. Dr. Tiago Osório Ferreira and Dr. Francisco Ruiz

Organizing committee: Giovanna Campanholi Delghingaro; Amanda Duim Ferreira; Julia Rossi Pereira; Yuri Fernando Parra Castilho; Antonio Elves Barreto Silva; Beatriz Marchese Silva; Thomas Trentin (Fig. 4)

Figure 5. Production team of the 1st CCARBON Symposium.

About the event:

- Name: 1st CCARBON Symposium: Integrating scales, expertises and scientific approaches in carbon studies.
- Date: December 8, 2023
- Location: Anfiteatro do Pavilhão de Agricultura da Engenharia, Escola Superior de Agricultura “Luiz de Queiroz” (ESALQ/USP), Piracicaba - SP
- Duration: 7 hours
- Modality: In-person
- Target audience: students, academic community and professionals
- Registered Audience: 175 (Fig. 5)
- Speakers: 8 (2 internationals / 6 Brazilians); - Cornelia Rumpel (Centre AgroParisTech - France); Abad Chabbi (Centre AgroParisTech - France); Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri (CCARBON/USP); Luiz Antonio Martinelli (CENA/USP); Maurício Roberto Cherubin (CCARBON/USP); Tiago Osório Ferreira (CCARBON/USP); José Alexandre Melo Demattê (ESALQ/USP); Dean Hesterberg (CNPEN/Sirius) (Fig.6).
- Presented posters: 57
- Sponsorship: Bayer

Figure 6. Event overview: a. opening ceremony; b. coffee break and exhibition of works

Time		Activity	Speaker/Participant
07:30	08:30	Registration	
08:30	08:45	Opening	Tiago Osório Ferreira, Maurício R. Cherubin, Thaís Vieira (Director ESALQ)
08:45	09:00	CCarbon presentation	
9:00	10:00	Lecture – Foresting soil carbon sequestration: processes at the molecular scale	Comelia Rumpel
10:00	10:30	Coffee Break - Poster Section	
10:30	11:50	Lecture – Peak Soil and its implications to human wellbeing/Climate Change	Abad Chabbi
11:50	13:30	Lunch break	
13:30	15:15	Panel 1: Challenges and opportunities for C sequestration in forests, agriculture and wetlands	Tiago Osório Ferreira, Maurício R. Cherubin, Gerd Sparovek, Francisco Ruiz (moderator)
15:15	15:45	Coffee Break - Poster Section	
15:45	17:15	Panel 2: Methods for studying carbon from macro to nanoscale	José Alexandre Dematê, Luiz A. Martineli, Dean Hesterberg, Tiago Ferreria (moderator)
17:15	17:30	Closing ceremony	Maurício R. Cherubin

Figure. 7. Lectures and panels: a. Fostering soil carbon sequestration: processes at the molecular scale (Cornelia Rumpel); b. Peak Soil and its implications to human wellbeing/Climate Change (Abad Chabbi); c. Challenges and Opportunities for C sequestration in forests, agriculture and wetlands (Tiago Ferreira, Maurício Cherubin, Gerd Sparovek, Francisco Ruiz); d. Methods for studying carbon from macro to nanoscale (José Alexandre M. Demattê, Luiz A. Martinelli, Dean Hesterberg).

2. CCARBON Soil Health Symposium: from the field to the socioeconomical and political perspectives
- 3.

The CCARBON Soil health Symposium: from the field to the socioeconomical and political perspectives (<https://www.esalq.usp.br/eventos/ccarbon-soil-health-symposium-field-socioeconomical-and-political-perspectives>) aimed to present, discuss and advance knowledge related to soil health and its impact on the sustainability of agricultural ecosystems, as well as the political and market implications of this topic. To this end, it featured prominent scientists and market experts. The main objectives were:

- Present research findings, innovations and technologies related to soil health in agricultural ecosystems;
- Discuss practices that promote soil health, improving agricultural sustainability;
- Facilitate networking, collaborations and partnerships among participants, thus contributing to global initiatives aimed at combating climate change;
- Launch of the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership, an initiative that aimed to establish a scientific collaboration network to promote soil health in agricultural production areas in Brazil.

Coordinators: Prof. Dr. Maurício Roberto Cherubin and Prof. Dr. Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Organizing committee: SOHMA – Esalq; Dr. Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior; Dr. Lucas Pecci Canisares; Dr. Lucas Freitas Nogueira Souza; Me. Beatriz da Silva Vanolli; Me. Victoria Santos Souza; Rafael Menillo (Figure 8)

Figure 8. Sohma-Esalq Team.

About the event:

- Name: CCarbon Soil Health Symposium: from the field to the socioeconomic and political perspectives
- Date: April 24, 2024
- Location: Anfiteatro do Pavilhão de Agricultura da Engenharia, Escola Superior de Agricultura “Luiz de Queiroz” (ESALQ/USP), Piracicaba - SP
- Duration: 7 hours
- Modality: In-person
- Target audience: students, academic community and professionals
- Registered Audience: 210 (Fig. 8)
- Speakers: 10 - Christine Morgan (Soil Health Institute – EUA); Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri (CCARBON/USP); Maurício Roberto Cherubin (CCARBON/USP); Maira Coscrato Lelis da Silva; Daniel Barcelos Vargas (Canal Agromais); Carlos Alexandre Costa Crusciol (UNESP Botucatu); Leidivan Almeida Frazão (UFMG); Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira (UFC); Francisco Fujita de Castro Mello (UNESP Botucatu); Eduardo Bastos (Fig. 9)
- Presented posters: 42
- Sponsorship: Bayer and Mosaic

Figure 9. a. event overview: opening ceremony and b. coffee break/work exhibition

Schedule:

Time		Activity	Speaker/Participant
07:30	08:30	Registration	
08:30	9:00	Opening – CCARBON: challenges and perspectives on the soil health agenda	Carlos E. P. Cerri, Maurício R. Cherubin, Thaís Vieira (Director ESALQ)
9:00	10:00	Lecture – Soil Health Institute: the American experience in a soil health program	Cristine Morgan
10:00	10:15	Discussion	
10:15	10:30	Launch of the book Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil	Maurício R. Cherubin
10:30	11:00	Coffee Break - Poster Section	
11:00	11:15	Sponsor space	Bayer
10:30	11:30	Roundtable discussion 1 – Soil health as the basis for regenerative agriculture	Maurício R. Cherubin, Maira Lelis
11:30	11:50	Launch of the on-farm soil health assessment kit	Bruna Schiebelbein
11:50	13:30	Lunch break	
13:30	13:50	Soil-plant relationship in agricultural systems	Carlos Alexandre Crusciol
13:50	14:10	Integrated production systems as a nature-based solution	Leidivan Frazão
14:10	14:30	Soil health in climatically stressed environments	Arthur Prudêncio Pereira
14:30	14:45	Discussion	
14:45	15:00	Sponsor space	Mosaic
15:00	15:15	Launch of the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership	Maurício Cherubin/Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior
15:15	15:45	Coffee Break - Poster Section	
15:45	17:15	Roundtable discussion 2 – Carbon and Soil Health in the context of international negotiations and initiatives	Eduardo Bastos, Francisco Mello, Daniel B. Vargas, Carlos E.P. Cerri
17:15	17:30	Closing ceremony	Carlos E. P. Cerri, Maurício R. Cherubin

Figure 10. Opening, lectures and panels: a. Opening of the event (Maurício Cherubin; Thais Vieira; Carlos Eduardo Cerri); b. Lecture - Soil Health Institute: The American experience in a soil health program (Cristiane Morgan); c. Panel - Soil health and its relationship with plants (Carlos Crusciol; Leidivan Frazão; Arthur Pereira); d. Roundtable - Soil health as the basis for Regenerative Agriculture (Maira Lelis; Maurício Cherubin); e. Roundtable - Carbon and Soil Health in the context of international negotiations and initiatives (Eduardo Bastos; Daniel Barcelos; Francisco Mello; Carlos Eduardo Cerri); f. Launch of the On-Farm Soil Health Assessment Kit and the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership (Maurício Cherubin).

4. Online course

The Low Carbon Agriculture (Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri and Maurício R. Cherubin) <https://lp.solloagro.com.br/agroparatodos-baixo-carbono>. The course developed by the CCARBON/USP team aims to provide accessible knowledge to producers and farm operational staff on how to use sustainable techniques to increase crop productivity, always aiming at "Low Carbon Agriculture". The classes were produced in simple and easy-to-understand language based on the didactic content produced and validated by the Professors. The initiative included a series of 6 courses, each with a workload of 25 minutes, and can also be accessed via cell phone (both online and offline). The course also offers a certificate for those who complete all stages. Below are the course topics:

- Greenhouse Gasses (GHG) Emitted by Agriculture;
- Impacts of Climate Change on the Agricultural Sector;
- Role of Agriculture, Livestock and Forestry in Containing Climate Change;
- Land Use Change and Carbon Emissions;
- Soil Preparation and Carbon Emissions;
- Agricultural Waste Management and Carbon Emissions;
- Recovery of Degraded Pastures and Carbon Emissions;
- Adoption of Integrated Systems and Carbon Emissions;
- Biological Nitrogen Fixation and Carbon Emissions;
- Sugarcane Cultivation and Carbon Emissions;
- Planting Forests and Carbon Emissions;
- The Use of Biomethane and Carbon Emissions;
- How to calculate the carbon stored in the soil;
- How to calculate the gasses emitted by agricultural systems;
- Emissions accounting: concept of life cycle analysis;
- What is the Carbon Market – Regulated vs. Voluntary;
- Carbon Footprint;
- Payment for Carbon Stored in Soil and Vegetation;
- Payment for ecosystem services;
- How Individuals and Governments Should Act to Contain Climate Change.

Social Medias

CCARCBON researchers have participated in videocasts and podcasts on research topics from carbon in agriculture, its trends and perceptions, besides its implications on climate change. There was a participation in five episodes of SOHMACast and one in an International Podcast with an interview for the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA). Below are the podcast topics, as well as the names of the participants and access links:

1. SOHMACast - Exploring Soil Health Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri and Maurício R. Cherubin) <https://youtu.be/TuoILjDza7s>
2. SOHMACast - The role of carbon in agriculture (Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri and Maurício R. Cherubin) <https://youtu.be/vs20OxldK5Y>
3. SOHMACast – Mangroves and the provision of ecosystem services (Tiago Osório Ferreira) <https://youtu.be/44TpWMmqwSc>

4. SOHMACast - Technosols and the recovery of degraded areas (Tiago Osório Ferreira) <https://youtu.be/kAPCjs62ktI>
5. SOHMACast - Tools and Strategies for Soil Health Assessment (Maurício R. Cherubin) <https://youtu.be/aZA0Xm3nZ5U>
6. PodCast IICA (Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri and Maurício R. Cherubin) <https://iica.int/pt>

Public awareness

CCARBON/USP researchers have participated in online news, interviews in TV programs, institutional news and scientific events to generate awareness about CCARBON/USP and disseminate findings and results of the ongoing research and activities. There were more than 30 mentions in the media mentioning the center. Below there is a list of participations in interviews, field days, events and other activities from CCARBON team that contributes with public awareness :

1. Interview for FAPESP Magazine (Maurício R. Cherubin);
2. G1 Interview (Maurício R. Cherubin);
3. Reception of visitors “on-site” (schools, cooperatives, campus visitors, etc.)- **EDUCARBON Station** [Home Page: https://sites.usp.br/solonaescola/](https://sites.usp.br/solonaescola/) (Antonio C. Azevedo);
4. Itinerant exhibition [Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/pontesolonaescola/](https://www.instagram.com/pontesolonaescola/);
5. In-house and online courses for school teachers and other groups (farmers, agricultural and environmental professionals, etc.) (Antonio C. Azevedo);
6. Citizen Science projects with schools and the general public (Antonio C. Azevedo);
7. Field days and lectures in courses and specializations at Department of Animal Science (LZT – ESALQ/USP) (Flávio Augusto Portela Santos);
8. Field days at APTA (Heitor Cantarella);
9. COP28 (Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri);
10. 19th International Symposium of Microbial Ecology (Cidade do Cabo, África do Sul) (Fernando Dini Andreote);
11. 9th International Symposium on Soil Organic Matter (Ben Guerir, Morocco) (Maurício R. Cherubin);
12. FAPESP WEEK China (Maurício R. Cherubin);
13. FAPESP WEEK Illinois (Tiago Osório Ferreira);
14. Annual event in coordination with FAO-UN: “Soil Sunday” (Antonio C. Azevedo);
15. XXVI IUFRO World Congress - Forests and Society Towards 2050, (Stockholm, Sweden), on June 23-29, 2024 (Pedro Brancalion);

16. V Brazilian Conference on Ecological Restoration (Juazeiro-BA and Petrolina-PE), on July 8 and 12, 2024 (Pedro Brancalion);
17. International Congress of the Brazilian Genetics Society (Helaine Carrer);
18. 5th International Symposium on Lipid Oxidation and Antioxidants, Bologna 5 to 8 July, 2024 (Thais Maria F. de Souza Vieira);
19. ASAS Annual in Calgary, Canada (Flávio Augusto Portela Santos);
20. SBZ Annual Meeting (Cuiabá - MT) (Flávio Augusto Portela Santos);
21. UNEM DATAGRO International Conference on Corn Ethanol (Cuiabá - MT) (Flávio Augusto Portela Santos);
22. 27th Annual Conference on Global Economic Analysis (GTAP) (Joaquim Bento de S. Ferreira Filho);
23. 14th World Conference of the Regional Science Association International (Joaquim Bento de S. Ferreira Filho);
24. Congress of the Brazilian Society of Economics, Administration and Rural Sociology – SOBER (Joaquim Bento de S. Ferreira Filho).

Professor Tiago Osório Ferreira's participation in FAPESP Week Illinois 2024

The University of Illinois hosted the 2024 FAPESP Week event at the Discovery Partners Institute in Chicago (<https://fapesp.br/week/2024/illinois>). This two-day event, held on April 9 and 10, aimed to connect researchers from diverse fields to create new opportunities for scientific and technological cooperation between researchers from the State of São Paulo and the Midwest of the United States (<https://fapesp.br/week/2024/illinois/program>). The main topics discussed at FAPESP Week 2024 included Smart Cities, One Health, Democratic Institutions and Social Inclusion, Climate, Smart Agriculture, Bioenergy, the Carbon Cycle, and Water.

Researchers from institutions in São Paulo, universities in Illinois, the Great Lakes region, as well as partner institutions from Canada and Mexico, participated in the event. Professor Tiago Osório Ferreira represented the University of São Paulo, moderating the Smart Agriculture and Bioenergy panel and delivering the Carbon Cycle lecture during the Coffee Session (Figure 11). Additionally, Professor Tiago visited the College of Agricultural, Consumer and Environmental Sciences (ACES) in Urbana (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Moderation of the Smart Agriculture and Bioenergy panel (a) and lecture at the Coffee Session Carbon Cycle (b)

Figure 12. Prof. Tiago's visit to the College of Agricultural, Consumer and Environmental Sciences (ACES) in Urbana

Future strategies

The CCARBON dissemination sector has several strategies that will be implemented in the coming months. The center is counting on the participation of more collaborators to continue these activities and aims to create a team that will increase engagement with the general public on issues related to carbon research in tropical agriculture. Below some of the futures strategies:

- Website construction with its launching by the end of the August ;
- Creation of different social media pages for the center with focus on LinkedIn, Instagram and Youtube to be launched by mid of September;
- Establishment of a schedule of frequent publications/posts on social media about general news and research carried out by the center and other relevant subjects to the general public ;

- In May of the present year, in Morocco , the CCARBON/USP was elected to host the Eleventh International Soil Organic Matter Symposium to occur in July 2026 in the city of São Paulo.

4. Innovation

Innovation initiatives are divided into five subareas (Figure 13) that aim to foster the development of a productive collaborative ecosystem to develop impacting innovations and technologies for the field. Its actions strategies include promoting **R&DI partnerships** with world class players in the sector, such as with national organizations such as Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa e Inovação Industrial, Instituto Tecnológico Vale, and Centro de Tecnologia Canavieira, and international organizations such as Agrifood 5 (A5) Alliance, C-MASC-OSU, and Instituto Interamericano de Cooperação para a Agricultura. In the **Discovery and Technology** front, we aim to develop novel products and processes, as well software, to resolve persisting problems of the sector and increase its competitiveness. Another important axis of activities is the **Promotion of Entrepreneurship**, through interactions and partnerships with private companies and startups, as well by fostering the establishment of new companies by researchers and students participating in CCarbon. And to optimize this process, we will work towards the promotion of **Public-Private Partnerships**, through co-finance with the private sector, co-working in R&DI, and institutional relationship with multiple stakeholder groups. Finally, we aim to be a new key player in the existing **Innovation Ecosystems** supporting the development of knowledge and solutions for carbon in tropical agriculture, focusing mainly on interactions with CERES-Hub, AUSPIN, AgTechValley, and EMBRAPPII.

Figure 13. Innovation action strategy from Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture

One of the main goals of the innovation strategy of CCarbon is to incentivize the development of innovations by researchers participating in the projects, through the five strategies described above, bridging the gap between applied research that has been typically developed by CCarbon researchers and the development of practical solutions to the field. In this context, we recognize that a first step towards this objective is to understand which research underway the CCarbon ecosystem has potential to be transformed into key innovations, so we did an internal survey among CCarbon researchers to identify such research. From this survey, we highlight the following outcomes, grouped into the five main action strategies described above:

- (i) **R&DI partnerships:** ongoing collaborative research with Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), Newcastle University, Wageningen University & Research, Cambridge University, UMR Qualisud, and University of California Davis and UC Santa Cruz. From these, we highlight a broader collaboration with CIRAD-France, formalized already through a MoU and to be further structured at an in-person workshop to be held on Nov. 4-6th, 2024, in Piracicaba-SP, involving more than 15 French researchers;
- (ii) **Discovery and Technology:** development in progress of the software EDUCARBON (EDUCARBON Station [Home](#) [Page: https://sites.usp.br/solonaescola/](#) - Antonio C. Azevedo); new algorithm and software for soil mapping and aboveground carbon stocking assessment

through UAV-Lidar, new soybean cultivars and, remarkably, a kit for assessing soil quality in a comprehensive way at the farm level – KitSOHMA, which has a patent request under evaluation. In agricultural systems, soil health refers to the "continued capacity of a soil to remain balanced from a chemical, physical and biological perspective, supporting processes and functions that provide a favorable environment for plant growth". Healthy soils are resistant and resilient to environmental stresses and provide greater production stability over time. However, soil health cannot be measured based on a single parameter, but indirectly assessed through chemical, physical and biological indicators that are dynamic and sensitive to management. Thus, the SOHMA Soil Health KIT consists of a set of methods that allow direct assessment in the field of soil health indicators with immediate results, easy to perform and interpret, low cost and that do not generate waste to the environment. These indicators provide information that supports decision-making on the management adopted, in addition to being correlated with the results obtained by standard laboratory methodologies.

- (iii) **Promotion of Entrepreneurship:** these activities are still incipient, as they rely on the advancement of the research and collaborative work to expand, so we expect to have a gradual increase in the performance metrics throughout the project. From now, we highlight ongoing tutorship of a few CCarbon researchers to establishing startups from the forest sector.
- (iv) **Public-Private Partnerships:** There are some initiatives under discussion, but one very important to highlight, with Fundo Vale. Based on the general premise of FAPESP CEPIDs, we are looking for ways to achieve the financial sustainability of CCarbon in the coming years. As the two other pillars of CCarbon (Research and Dissemination) have been so far financed by FAPESP, we are targeting external investments to support the innovation pillar, which has not been sufficiently covered by the FAPESP fund. As part of our strategy, it is important that funds for innovation come from public-private partnerships, so they are heavily linked with an agenda for innovation and deliverables of importance to impacting the sector. In this context, this type of partnership is valuable not only for the funding it may provide, but also by the collaborations and mindset it may stimulate, integrating CCarbon with some of the leading innovation organizations. We chose the Instituto

Vale as a key partner to start such collaboration and have advanced rapidly in the negotiations to receive important financial support from them. We are in the process of signing a MoU to receive funds to structure the innovation team of CCarbon, to be potentially composed of one innovation project manager, one project analyst per research line (soil, plant, atmosphere, animal, digital tools), and one financial manager. The funding would be used to hire these professionals for three years initially, who would work exclusively to foster the innovation activities of CCarbon in a professional and productive way, thus fulfilling an important gap of the project, as most of its researchers do not have a solid experience and background on innovation.

5. First International Scientific Advisory Board Meeting

On August 12th, 2024, the first meeting of the *International Scientific Advisory Board* was held, starting at 9:58 AM and ending at 12h21AM. The meeting was organized in a hybrid format, with presential and videoconferencing participations. The participants were: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri (CCARBON/USP), Douglas Karlen (USDA – Agricultural Research Service), Eden Vilarinho Costa Junior (CCARBON/USP), Rachel Schulte Creamer (Wageningen University), Francisco Mello (Instituto Interamericano de Cooperación para la Agricultura – IICA), Jacques Marcovitch (FEA/USP), Jessica Suarez Campoli (CCARBON/USP), João Luis Nunes Carvalho (Centro Nacional de Pesquisa em Energia e Materiais – CNPEM), Luiz Antonio Martinelli (CENA/USP), Maurício Roberto Cherubin (CCARBON/USP), Mercedes Maria da Cunha Bustamante (Universidade de Brasília), Pedro Brancalion (CCARBON/USP), Pete Smith (University of Aberdeen), Rattan Lal (Ohio State University), Thais Maria Ferreira de Souza Vieira (ESALQ/USP) and Tiago Osorio Ferreira (CCARBON/USP). The only member that could not attend (he was in vacation) was Dr Martial Bernoux (FAO/Rome).

The objective of the meeting was to present the progress of CCARBON in its first year of activities. The Director of CCARBON, Professor Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, gave a general presentation of the research center. The other directors then complemented the presentation.

The Research Director, Professor Maurício Roberto Cherubin, presented the research macro-programs - SOIL, PLANT, ANIMAL, ATMOSPHERE and DIGITAL TOOLS. The professor highlighted that each macro-program has its respective research questions, the division of principal researchers and associate researchers. In terms of

private research projects, the professor also presented three major projects that are being negotiated to be implemented in the near future.

Following this, the Director of Scientific Dissemination, Professor Tiago Osório Ferreira, presented the five dissemination centers: scientific publications, advocacy, training, social media and public awareness. Moreover, the Professor Tiago highlighted the strategy of holding scientific events to generate awareness on CCARBON and present the results of the ongoing activities

In addition, Innovation Director Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion presented some of the activities on the CCARBON innovation front from the first years of the Center's development. Among the innovation strategies, he highlighted international partnerships and promoting private partnerships.

In the sequence, The CCARBON Director highlighted that CCARBON was presented in four ministers to present carbon and discuss how CCARBON can help the Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Economy, Ministry of Science Technology and Ministry of Environment, highlighting the great visibility that is being given to CARBON. Finally, space was opened for discussions and members of the International Scientific Advisory Board asked questions and made general suggestions for the next year's activities.

6. Final Considerations

In its first year of operation, CCARBON has made significant strides in research, innovation, and scientific outreach, laying a robust foundation for its future growth. The center has focused on advancing knowledge about the role of tropical agriculture in carbon capture and greenhouse gas mitigation, resulting in several impactful scientific publications and strategic partnerships. Through its five macro-programs — SOIL, PLANT, ANIMAL, ATMOSPHERE, and DIGITAL TOOLS — CCARBON has engaged over 40 researchers and 100 students and postdoctoral researchers, addressing 19 complex questions related to carbon and climate in agriculture. While the innovation initiatives are still in their early stages, they have set a promising path for future contributions to low-carbon agriculture. Moreover, CCARBON's comprehensive Scientific Dissemination Plan is fostering greater awareness and engagement on environmental issues, leveraging diverse platforms and initiatives to reach a broad

audience. Moving forward, CCARBON is well-positioned to continue advancing its mission of promoting sustainable practices in tropical agriculture and influencing global climate change mitigation efforts.

Looking ahead, CCARBON aims to expand its research and innovation efforts by further exploring the complexities of carbon dynamics in tropical agricultural systems. The center plans to deepen its collaborations with national and international partners, fostering a global network that enhances the exchange of knowledge and best practices. By leveraging emerging technologies and innovative methodologies, CCARBON intends to develop more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices that contribute to climate change mitigation. Additionally, the center will continue to enhance its scientific outreach activities, aiming to increase public awareness and engagement on the importance of low-carbon agriculture. Through these efforts, CCARBON is committed to playing a leading international role in advancing the science and practice of sustainable tropical agriculture and driving meaningful progress toward global climate goals.

Sincerely

Prof. Dr. Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Appendix 1 Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

2.1.1 – Are the Brazilian agricultural soils acting as C sinks or sources?

Principal investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Main objective:

The main objective is to evaluate soil C removals (C sink) and GHG emissions (C source) due to different land use types and adoption of best agricultural management practices across the country. To do so, we are taking into account assessments under annual crops (soybeans, corn, wheat), semi-perennial crops (sugarcane) and perennial crops (coffee, citrus, pasture). For that, existing long-term experiments and chronosequence-based strategies are being adopted under the main edaphoclimatic conditions in Brazil.

Subproject 1.1 - What is the impact of cropping intensification strategies on soil organic matter (SOM) dynamics and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the Brazilian Cerrado biome? is being conducted by *Jorge Luiz Locatelli (PhD student FAPESP: [2022/15778-6](#))*

Main objective:

To evaluate the effect of the intensification of agroecosystems in the soil carbon (C) balance and the quality of SOM in the Brazilian Cerrado.

Specific objectives:

- To identify the current state-of-the art on GHG emissions research in agroecosystems in the Cerrado biome;
- To evaluate changes in C and N stocks, as well as CO₂eq emissions (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) and the soil C balance influenced by the intensification of agroecosystems;
- To assess changes in soil aggregate stability, C allocation in different aggregate classes, and qualitative changes in SOM influenced by the intensification of agroecosystems;
- To predict the long-term C dynamics under cropping intensification and climate change scenarios using modeling techniques.

Main Results

The project is divided into four stages (Figure 1): i) Systematic literature review; ii) Assessment of soil C balance (i.e., changes in soil C stocks + N₂O and CH₄ emissions); iii) Assessment of qualitative changes in SOM (i.e., use of spectroscopic techniques); iv) Prediction of long-term soil C dynamics under cropping intensification strategies and climate change scenarios (i.e., use of modeling techniques).

Figure 1. Overall view of the experimental Project including the assessed sites, cropping systems, and stages to be developed. ¹Soil tillage, ²Soybean, ³Cotton, ⁴*Brachiaria* sp., ⁵*Crotalaria* sp., ⁶Millet, CT: Conventional tillage, NT: No-tillage.

The first stage (systematic literature review), which aims to determine the current state-of-the-art on GHG emissions research in the Cerrado biome, has already been completed, and is currently under review in the *Catena Journal*. The results obtained in this stage can be seen in Annex 1. Briefly, it was observed that “GHG” subject has been fairly investigated, having a huge discrepancy compared to other related topics such as SOM. Most of the studies only mention GHG-related terms, not measuring it. Only 16% (from 236) of studies presented measured data on GHG emissions in agricultural systems. These studies were conducted mainly in the south-central part of the region and were mostly limited to short-term experiments (< 5 years) or monitoring periods (< 1 year). Our findings suggest a concerning gap related to the monitoring of GHG fluxes in the Cerrado region, particularly within the northern part where Brazil’s new agricultural frontier, the Matopiba region, is located. Therefore, efforts should prioritize generating comprehensive GHG data for Cerrado agriculture while employing more robust monitoring protocols.

The third (iii) step, whose objective is to evaluate how cropping diversification strategies based on cover crops and no-tillage affect SOM dynamics and aggregation in a tropical clayey Oxisol, also was concluded. The complete results can be observed in the Annex 2 (currently under final revision for submission). In summary, results showed that bulk soil C and N stocks increased by ~20% and 29%, respectively, under the most complex crop rotation systems with cover crops compared to soybean-maize double cropping. The complex crop rotations based on cover crops also increased soil aggregate stability, with results indicating that the proportion of large macroaggregates in the 5-10

and 10-20 cm layers doubled compared to the soybean-maize double cropping system; while a decrease in the microaggregates fraction was observed for the same layers. The improvements in the aggregate stability under the complex crop rotations were followed by increased C levels within aggregates. On average (considering different soil layers), C levels were increased by ~48%, 32%, and 34% for large macro, macro, and microaggregates, respectively. The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analysis showed that complex rotations increased the proportion of aromatic C fraction in the large macroaggregate fraction from the 0-5 cm layer, while reducing the content of C=O/O-C-O and C-O. The observed changes in the C composition may have contributed to the soil aggregate stability alterations. Overall, results show that cropping diversification based on cover cropping and crop rotation systems under no-tillage are effective strategies for increasing soil aggregate stability and promoting soil C sequestration in tropical Cerrado.

The step “iv”, whose objective is to use the DayCent model to simulate the impact of crop diversification and tillage on SOC dynamics in the long-term (~50 years), is concluded and under review at Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment Journal. The complete results can be observed in the Annex 3. Briefly, results indicate that SOC stocks would decrease under the long-term (~50 years) soybean-cotton succession, regardless of soil management (-0.04 to -0.17 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). Crop diversification with crop rotation and cover crops (i.e., millet, ruzigrass, sunn hemp) had the highest SOC accrual potential (~0.71 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹), resulting in SOC stocks of up to 130 Mg C ha⁻¹ by 2070. Ruzigrass, either single or intercropped with maize on crop succession systems, showed substantial potential for soil C sequestration (~0.55 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹) and could be a viable strategy if implementing more complex rotations is not feasible. The SSP2 – 4.5 and SSP4 – 8.5 climate change scenarios increased SOC stocks by ~6.3 and 8.2% in SOC across treatments by 2070, respectively. Results suggest that diversified cropping systems are a promising strategy for increasing SOC sequestration, and they offer valuable guidance for enhancing current management practices in the region.

Step “ii” is being carried out and is expected to be completed by August 2025.

Highlights

- 1- Research on GHG emissions in the Cerrado biome still is poorly developed, where the few conducted studies measuring only N₂O (not CO₂ and CH₄) in short-term experiments using low-frequency and short-term monitoring schedules;
- 2- Cropping intensification can promote soil C sequestration through increased soil aggregate stability and C accrual in large macroaggregates, and can alter soil C composition in these fractions;
- 3- Long-term predictions of soil C dynamics under cropping intensification strategies suggested the potential for soil C sequestration even under climate change scenarios, mitigating soil C losses originating from the land-conversion process;

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

For the next 1-year period, activities will consist of finishing soil C balance calculations and additional simulations for GHG emissions that will be performed using the DayCent Model. The soil C balance calculations will be performed considering C stock rate changes obtained from DayCent model (Annex 2) and the N₂O and CH₄ emissions data obtained from field measurements presented in this report. The additional simulations using the DayCent model for N₂O and CH₄ emissions will be conducted to estimate the

long-term impact of climate change scenarios on these GHG emissions under the different cropping intensifications scenarios.

Other research content (partial results):

Figure 1. Fluxos de $\text{CH}_4\text{-C}$ (a), $\text{N}_2\text{O-N}$ (b), e $\text{CO}_2\text{-C}$ (c) para o protocolo conduzido em Itiquira – MT. CS1-SM: Sucessão entre soja e milho; CS2-SB: Sucessão entre soja *Brachiaria* sp.; CR1-SMCM+B: Rotação entre soja, milho, *Crotalaria* sp., e milho consorciado com *Brachiaria* sp.; CR2-SCM+B: Rotação entre soja, *Crotalaria* sp., e milho consorciado com *Brachiaria* sp.; CR3-SCM+B1y: Rotação entre soja, *Crotalaria* sp., e milho consorciado com *Brachiaria* sp. por um ano.

Figure 2. Emissões acumuladas de CH₄-C (a), N₂O-N (b), e CO₂-C (c) para o protocolo conduzido em Itiquira – MT. CS1-SM: Sucessão entre soja e milho; CS2-SB: Sucessão entre soja e *Brachiaria* sp.; CR1-SMCM+B: Rotação entre soja, milho, *Crotalaria* sp., e milho consorciado com *Brachiaria* sp.; CR2-SCM+B: Rotação entre soja, *Crotalaria* sp., e milho consorciado com *Brachiaria* sp.; CR3-SCM+B1y: Rotação entre soja, *Crotalaria* sp., e milho consorciado com *Brachiaria* sp. por um ano.

Figura 3. Fluxos de $\text{CH}_4\text{-C}$ (a), $\text{N}_2\text{O-N}$ (b), e $\text{CO}_2\text{-C}$ (c) para o experimento conduzido em Costa Rica – MS. SA-CT: Soja + algodão sob Sistema convencional de manejo do solo; SA-NT: soja + algodão em plantio direto; SA+B: Soja + algodão e *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+C: Soja + algodão e *Crotalaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+M: Soja + algodão e milho em plantio direto.

Figure 4. Emissões acumuladas de CH₄-C (a), N₂O-N (b), e CO₂-C (c) para o experimento conduzido em Costa Rica – MS. SA-CT: Soja + algodão sob Sistema convencional de manejo do solo; SA-NT: soja + algodão em plantio direto; SA+B: Soja + algodão e *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+C: Soja + algodão e *Crotalaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+M: Soja + algodão e milho em plantio direto

Figura 5. Fluxos de $\text{CH}_4\text{-C}$ (a), $\text{N}_2\text{O-N}$ (b), e $\text{CO}_2\text{-C}$ (c) para o experimento conduzido em Diamantino – MT. SA-CT: Soja + algodão sob Sistema convencional de manejo do solo; SA-NT: soja + algodão em plantio direto; SA+B: Soja + algodão e *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+C: Soja + algodão e *Crotalaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+M: Soja + algodão e milho + *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto.

Figure 6. Emissões acumuladas de CH₄-C (a), N₂O-N (b), e CO₂-C (c) para o experimento conduzido em Diamantino – MT. SA-CT: Soja + algodão sob Sistema convencional de manejo do solo; SA-NT: soja + algodão em plantio direto; SA+B: Soja + algodão e *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+C: Soja + algodão e *Crotalaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+M: Soja + algodão e milho + *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto.

Anexo 3:

Figura 7. Estoque de carbono (Mg ha⁻¹) acumulado para a camada de 0-30 cm em Itiquira – MT (A), Costa Rica – MS (B), e Diamantino – MT (C). SM: Soja + milho; SB: Soja + *Brachiaria* sp.; SSHMB_4sp: Soja + *Crotalaria* sp. + Milho + *Brachiaria* s.; SSHMB1y_4sp: Soja + *Crotalaria* sp. + Milho + *Brachiaria* sp. por um ano; SMiSHMB_5sp: Soja + milho + *Crotalaria* sp. + Milho + *Brachiaria* sp.; SA-CT: Soja + algodão sob Sistema convencional de manejo do solo; SA-NT: soja + algodão em plantio direto; SA+B: Soja + algodão e *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+C: Soja + algodão e *Crotalaria* sp. em plantio direto; SA+M: Soja + algodão e milho + *Brachiaria* sp. em plantio direto.

Subproject 1.2 - How can the CENTURY-based module coupled with DSSAT be improved through detailed evaluation of soil GHG emissions predictions to enhance future simulations of the effects of sustainable agricultural practices on GHG reduction and soil carbon sequestration? is being conducted by *Evandro Henrique Figueiredo Moura da Silva* (Post-Doc FAPESP: [2022/16715-8](#))

Main objective:

The main goal was to evaluate and improve the predictions of GHG emissions from DSSAT in tropical environments under several crop management to allow the effect of sustainable agricultural practices to be evaluated on reducing GHG emissions from crop fields.

Main Results

This study investigated the sensitivity of the DSSAT-GHG model's parameters. It optimized them against observed methane emissions, alongside evaluating crop phenology, aboveground biomass, and grain yield under different irrigation practices. The findings highlight the significant impact of varying BRAD and WFPS_{thresh} parameters on methane emission simulations, particularly under alternate wetting and drying (AWD) irrigation practices. Methane emissions were observed to be highest when WFPS_{thresh} exceeded 45%, while BRAD influenced emission rates when soil water content ranged between 50% and 90%.

For crop phenology, the model effectively simulated the R4 and R9 stages across multiple rice cultivars, with biases between simulated and observed values ranging from 0 to 18 days. Grain yield and aboveground biomass simulations showed close alignment with measured data, with biases ranging from 12 to 1,591 kg ha⁻¹ for biomass and 0 to 802 kg ha⁻¹ for grain yield. The study noted that the A705 cultivar exhibited the best grain yield simulation, while XP 113 performed best for aboveground biomass.

In terms of methane emissions, the calibrated DSSAT-GHG model showed improved accuracy, particularly under AWD conditions, aligning closely with field data and demonstrating a reduction in methane emissions compared to continuous flooding (CF) practices. The AWD condition effectively reduced methane production rates, demonstrating a significant reduction compared to CF conditions.

Long-term scenario analysis revealed that irrigation practices with reduced water application, such as sprinkler systems triggered at 50% soil water remaining, led to lower methane emissions and slightly higher grain yields compared to CF. This practice also demonstrated the highest crop water productivity (CWMP), making it the most sustainable option among the scenarios evaluated.

Overall, the study confirms the effectiveness of the DSSAT-GHG model in simulating methane emissions and crop performance under varying irrigation practices in a subtropical environment, providing valuable insights for optimizing water use and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in paddy rice cultivation.

Highlights

- 1- Simulated GHG with CSM-CERES-Rice of DSSAT was compared against measured daily CH₄ emissions data in paddy rice
- 2- Soil-related parameter changes were proposed to improve CH₄ simulations under Alternate Wetting and Drying conditions.
- 3-The model successfully simulated CH₄ emissions under non-flooding conditions following parameter changes.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

In the upcoming project cycle, the primary focus will be on evaluating the code and the model for simulating CO₂ and N₂O emissions within the rice-soybean cropping system, as well as extending this evaluation to other cropping systems. This will involve a detailed analysis of the model's accuracy and reliability in predicting greenhouse gas emissions across different agricultural practices, aiming to enhance its applicability and effectiveness in diverse cropping scenarios. The outcomes of this evaluation will contribute to more informed decision-making in agricultural management, particularly in optimizing practices to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions.

As a result, there is an advanced draft, an abstract submission and a poster acceptance:

Evandro H Figueiredo Moura da Silva, Gerrit Hoogenboom, Kenneth J Boote, Santiago Vianna Cuadra, Cheryl H Porter, Walkyria Bueno Scivittaro, Silvio Steinmetz, Carlos E. Pellegrino Cerri. **Implications of water management on methane emissions and grain yield in paddy rice: A case study under subtropical conditions in Brazil using crop modeling** (advanced draft)

Evandro Figueiredo Moura da Silva, University of Sao Paulo, Piracicaba, São Paulo, US, Jorge L Locatelli, University of São Paulo, Piracicaba, SP, Brazil, Gerrit Hoogenboom, P.O. Box 110570, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, US, Kenneth J. Boote, Agric. and Biol. Engr. Dept., 120 Rogers Hall, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, US, Cheryl H. Porter, 103 Frazier Rogers Hall, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL and Carlos E Pellegrino Cerri, Department of Soil Science, Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture - University of São Paulo, Piracicaba, Brazil. **Performance of the DSSAT in Simulating Greenhouse Gases Emissions Under Soybean-Cotton Cropping Sequence.** CSSA, SSSA International Annual Meeting (abstract submission).

Poster Acceptance Notification - 5th Global Food Security Conference Towards equitable, sustainable and resilient food systems. Title: **Implications of water management on methane emissions and crop yield in paddy rice: A case study in Brazil using the CSM-CERES-Rice** Authors: Evandro Figueiredo Moura da Silva, Santiago Vianna Cuadra, Gerrit Hoogenboom, Kenneth Boote, Cheryl Porter, Walkyria Bueno Scivittaro, Silvio Steinmetz, Carlos Pellegrino Cerri Presenter author: Evandro Figueiredo Moura da Silva

Subproject 1.3 – “Impacts of land use change on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter in production systems under pasture and regenerative agriculture in the subtropical and tropical regions of Brazil” is being conducted by *Daniel Aquino De Borba (PhD student, scholarship from CAPES)*

Main objective:

To evaluate the impacts of land use change on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter throughout the soil profile in production systems under pasture and regenerative agriculture in the subtropical and tropical region of Brazil.

Main Results:

The project covers three study areas that will be evaluated separately by region, whose experimental areas are composed of agricultural plantations in a regenerative agriculture system (diversified and intensified systems) and a pasture area. The objective is to measure the carbon stock in the soil, understand the dynamics of organic matter and its permanence in these agroecosystems. The areas are located in important grain and beef/dairy cattle producing regions in Brazil, namely: Faxinal dos Guedes – Santa Catarina (SC), Itirapina – São Paulo (SP) and Sinop – Mato Grosso (MT).

o In Faxinal dos Guedes-SC the treatments were: conventional pasture, regenerative agricultural system and traditional direct planting.

- o In Itirapina-SP the treatments were: conventional pasture and regenerative agroforestry system.
- o In Sinop-MT the treatments were: conventional pasture, managed pasture, regenerative agricultural system, crop-livestock integration and direct planting system.

Soil samples were collected in all study areas following an experimental design using a grid sampling method, covering 1 hectare with nine points spaced 50 meters apart. The soil sample collection procedure involved obtaining three distinct categories: deformed, semi-deformed and undeformed. These samples were used to analyze the total carbon (C%) and nitrogen (N%) contents, as well as to determine the C and N stocks. Additionally, the deformed samples will be used in the chemical characterization of the soil, including nutrient contents in the areas. Simultaneously, additional deformed samples were collected at a depth of 0-10 cm. These samples were later used to evaluate soil microbiological indicators (activity of the enzyme arylsulfatase, β -glucosidase and determination of C and N in microbial biomass). Semi-deformed samples were obtained to investigate the stability of soil aggregates (aggregate particle size distribution and physical fractionation of soil organic matter). Finally, undisturbed samples were obtained using Kopeck rings, collected in each of the indicated layers, up to 1 m depth. The undisturbed samples, obtained through Kopeck rings (Soil density (Ds)), the deformed samples to determine the C and N contents of the soil, consequently the C and N stock. Ds analyses, chemical analysis of the soil and analyzes of the activity of arylsulfatase and β -glucosidase enzymes were completed for all areas. For the analysis of C% and N% content, we are in the process of finalizing these data in the laboratory.

For a more in-depth understanding of the partial results, to facilitate the formulation of hypotheses, it is necessary to submit the results to analysis of variance and comparison of means, which have not been carried out to date. It is important to highlight that the main objective of the work is subject to adjustments and analyzes throughout the doctorate.

Highlights

1. Carbon Sequestration and Greenhouse Gas Mitigation: The research investigates the potential of regenerative agriculture to increase soil carbon stocks, thereby mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This is particularly significant in degraded areas, such as pastures, which have a high potential for carbon sequestration when managed sustainably.
2. Impact of Land Use Change: The study assesses how converting pasture areas to regenerative agriculture systems can alter the quantity and quality of soil organic matter (SOM), driving changes in SOM composition and stabilization, and contributing to soil health and resilience.
3. Development of Sustainable Strategies: The research aims to develop strategies to enhance the adoption of regenerative agriculture practices, with the goal of improving soil quality and meeting Brazil's climate targets, thus contributing to the sustainable development of agriculture in the country.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle:

For the next semesters (2024/2 and 2025/1), the following activities are planned in the schedule: i) complete soil analyzes (physical fractionation of SOM, stability of aggregates, extraction of DNA from the soil, fluorescence spectroscopy induced by laser

(FIL)); ii) tabulation, organization, graphing and statistical analysis and, iii) writing science and publishing articles and iv) writing and submitting the thesis.

The activities described in item “i”, semi-deformed samples for analysis of aggregate stability, and simultaneously, the disturbed samples are being processed to determine the particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) fractions of the matter soil organic matter. Both analyzes are expected to be completed by the end of the first half of 2024/2. The activity of item “i”, DNA and FIL extraction, is expected to be carried out in the first half of 2025/1. The activities presented in item “ii” must be carried out in parallel with the other tasks mentioned, being developed while the information is obtained. During the entire period (items “i”, “ii”), writing activities will be reconciled and the results will be published (item “iii”) following the schedule presented in the proposal.

Information from these data will allow the identification of management practices and the degree of intensification of systems that are most suitable for storing carbon in the soil, with the aim of minimizing the potential for global warming. Based on this information being generated, it will be possible to more assertively recommend mitigating management practices in cultivated areas, contributing to reducing the negative impacts of agriculture on greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable production systems.

Subproject 1.4 – “Land-use change effects on soil greenhouse gas emissions in the Matopiba region: the new Brazilian agricultural frontier” is being conducted by *Caroline Andreatto Zanoli* (Undergraduate student FAPESP: 2024/06008-8).

Brazil has experienced an accelerated agricultural expansion process in recent decades, with emphasis in the so-called Matopiba region. This new agricultural frontier, located in the Cerrado biome, covers ~73 million hectares, distributed over the states of Maranhão, Tocantins, Piauí, and Bahia. However, despite the well-known potential of the Cerrado biome for agricultural activities, the Matopiba region is located in an area characterized by unique climate and soil aspects (i.e., short rain season and sandy soils), which raises the risk of soil degradation as agriculture expands. Disturbance of natural areas is known to have a direct impact on soil organic carbon (C) dynamics. The land conversion followed by mismanagement and the lack of best management practices is between the main activities that promote soil decarbonization through greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to the atmosphere. The objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of land-use change on soil GHG emissions in areas of agricultural expansion in the Matopiba region. The study will be conducted in multiple locations, under the use of native forest and annual crops; the latter under different levels of crop diversification (i.e., successional and rotational systems). The GHG emissions will be monitored for a period of nine months, during the first and the second crop seasons. The fluxes of CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄ gases will be measured using static chambers, and the daily fluxes will be used to calculate the accumulated emissions. Additionally, the yield-scaled emissions will be calculated based on the system's production history. The data will be submitted to analysis of variance, and when significant, to the Tukey test ($p < 0.05$).

Description of activities

The study will be carried out in long-term experiments conducted under multiple crop system cultivation in the Matopiba region. The treatments will compose different land uses (i.e., native forest areas, pastures, and annual crops, with the latter under levels of

intensification (tillage and cropping systems). The fluxes of CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ gases will be measured for a period of nine months, using the manual static chambers method (Stuedler et al., 1991). Sampling will be carried out monthly, and the sampling frequency will be adjusted according to environmental variations (e.g., climate) and management (e.g., soil preparation, fertilization, sowing); with more intense assessment frequency in these events (e.g., daily samplings for a week) and less intense between management events (e.g., weekly samplings). The concentration of CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ gases will be quantified using a Shimadzu 14A chromatograph.

where f is the N₂O or CH₄ flux in $\mu\text{g N or C m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$, respectively; Q is the amount of each gas in the chamber at the time of sampling ($\mu\text{g N or } \mu\text{g C per chamber}$); P is the chamber pressure, which was assumed to be equal to the atmospheric pressure (1 atm); V is the chamber headspace volume (8 L); R is the universal gas constant ($0.08205 \text{ atm L mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$); T is the temperature inside the chamber at the time of sampling (K); and A is the surface area of the metal steel collar (0.082 m^2).

The cumulative emission (kg ha^{-1}) of each gas during the period will be calculated by plotting daily fluxes through time and calculating the area below the curve by trapezoidal integration (Jantalia et al., 2008; Bayer et al., 2015). Finally, the yield-scaled emissions (i.e., emissions intensities) of each gas (i.e., CO₂, N₂O and CH₄) will be calculated by dividing the gases emissions per unit of biomass produced in each assessed treatment (Mosier et al., 2006).

The data will be submitted to analysis of variance, and when significant, to the Tukey test ($p < 0.05$).

Soil CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ fluxes will be calculated using Eq. (1)

$$f = \Delta Q / PV \quad (1)$$

Timetable

Activities	1 st bi.	2 nd bi.	3 rd bi.	4 th bi.	5 th bi.	6 th bi.
Literature review	x	x	x	x	x	x
Selection of experimental areas and soil sampling	x					
Greenhouse gas sampling and analysis	x	x	x	x	x	
Results interpretation and statistical analysis						x
Elaboration of scientific papers						x
Elaboration of reports			x			x

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Subproject 1.5 - “Land-use change and agricultural intensification: impacts on carbon and nitrogen distribution in soil profiles of the Amazon-Cerrado frontier” by *Gustavo Vicentini Popin (PhD student FAPESP: 2022/07695-3)*

Research Question: Land-use change and agricultural intensification: impacts on carbon and nitrogen distribution in soil profiles of the Amazon-Cerrado frontier

We hypothesized that land-use change and agricultural intensification, such as the double cropping system, alter the vertical distribution of soil C and N stocks in the Amazon-Cerrado frontier by causing significant changes to soil C and N biochemistry in the surface 1 m, consequently altering the large C and N stocks stored from 2 m to 8 m. We sampled in native forest, pasture, soybean cropland, soybean-maize cropland, and an area of forest that was deforested and maintained cleared but never pastured or cropped.

Main objective:

Our objectives were: i) measure soil C and N stocks on different land uses to 800 cm; ii) identify the relations among soil C and N fractions, land use and soil depth; iii) evaluate how changes on topsoil modify the C and N stored in deep-soils of the Brazilian Amazon-Cerrado transition.

Main Results

Over the last decades, most events of agriculture expansion and intensification have occurred in the South hemisphere (Pellegrini and Fernández, 2018; Winkler et al., 2021), especially along the Brazilian Amazon and Cerrado biomes frontier (Lathuillière et al., 2016; Stabile et al., 2020a). The conversion of native vegetation on different land-uses results in losses of superficial carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) from soil and vegetation to atmosphere (IPCC, 2006; Paustian et al., 2016; Watson et al., 2000). Yet, little is known about C and N changes on deep-soil profiles. The present study aimed to assess the impact of land use change and agricultural intensification to soil C and N in the Amazon-Cerrado agriculture frontier and identify relations between topsoil vs deep-soil – from 0 until 800 cm (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Topsoil and deep-soil C and N fractions dynamics after land-use change and agricultural intensification at the Amazon-Cerrado frontier. Soil parameters = C stocks - total soil carbon stocks, N stocks – total soil nitrogen stocks, MAOM – mineral associated organic matter, POM – particulate organic matter, WEC - water-extractable carbon, WEN = water-extractable nitrogen, NO₃⁻ = nitrate stock, NH₄⁺= ammonium stock.

We showed significant reductions of soil C in the mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) fraction after conversion of forest to no-till single-cropping soybean. Although no reduction of soil C stocks was detected in the recent deforested area, superficial water-extractable C was drastically reduced by vegetation removal.

Sustainable intensification showed potential to prevent greater C losses or even restore C values to native vegetation levels.

Soil C stocks to 800 cm ranged from 168 Mg ha⁻¹ in the sandy area to 288 Mg ha⁻¹ in medium and clay soils. The top 100 cm stored ~30% of the C stocks for areas of medium/clay texture and 40% for the sandy soil. The proportion increases to approximately 45% at 0-200, and 60% at 0-300 cm. The sandy area differed from the clay areas in two aspects: i) a higher proportion of carbon stocks on the first 0-100 cm, 40%; and ii) the 0-800 cm soil stocks were 40% lower. Interestingly, no significant differences for soil C stocks were detected after the 0-300 cm layer.

Soil N stock declined by 40% in the first 0-10 cm and 20% to 50 cm in the recent deforested area; such N losses occurred from the particulate organic matter fraction. In all cases, N stocks in the MAOM fraction were lower to soil forest values in the first 10 cm. The soil N stocks to 800 cm varied from 14 Mg ha⁻¹ to 18 Mg ha⁻¹ with no significant difference among land-uses. Overall, 40% and 60% of the total soil N stock to 800 cm were in the first 100 cm and 300 cm, respectively. In the recent deforested area, less than 28% was in the 0-100 cm soil depth.

Soil ammonium and nitrate stocks to 0-800 cm were the highest at recent deforested area and lowest in native forest. The large portion of the nitrate stocks were in the first 0-200 cm, while croplands had the greatest stocks from 200-600 cm. These results suggest that deforestation, rather than agriculture implementation and intensification was the cause for inorganic-N surplus on Amazon-Cerrado transition profiles.

In this context, these findings must can support decision-makers, politicians, and scientists in proposing financial incentive programs, such as the national-level "Renovagro" (formerly the "ABC" program – Low Carbon Emissions in Agriculture), alongside other sustainable agricultural financing instruments like voluntary initiatives (*e.g.*, blended finance, green bonds, carbon market and fair trade) aiming to foster Climate-smart agriculture (FAO, 2013). These initiatives translate into improving agricultural production (food and energy security), whilst enhances resilience to climate change by promoting practices that improve soil health and foster long-term deep carbon storage in the soil. As a result, agriculture emerges as a potential Nature-based Solution.

We also hope that our findings can support decision-makers, politicians, and scientists in international forums, such as COP/UN and help develop strategies to increase soil carbon sequestrations on topsoil and in the deep layers, *e.g.*, achieve Brazilian goals assumed during the COP 21 – Paris agreement. Finally, we encourage more detailed studies that include a wider range of areas, soil types, soil attributes, land uses, and analytical tools to enhance our understanding of soil carbon dynamics over time following land-use change and subsequent land management practices, thereby expanding our knowledge of deep soils in tropical conditions.

Highlights

1- The soil C stocks to 800 cm ranged from 168.4 Mg ha⁻¹ to 288.3 Mg ha⁻¹ while the average total soil N stocks from 0-800 cm was 15.4 Mg ha⁻¹, with no significant difference among uses.

2- Soil carbon between 300-800 cm were relatively uninfluenced by land use but more dependent on the parental material and soil texture (clay content).

3- Soil inorganic-N stocks (nitrate and ammonium) to 0-800 cm in deforested site were 3-folds greater to forest. Croplands had the greatest stocks from 200-600 cm.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

In the next 1-year cycle, we expect to finish the biological data analysis. The biological analyses were conducted on soil samples from the 0-10 cm layer from all treatments. The samples were collected at four random points per use (a total of 20 samples). After being stored at -20°C, the total DNA was extracted from 0.25 g of soil using the DNeasy PowerSoil kit (QIAGEN Laboratories, Carlsbad, California, USA), following the manufacturer's instructions. The integrity of the extracted material was verified using 1.2% agarose gel in electrophoresis at 80 V for 40 minutes, in the presence of 1x TAE buffer solution (Tris, Acetate, EDTA) and GelRed® dye (Biotium, California, USA). A NanoDrop® 1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) was used to assess the quality and quantity of the DNA. Samples with well-defined bands and a 260:230 nm ratio close to 1.8 were considered suitable for analysis. After receiving the raw data, the bioinformatics phase began, with the first activity being the determination of diversity indices by Simpson and Shannon for the 16S rRNA gene of bacteria (using the primers 515F (5'-GTGCCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA-3') and 806R (5'-GGACTACHVGGGTWTCTAAT-3')) and ITS of fungi (using the primers ITS1-1F-F (5'-CTTGGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA-3') and ITS1-1F-R (5'-GCTGCGTTCTTCATCGATGC-3')). We are currently processing the data and generating new figures for a scientific publication which aims to identify changes in microbial composition and structure, and abundance of gene due to different types of land-use change at the Amazon-Cerrado biome frontier.

Subproject 1.6

Selection of potential areas and pasture management practices for sequestering carbon in Brazilian soils: a modeling approach is being conducted by *João Marcos Villela (Post-Doc FAPESP: [2023/09533-3](#))*

Research Question:

What are the best strategies (technical-economic) to enhance carbon sequestration through the recovery of degraded pastures in Brazil to compose the national restoration plan and contribute to achieving the goals set out in the NDC?

Main objective:

This project aims to evaluate different pasture recovery scenarios through mathematical modeling (DayCent and LandSHIFT models), aiming to enhance carbon sequestration in the main agricultural regions of Brazil. To achieve this goal, the following secondary objectives are proposed (achieved in this first year of the project):

- ✓ Develop a geospatial database with data on soil organic carbon stocks (SOC^{stocks}), socioeconomic data and other data that support the construction of pasture recovery scenarios predicted by the proposed modeling approach;
- ✓ Conduct a meta-analysis with data related to SOC^{stocks} in order to measure the effects of pasture management practices on soil carbon accumulation;
- ✓ Select study areas that include the data the models require and preferably located in regions with extensive areas of degraded pastures.

Main Results

During the review and data collection stage on SOC^{stocks} in pastures, a significant number of studies were identified, which are generally well distributed among Brazilian biomes, with high densities in the main Brazilian agricultural regions (Fig. 1a). A total of 127 studies were identified, with the Cerrado being the biome with the largest number of studies (55), followed by the Atlantic Forest (37), which together account for 72% of the total studies conducted in Brazil (Fig. 1b). The Amazon has twice as many studies (18) as the Caatinga (9). At the same time, the Pampa and Pantanal presented the lowest number of studies, respectively (6 and 2). Completing this extensive project stage resulted in the first product of the activities planned for the work period, the georeferenced database of SOC^{stocks} in pastures in Brazil, with data available in the literature. In addition to revealing information on the amount of SOC^{stocks} data in Brazil and how these data are distributed (geographically and along the soil profile), the database also allowed for the generation of a quantitative overview of soil carbon stocks for Brazilian biomes.

Figure 1. Map showing the location of studies containing data on SOC^{stocks} in pastures distributed across Brazilian biomas a); total number of studies in Brazil divided by biomas.

Figure 2a compares the SOC^{stocks} of pasture (nominal and improved) for the 0–20 cm layer among the biomas with the largest areas of degraded pasture. It is noted that the Atlantic Forest presented the highest average value of soil carbon stock (62.4 ± 22.4 Mg ha⁻¹) about the other biomas. The value was approximately 43 and 28% higher ($p < 0.05$) than that of the Caatinga (35.5 ± 15.0 Mg ha⁻¹) and Amazon (45.2 ± 10.6 Mg ha⁻¹), respectively, and showed no significant difference with the Cerrado biome. The SOC^{stocks} of the Cerrado (56.0 ± 17.6 Mg ha⁻¹) was also significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than that of

the Caatinga and Amazon, with percentage differences of 37 and 19%, respectively. Although the value for the Amazon was higher than that for the Caatinga, no significant difference was observed. These results may be associated with the high standard deviation values observed between the values for the biomes, which indicate high data variability, also explaining the lack of difference between the Atlantic Forest and the Cerrado. The results suggest that the soil carbon accumulation pattern occurs in the following order: Atlantic Forest > Cerrado > Amazon > Caatinga. The variability observed between the carbon stocks of the biomes can be partially explained by the climate factor, in which subtropical (Cfa, Cfb, Cwa and Cwb) and tropical (Af, Am, As and Aw) climates tend to accumulate greater amounts of carbon in the soil, while in semi-arid climates (BSh) accumulation is significantly reduced. This information helps to explain the significant differences between the values for the Atlantic Forest (65% of the area of this biome is under subtropical climates) and Cerrado (Aw climate present in 74% of the biome) in relation to the Caatinga (more than 80% of the biome covered by the semi-arid climate). Additionally, the high altitudes observed in the Atlantic Forest and Cerrado (Central Plateau) biomes also favor soil carbon accumulation in these biomes.

Figure 2. SOC stocks at pasture (nominal/improved) at 0 – 20 cm depth for biomes with larger areas of degraded pasture. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between at the biomes a), SOC storage/loss rates for degraded pasture converted to nominal/improved pasture. The black dotted line represents the boundary between a positive and negative response to the response ratio. Effect sizes were considered significant if 95% CI did not overlap zero.

From the database developed, it was possible to quantitatively evaluate the effect of restoring degraded pasture, using meta-analysis techniques to measure soil carbon accumulation resulting from the transition from degraded to nominal/improved pasture. Figure 2b shows the carbon accumulation rates resulting from the transition from a degraded to nominal/improved pasture system at the four depths evaluated (0–10, 0–20, 0–30 and 0–100 cm). It is noted that except for the 0–20 cm layer in which the difference was not significant, the effect of soil C accumulation was observed in the other layers, resulting in average rates (Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) of 0.4 ± 0.2 in the 0–10 cm layer, 0.68 ± 0.3 in the 0–30 cm layer and 0.79 ± 0.4 for 0–100 cm. Although the estimated rates are generalized, obtained from the set of pairs of biomes with the greatest data availability (Cerrado, Atlantic Forest and Amazon), the result contributes to updating/complementing the values generated by other authors. Another practical contribution, considering the

selection of potential areas for soil carbon sequestration, would be to direct new analyses to locations where the greatest increases were observed.

Highlights

- 1- Cerrado and Atlantic Forest account for 72% of pasture studies conducted in Brazil;
- 2- SOC^{Stocks} in the Atlantic Forest and Cerrado are on average 40 and 24% greater than those in the Caatinga and Amazon, respectively;
- 3- Average rate of soil carbon accumulation through pasture recovery varies from 0.4 to 0.79 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in the 0-100 cm layer.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

The work plan presented below describes the activities that will be developed in the second year of the project (July 1, 2024 to June 30, 2025). During this period, activities will focus on the modeling approach, applying the DayCent and LandSHIFT models to simulate soil carbon dynamics and land use changes for the predicted scenarios. More specifically, the following activities will be carried out:

- ✓ Simulate soil carbon dynamics for the selected study areas using the DayCent model;
- ✓ Calibrate and validate the model in order to obtain consistent simulations of potential changes in carbon stocks that allow for the assessment of how different pasture management scenarios can contribute to a restoration plan;
- ✓ Evaluate potential changes in soil carbon stocks obtained through simulations of land use change scenarios (LandSHIFT Model);
- ✓ Generate prioritization maps for the recovery of pasture areas, indicating the locations with the most significant potential for GHG mitigation, considering the best cost-benefit.

Subproject 1.7 – “Does the conversion of degraded pasture to agriculture based on regenerative practices increase the stock and quality (molecular complexity) of organic carbon in soil aggregates?” is being conducted by *Marcelo Trybek (Master student FAPESP: 2024/05184-7)*

Research Question:

- Does the conversion of degraded pasture to agriculture based on regenerative practices increase the stock and quality (molecular complexity) of organic carbon in soil aggregates?
- Is glomalin associated with increased soil aggregation and carbon stock during the conversion of degraded pasture to regenerative agriculture?
- In which size aggregates is glomalin most important for C storage in these areas?
- Can the conversion of degraded pastures to regenerative models improve soil health and ecosystem services?

Main objective:

Evaluate the impact of land use change by converting degraded pasture into regenerative agriculture on the sequestration and quality of intra-aggregate carbon, glomalin content, and soil health in the Brazilian Cerrado region.

Main Results

This project is in its initial phase, and as such, we do not yet have preliminary results. However, we believe that this work will be pioneering in its detailed study of the soil organic matter (SOM) fractions within aggregate classes, particularly in the context of certified regenerative agriculture.

The study will focus on Brazil's primary agricultural region, which holds particular significance as these areas are agricultural frontiers located in the Cerrado Biome. In this region, knowledge about SOM dynamics is both recent and scarce. The quantitative and qualitative information obtained will enhance our understanding of the: stabilization mechanisms of SOM under different conditions; establish reference potentials for carbon sequestration through the adoption of regenerative practices in degraded areas; infer the residence time of the sequestered carbon; unravel the interaction between C, glomalin and soil structure, and identify and recommend management practices that enhances the soil's role as a stable and long-lasting sink for atmospheric CO₂.

The proposal aligns with the objectives of the National Program for the Conversion of Degraded Pastures into Sustainable Agricultural and Forestry Production Systems (PNCPP), recently established through by federal government decree No. 11,815. Therefore, understanding the dynamics and nature of SOM in its interaction with glomalin and soil structure is critical for large-scale decision-making regarding land use change.

The strategies and insights generated by this work will have the potential to guide national public policies that are based on a decarbonized economy, such as the ABC+ Program. Furthermore, the results are expected to inspire the widespread adoption of regenerative agriculture, especially for producers interested in the carbon market.

Ultimately, these advances are essential for Brazil to achieve the goals set before the international community to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In the long term, they could position the country as a leading global player in regenerative agriculture, in function of significant potential for expanding over degraded pasture areas.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

For the next year of the project, soil samples are expected to be collected in certified regenerative agriculture areas belonging to the Scheffer Group in the Cerrado region, along with samples from other evaluated land uses. These samples will undergo chemical, physical and biological characterization, as well as carbon and nitrogen determination in bulk soil. Furthermore, aggregate sizes will be separated using the wet sieving method in a Yoder-type vertical oscillator. The obtained size classes will then be subjected to methodologies for glomalin extraction and physical fractionation of SOM. Finally, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) technique will be applied to the SOM fractions and intra-aggregated glomalin to evaluate the carbon functional groups.

Subproject 1.8 – “Co-inoculation of soybeans with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum*, and inoculation with *Azospirillum* in the corn-brachiaria consortium in succession increase the contribution of C and N to the soil and favor the GHG balance?” is being conducted by *Arnold Barbosa de Oliveira (PhD student, no scholarship associated)*

Main objective:

Quantify the benefits of continued inoculation and co-inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* in SPD with soybeans, corn and brachiaria in terms of: i) the contribution of C and N to the soil and its effects on the quality and agronomic performance of the system; and ii) the reduction of GHG emissions.

Main Results

- Measurement of the improvement in soil quality attributes evidenced by BioAS and the contribution of C and N to the soil over the time of trial implementation;
- Measuring direct productive responses in the soybean crop to inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and co-inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* in the summer;
- Measurement of reflexes in the productivity of the corn crop in succession to soybeans, in response to inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and co-inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* of soybeans in the summer;
- Measurement of direct productive responses in corn intercropped with brachiaria to inoculation with *Azospirillum*;
- Measurement of reflexes in the productivity of the soybean crop in succession to corn intercropped with brachiaria, to the inoculation of corn and brachiaria with *Azospirillum*.

Highlights

1. The routine establishment of cover crops with brachiaria on corn in succession to soybeans, and inoculations and co-inoculations with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* on these crops can have an impact on enzymatic activity, and the contribution of C and N to the soil, as well as GHG emissions.
2. Inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and co-inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* and *Azospirillum* in soybeans can result in increased yields of soybeans and corn intercropped with brachiaria.
3. Intercropping corn with brachiaria and inoculation with *Azospirillum* can result in increased yields of corn intercropped with brachiaria and soybeans in succession.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

- Tabulation of yield data for corn intercropped with brachiaria;
- Sampling and analysis of GHG until the soybean harvest;
- Sampling and analysis of C and N in the soil;
- Sampling and analysis of the mass and levels of C and N in the litter on the ground before sowing the soybeans;
- Sowing soybeans;
- Measuring soybean yields and tabulating data;
- Calculation of GHG emission mitigation per unit of grain produced
- Analysis of the incorporation of C and N into the soil
- Final data analysis (harvests and off-seasons).

Subproject 1.9 – “Support for field measurements on greenhouse gas (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) fluxes in pasture systems in Brazil” is being conducted by Valéria Cherubim (Technical Training FAPESP: 2024/05817-0)

The main goal

The main objective of this work plan is to support the measurement of greenhouse gas fluxes associated with degraded pastures and after their recovery or reform practices under field conditions in Brazil.

Abstract

Rehabilitation of degraded pastures are key strategies for carbon sequestration and mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Brazil (Brasil, 2012). In this context, the main objective of this work plan is to support the measurement of greenhouse gas emissions associated with degraded pastures and after their recovery or reform practices under field conditions in Brazil. The results generated here will improve the quality of the default values (IPCC Tier 1 approach), enhancing reliability and accuracy (reducing uncertainties) of this key-category of the Brazilian GHG emission inventory, as well as forming an important basis for national climate policy to achieve the mitigation targets presented at the NDC under the Paris Agreement.

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) guideline establishes the stratification of the inventoried area (for the entire country, but focusing in the Cerrado and its transition with others Biomes) in homogeneous spatial units with respect to climatic and edaphic conditions, besides land use and management. The edaphoclimatic information is available in the RADAM BRASIL project and the Socio-Economic Ecological Zoning (for each state). The dataset on land-use are available in the Agricultural Census and Municipal Agricultural Production (IBGE, 2019). This information will be transformed into individual thematic maps through a geographic information system (ESRI ArcGis 9.2®, Redlands, USA). Based on these information maps, homogeneous representative sites will be selected, taking into account aspects of physical and logistical infrastructure, where land-use and management questionnaires for local's specialists and farmers will also be applied. In these selected areas we will evaluate pairing of sites with pasture, one with low intensification or technological level and the other with some level of intensification aiming at increasing pasture yield. Samples will be collected using PVC chambers installed in the experimental plots, according to the chamber technique described by Davidson & Schimel (1995) and Allen et al. (2010). The chambers for gas sampling will follow the design described by Varner et al. (2002). We estimate that 12 chambers will be installed in each treatment (experimental plots when in research areas and paddocks in the case of commercial areas), diagonally towards the main slope of the experimental area. Each chamber will be a repetition for statistical purposes. Gas samples will be taken using 60 mL BD plastic syringe (Becton, Dickinson and Co., Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) and transferred to evacuated 12 mL LABCO vials. The first sample will be collected soon after the chamber is closed and the remaining samples after 10, 20, and 40 minutes. The emissions quantification plan should include the dry and wet seasons typical of the regions, with the sampling being more frequent close to a management practice to be implemented, such as nitrogen fertilization (as illustrated in Figure 5), spacing the collections in later periods. In the case of nitrogen fertilization, the monitoring duration will be approximately 90 days; sufficient time to assess the effect of fertilization. Shorter experiments will be carried out with the addition of urine and dung to the chambers, with measurements of GHG flows for periods of 30- 40 days. Tentatively, two samples will be taken per week.

Climatic data will also be monitored and quantifications of NO_3^- and NH_4^+ contents, as well as volatilized N in the form of ammonia will also be performed. Ammonia volatilization will be carried out following the methodology of Martins et al. (2017). Means cumulative GHG fluxes will be calculated into CO_2 - equivalent according to their respective global warming potentials (100 yrs.) (IPCC, 2019).

Activity	Year 1	Year 2
Organization and preparation of gas sampling materials	x	
Field gas samplings	x	x
Laboratory gas analysis		x
Data tabulation and basic analysis		x
Final report writing		x

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Subproject 1.10 – “C sequestration potential in Brazilian pastures: meta-analysis” is being conducted by *José Igor Almeida Castro (PhD student - CNPq)*

Research Question:

What is the impact of different pasture management systems on soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks in Brazil and what are the main factors contributing to C sequestration in these areas? How does converting poorly managed pastures into improved pastures influence soil organic carbon sequestration over time and along the soil profile?

Main objective:

The main objectives of this research are to evaluate the impact of different pasture management systems on SOC stocks in Brazil by conducting a comprehensive systematic review and meta-analysis of existing studies, to analyze the effectiveness of recovering poorly managed pastures in increasing SOC sequestration over time and identify key factors influencing SOC variability in well-managed and integrated production systems. Additionally, the study aims to assess the role of improved pasture systems in mitigating

greenhouse gas emissions in Brazilian pastoral landscapes with C management factor estimates.

Main Results

1. Overview

A systematic review was conducted to synthesize the evidence about the influence of improving extensive pastures into well-managed systems on SOC stock changes. This review adopted principles reported by (CEE, 2018) and Fohrafellner (2023), providing guidelines and major features of outstanding systematic reviews like the research question, search strategy, study selection, critical appraisal, statistical assessment, and review report.

The literature search was conducted in four bibliographic repositories: Web of Science (core collection: SCI-E, SSCI, and ESCI), Scopus, CAB Direct, and SciELO. The search query was developed and applied in all repositories preserving the same string to retrieve as many studies as possible. The search terms included combinations of keywords related to soil organic carbon, pasture management, and integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems. We restricted our search to peer-reviewed scientific papers (i.e. gray literature was not included.) with experimental sites in Brazilian territory and published until December 2022.

Articles were screened based on several criteria, including reporting SOC stocks study site location, sampling depth, and time since the management change. We included studies that conducted paired comparisons or chronosequence experiments between a pasture management intensification area and an extensive or degraded area, which were used as a reference.

To conduct the meta-analysis statistics, the continuous outcomes extracted were SOC stocks, or enough available data to calculate it, mean standard deviation, or any equivalent mean variability measurement to calculate SD and the number of replicates. Other extracted information comprises study location, climate, biome, soil type, depth, pasture management system, and management conversion time.

Our analysis includes a set of studies distributed across the country that compare SOC stocks across various pasture management practices, these systems were categorized into crop-livestock-forestry systems (CLFS), crop-livestock systems (CLS), livestock-forestry systems (LFS) and improved pasture management. The geographic distribution of the studies are concentrated in the Cerrado biome, with others located in the Amazon, Atlantic Forest, and Pampa biomes (Figure 1). In total, 310 data pairs were included in the regression analysis, distributed in 35 published articles, belonging to 43 experimentation sites.

Figure 1. Observation distribution in Brazil

The climatic data indicates that the average temperatures in the study regions range from 14.1°C to 32°C, with most studies conducted in areas with temperatures between 20°C and 25°C. Annual precipitation varies significantly, from 927 mm to 2628 mm, with an average of around 1500 mm.

Regarding the temporal aspect, the time since system implementation ranges from 1 to 26 years, with an average of approximately 9 years. This temporal variation allows for the assessment of both short-term and long-term impacts of pasture management on SOC stocks.

Published papers range from 2000 to 2022 (Figure 2). There is an evolution of studies assessing integrated production systems, while the first CLS study was published in 2004 (Neves et al., 2004), the first study evaluating LFS was published only in 2015 (Baldotto et al., 2015), however, these systems have been frequently studied in the last four years.

Figure 2. Evolution of published papers included in meta-analysis.

Considering the SOC stock levels for each system, the LFS system has the highest average SOC stock across all reported depths, followed by the improved pasture system (Figure 3). The LFS system also exhibits substantial variability, as indicated by the large error bars, suggesting that SOC storage in this system can vary depending on specific conditions or studies. In contrast, the CLS system has the lowest average SOC stock, with narrower error bars, indicating lower carbon sequestration potential and more consistent SOC storage outcomes. The CLFS system, while having higher SOC stocks than CLS, still falls short of the levels observed in improved pastures and LFS. These variations underscore the distinct impacts of different management practices on SOC accumulation, with LFS and improved pasture systems offering more predictable outcomes in terms of carbon storage than the others.

Figure 3. SOC stock distribution in all soil profiles

2. Effect size distribution

We used the response ratio of SOC stocks as the effect size to demonstrate the relation between the treatment and reference. This distribution indicates that pasture management systems improve SOC compared to extensive or degraded pastures (Figure 4). However, we observed variability within each system. While most observations for CLS, Improved Pasture, CLFS, and LFS are above the response ratio of 1.00, indicating a positive effect, there are also notable instances where the response ratio falls below 1.00, highlighting some limitations of these management practices.

Nevertheless, the considerable variability in response ratios within each system underscores the influence of local conditions and management practices on SOC outcomes, as highlighted by Silva et al. (2020) and Jones et al. (2022). This variability suggests that tailored, site-specific management strategies are essential for maximizing SOC sequestration benefits.

Figure 4. Data pairs effect-size distribution

Regarding management time, improved pasture systems tend to have the highest effect size, often exceeding 1.5 and reaching above 3.0, particularly within the first 10 years of management, indicating a strong positive impact on soil organic carbon stocks during shorter management periods (Figure 5). In contrast, CLFS and CLS show more moderate effects, with most observations close to 1.0, suggesting a balanced effect over time. LFS displays a neutral to slightly positive relationship with RR, with most values clustering around 1.0. The lack of a clear increasing or decreasing trend in RR over longer management times across all systems suggests that the impact of management duration on soil carbon dynamics is complex and influenced by other factors, like depth or climate conditions.

Figure 5. Relationship between response ratio and management time since the beginning of pasture improvement.

3. SOC management factors

We utilized a linear mixed-effects regression model to quantify the response ratio (RR) of SOC stock changes, considering fixed effects as the system type, years of management, and soil depth, with study-specific variations accounted for as random effects. Thus, we estimated SOC management factors for pasture systems in Brazil.

Over 10, 20, and 30 years, (Figures 6, 7, and 8) SOC management factors were predicted across depths from 10 cm to 100 cm. At 10 years, the LFS showed the highest SOC management factor across all depths, indicating a significant positive effect on SOC storage. CLFS and IM.PA also exhibited positive impacts with SOC factors consistently above 1.00. However, CLS did not reach an average level above 1.00 in the first 30 cm, although its standard deviation included values above this threshold.

By 20 years, LFS continued to have the highest SOC management factors. CLFS and IM.PA maintained positive impacts on SOC, with factors above 1.00 at all depths. CLS, which initially lagged, reached, and exceeded the 1.00 threshold across all depths by the 20-year mark. Finally, at 30 years, LFS remained the most effective, while CLFS and IM.PA sustained their positive contributions. CLS showed substantial improvements, particularly from 30 cm depth and beyond, consistently surpassing the 1.00 threshold.

Figure 5. SOC management factors for 10 years of management in cumulative depth layers from 0 to 100 cm

Figure 6. SOC management factors for 20 years of management in cumulative depth layers from 0 to 100 cm

Figure 7. SOC management factors for 30 years of management in cumulative depth layers from 0 to 100 cm

We observed that integrated production systems that include the forestry component (LFS and CLFS) have a sustained impact on SOC levels over time. The LFS showed the highest SOC management factors, due to the synergistic effects of combining livestock and forest vegetation, which increases organic matter input and enhances soil structure stability (Tadini et al., 2021). The CLFS also showed positive results, benefiting from diverse crop biomass and root systems that contribute to SOC improvement (Sharma et al., 2021).

Improved pasture provided consistent benefits to SOC across all depths, due to better management practices and improved plant varieties (Matos et al., 2022). While initially showing lower SOC management factors, CLS achieved and exceeded the threshold of 1.00 by the 20-year mark, indicating that longer-term implementation can enhance its effectiveness. This trend was particularly notable beyond 30 cm depths, where SOC management factors continued to improve (Tadini et al., 2020). These results underscore the importance of integrated land management practices for long-term soil health and carbon sequestration (Bieluczyk et al., 2020).

Highlights

- 1- Integrated production systems that include the forestry component provide the highest potential for SOC sequestration.
- 2- Pasture recovery techniques can effectively increase SOC sequestration over time up to a 23% increase in SOC stocks compared to degraded pastures.
- 3- Through a systematic review and meta-analysis, the study provides a comprehensive assessment of SOC dynamics across various pasture systems in Brazil, offering valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners aiming to optimize sustainable land management practices.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

For the next year of the project, the focus should be on finalizing the meta-analysis by incorporating additional studies, refining data aggregation, and performing more detailed statistical analyses to enhance the robustness of the findings. This will include deeper exploration of moderator variables, such as climate conditions, soil types, and pasture management practices, to understand their influence on soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks.

Parallely, developing carbon modeling simulations focused on Brazilian pasture systems will be crucial. This model should aim to predict SOC dynamics over time under different management scenarios, including integrated production systems. Furthermore, engaging in sensitivity analyses and scenario testing within the model will help identify key drivers and uncertainties, informing best management practices for maximizing carbon sequestration in Brazilian pastures.

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Appendix 1.1

Catena
A comprehensive assessment of greenhouse gas emissions research in the Cerrado region, Brazil
 --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	CATENA24325
Article Type:	VSI: Carbon inventories in agriculture and forestry
Keywords:	climate change; Conservation agriculture; tropical agriculture; soil organic matter; carbon balance
Corresponding Author:	Jorge Luiz Locatelli University of São Paulo Piracicaba, BRAZIL
First Author:	Jorge Luiz Locatelli
Order of Authors:	Jorge Luiz Locatelli Gustavo Vicentini Popin Rafael Silva Santos Wanderlei Bieluczyk Leticia Thomas Cipriani Maurício Roberto Cherubin Carlos Eduardo Cerri
Abstract:	The increasing global demand for food, fiber, and (bio)energy boosted by population growth has accentuated agricultural expansion, contributing to increasing global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This scenario is particularly valid in Brazil, where the agricultural sector accounts for the largest part of the nation's GHG emissions, primarily associated with the expansion of agriculture over areas of native vegetation.

193 **Cropping diversification strategies promote soil aggregation, carbon sequestration and**
 194 **composition changes in the Brazilian Cerrado**

195 Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerni^{1,6}, Catherine Stewart⁵, Felipe Bertol⁴, Gustavo Vicentini Popin¹,
 196 João Luis Nunes Carvalho², Jorge Luiz Locatelli^{1,5*}, Matheus Bortolanza Soares¹, Mauricio
 197 Roberto Cherubin^{1,6}, Rafael Silva Santos³, Sarah Tenelli^{2,3}, Stephen Del Grosso⁵ (*Alphabetical*
 198 *order*)

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 201 Laboratory, Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials - LNBR/CNPEM, Campinas,
 202 São Paulo, Brazil; ³Department of Soil and Crop Sciences, Colorado State University, University
 203 Ave, 307, Fort Collins, CO, 80521, USA; ⁴The Center for Agricultural Resources Research,
 204 USDA-ARS, Soil Management and Sugarbeet Research, Fort Collins, CO 80526, USA; ⁵Center
 205 for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON) - University of São Paulo, Avenida
 206 Pádua Dias 11, Piracicaba, SP, 13418-900, Brazil

207

Appendix 1.2

Agricultural Water Management

Implications of water management on methane emissions and grain yield in paddy rice:
 A case study under subtropical conditions in Brazil using crop modeling
 --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	AGWAT-D-24-00442
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	DSSAT; GHG; CH ₄ ; crop modeling
Corresponding Author:	Evandro Moura da Silva University of São Paulo Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture Piracicaba, SP Brazil
First Author:	Evandro H Figueiredo Moura da Silva
Order of Authors:	Evandro H Figueiredo Moura da Silva Gerrit Hoopenboom Kenneth J Boote Santiago Viana Cuadra Cheryl H Porter Walkyria Bueno Scvittaro Silvio Steinmetz Carlos E. Pellegrino Cerni

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Evandro Figueiredo Moura da Silva, University of Sao Paulo, Piracicaba, São Paulo, US, Jorge L. Locatelli, University of São Paulo, Piracicaba, SP, Brazil, Gerrit Hoogenboom, P.O. Box 110570, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, US, Kenneth J. Boote, Agric. and Biol. Engr. Dept., 120 Rogers Hall, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, US, Cheryl H. Porter, 103 Frazier Rogers Hall, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL and Carlos E Pellegrino Cerri, Department of Soil Science, Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture - University of São Paulo, Piracicaba, Brazil

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5th Global Food Security Conference

Towards equitable, sustainable and resilient food systems

9th-12th April 2024 | KU Leuven, Belgium

Appendix 2 Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho

Additional question: Can biochar be a feasible strategy to increase soil C sequestration and mitigate N₂O emissions in tropical soils?

Subproject 1 – “Evaluating the potential of biochar from crop residues as a strategy to mitigate N₂O emissions and boost carbon sequestration in tropical soils” is being conducted by *Fernanda Palmeira Gabetto (Doctorate – CAPES)*

Project Progress Summary:

The project aims to characterize the physicochemical properties of biochar from different feedstocks and evaluate its effects on soil N₂O emissions, C storage, and soil microbial community diversity. In this first year, significant progress has been made in the following areas.

1. Introduction and Context:

- Biochar use in agriculture has been considered an effective solution for decreasing soil nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions while promoting carbon (C) dioxide removal from the atmosphere. Biochar can be produced primarily from different agricultural and wood residual biomasses, potentially resulting in biochar types with distinct capacities to mitigate soil GHG emissions.
- Therefore, this study was designed with the hypothesis that the effects of biochar on soil N₂O and C storage are related to changes in chemical properties caused by different feedstock materials.

○

2. Methodology:

- Four types of biochar produced from sugarcane (straw and bagasse) and wood residues (pinus and eucaliptus) were evaluated over 60 days in a greenhouse experiment.
- Six treatments were arranged in a completely randomized design with four replications. The treatments included i) soil without addition of N fertilizer and biochar as the control (CTR); ii) soil with N fertilizer addition (NF); iii) NF with sugarcane straw biochar (NF+SB); iv) NF with sugarcane bagasse biochar (NF+BB); v) NF with pinus biochar (NF+PB); vi) and NF with eucalyptus biochar (NF+EB).
- The physicochemical characterization of biochar was performed with a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to assess microstructural and morphological characteristics, and with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) to explore the elemental distribution in each material. The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) technique was utilized for chemical quantification and characterization of the elements and functional carbon (C) groups present at the surface of the materials
- The N₂O emissions were accounted for using gas chromatography (Shimadzu 2014)
- Soil samples were collected over the experimental period to determine the dynamics of inorganic N (NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻) and C concentration.

3. Results and Analysis:

- Regardless of the feedstock used, all evaluated biochar reduced the cumulative N₂O emissions by 25-50% in comparison to the application of N fertilizers. A high mitigation effect was observed for sugarcane straw biochar.
- Biochar derived from different residues showed distinct amounts of chemical bonds identified on the surface of the particles. All biochar presented the aromatic C form (C-C/C=C) as the dominant functional C group. Biochar from wood residues had low share of oxidized C species compared to sugarcane-based biochar.
- All biochar types increased soil C levels compared to N fertilizer treatment. Biochar application had no significant effect on sugarcane biomass production and N-NH₄⁺ availability; however, it exhibited the capacity to retain N-NO₃⁻.

4. Conclusions:

This study highlights that biochar application in tropical soils can be considered a nature-based solution to decrease N₂O emissions and increase soil C levels. The findings observed that sugarcane biochars were more effective in mitigating N₂O emissions and wood biochars resulted in high soil C content. Finally, this study pointed out that long-term studies under field conditions and modeling efforts are recommended to elucidate better the impacts of applying different biochar on GHG emissions and soil health in the long-term perspective.

Subproject 2 – “Using process-based models to assess the long-term effects of biochar application on soil carbon sequestration in Brazil” is being conducted by *Dr Amanda Ronix (Pós-Doc – CNPq)*

The project aims to assess the potential of process-based models as a strategy to evaluate the long-term effects of biochar application on soil carbon sequestration. This project is divided into two complementary parts: 1) Literature review on the use of process-based models to assess the effects of biochar on carbon stocks and greenhouse gas emissions; 2) Application and validation of the RothC model to assess the impact of biochar on soil carbon stocks in Brazilian conditions. The first part of this project was finalized, and the main results will be presented.

1. Introduction and Context:

- In the last two decades, several studies have been conducted using process-based biogeochemical models to evaluate the impact of various practices on soil carbon storage and study the dynamics of soil organic carbon. Certification bodies have already considered the use of these models as part of the carbon credit trading process (“measure and model approach”). At the same time, the use of biochar, a carbon-rich material obtained from the controlled combustion of biomass residues, has been identified as a promising carbon sequestration strategy. However, most of the models do not adequately incorporate the role of biochar in soil management.

2. **Methodology:**

- A bibliometric analysis was performed using the Web of Science® (WoS) (Clarivate Analytics) platform. The search considered terms mentioned in the “title, abstract, and keywords” (Topic field) of each record and was limited to research articles published between 2000 and 2024. The project utilizes the Ceres-Maize/DSSAT model to simulate maize growth, development, and yield under different climate scenarios.

3. **Results:**

- The research indicated that the development of studies on the topic “biochar” is widely explored, with 4259 papers being identified, using the first search filter. Specifically, searching for studies that mentioned terms related to biogeochemical models for estimating soil carbon stock, it was observed that a small number of the studies (N = 46) considered the entry of biochar into the models. Among these studies, a minority presented the results of calibration and validation of the models, which are paramount for the credibility of the model. Therefore, efforts must be concentrated on solving the lack of useful data to validate the models.

Conclusion:

Biochar has been proposed as a promising technology for C sequestration and climate change mitigation. However, assessing the long-term soil C sequestration potential of biochar is challenging and modeling should be a useful tool. However, assessing the long-term soil C sequestration potential of biochar is challenging and modeling should be a useful tool. However, most of the model studies have not been validated with field measurements and few long-term experiments are available, especially under Brazilian conditions. To overcome these challenges and improve our understanding of the long-term C sequestration potential of biochar, modeling studies, and long-term field experiments should be a priority to evaluate biochar performance under real-world conditions.

APPENDIX 2.1

Journal of Cleaner Production

Biochar from crop residues mitigates N₂O emissions and boosts carbon sequestration in tropical soils –Manuscript Draft–

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Original article
Keywords:	Scanning electron microscopy; functional groups; XPS; yield-scaled N ₂ O emissions; MEV.
Corresponding Author:	João Carvalho, Ph.D Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials BRAZIL
First Author:	João Carvalho, Ph.D
Order of Authors:	João Carvalho, Ph.D Fernando Gabetto Sarah Terroli Julia Netto-Ferreira Octavio Almeida Joachim Martins Junior Marcelo Lamos Matthias Strauss
Abstract:	Biochar use in agriculture offers a cost-effective solution for decreasing soil nitrous oxide (N ₂ O) emissions while promoting carbon (C) dioxide removal from the atmosphere. Biochar can be produced primarily from different agricultural and wood residual biomasses, potentially resulting in biochar types with distinct properties. Therefore, this study evaluated the effects of different biochar types on soil N ₂ O

Biochar

Biochar input in biogeochemical models to simulate soil carbon stocks and changes: A review –Manuscript Draft–

Manuscript Number:							
Full Title:	Biochar input in biogeochemical models to simulate soil carbon stocks and changes: A review						
Article Type:	Review						
Funding Information:	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (2021/10573-4)</td> <td>Dr Carlos Eduardo Cerri</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (1.72418/2023-2)</td> <td>Dr Amanda Ronix</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (314597/2021-2)</td> <td>Dr João L. N. Carvalho</td> </tr> </table>	Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (2021/10573-4)	Dr Carlos Eduardo Cerri	Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (1.72418/2023-2)	Dr Amanda Ronix	Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (314597/2021-2)	Dr João L. N. Carvalho
Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (2021/10573-4)	Dr Carlos Eduardo Cerri						
Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (1.72418/2023-2)	Dr Amanda Ronix						
Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (314597/2021-2)	Dr João L. N. Carvalho						
Abstract:	In the last two decades, several studies have been conducted using process-based biogeochemical models to evaluate the impact of various factors on soil carbon storage and study the dynamics of soil organic carbon (SOC). At the same time, the use of biochar, a carbon-rich material obtained from the controlled combustion of biomass residues, has been identified as a promising carbon sequestration strategy. However, current models do not adequately incorporate the role of biochar in soil management. In this context, the current state of research on biogeochemical models that incorporate the entry of biochar into soil has been characterized. The research indicated that the development of studies on the topic "biochar" is widely explored, with 4259 papers						

Appendix 3 Principal Investigator: Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni

Subproject 1 – Impact of ambient temperature variations on chemical and biological attributes of a soil contaminated by zinc and cadmium and remediated with biochar
Ms. Student Mariana Pezzatte Pollo, FAPESP (2023/04271-0).

Subproject 2 – Chemical and Biological Attributes of Soil and Plant Nutrition in Conventional Pastures and Integrated Crop-Livestock-Forest Systems
Ph.D. Student Tamires Maiara Ercole, FAPESP (2023/14904-0).

Subproject 3 – Enzymatic activity and CO₂ emission by soil microbiota as a function of ambient temperature variation in an Oxisol under degraded pasture and under crop-livestock-forest integration
Undergraduate Student Bruno Stella, FAPESP (2024/03712-6).

Highlights

1 – Subproject 1: we investigated how temperature and the type of biochar affect the ability to retain toxic substances in mining waste. By varying the temperature and using biochars produced at 350°C and 750°C, we found that temperature played a key role in the mobility of toxic substances. Increases in temperature lead to an increase in the amount of soluble toxic substances and decreased the tailing's ability to retain zinc. Biochar produced at 350°C was less efficient at retaining toxic substances, but it was more resistant to temperature changes. On the other hand, biochar produced at 750°C had a more organized structure and retained more toxic substances, although more sensitive to temperature increases. The addition of biochar reduced the amount of dissolved organic carbon in the tailing, but increased the total amount of organic carbon. In addition, the addition of biochar increased the sensitivity of the tailing to temperature changes, regardless of the pyrolysis temperature for producing the biochar. Biochar produced at 350°C reduced carbon dioxide emissions, while biochar produced at 750°C increased these emissions. These results are important for understanding how biochar can be used to treat mining waste and reduce the associated environmental risks. The information obtained can help to develop more effective strategies to clean up areas contaminated by mining.

2 – Subproject 2: the areas studied have already reached stability and can provide consistent data on the changes caused by land use, considering pasture management types, the presence of trees, and the changes in the soils' chemical and biological attributes associated with management practices. Furthermore, it is expected that the results will contribute to a better understanding of nutrient availability and cycling in integrated livestock-forest, crop-livestock and crop-livestock-forest (ICLF) systems both eucalyptus and native plants. Similarly, advances in understanding the soil microbial community and its ecosystem functions are anticipated. Finally, the influence of eucalyptus in ICLF systems on soil chemical and biological attributes will also be assessed (undergoing analyses).

3 – Subproject 3: we are evaluating soils collected from long-term experiments; so, it is believed that there is a great chance of obtaining consistent results for changes due to increased ambient temperature (from 20°C to 30°C). It is expected that soils under native forests and crop-livestock-forest integration systems will contain higher amounts of soil

carbon, making them more susceptible to CO₂ losses to the atmosphere as temperature increases. In contrast, it is expected that degraded pasture will have a less pronounced response to climate change due to its lower soil carbon content (undergoing analyses).

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

1 – Subproject 1: the FAPESP project (2023/04271-0) was concluded on June/2024, and the thesis was defended and approved by the Graduate Program in Soils and Plant Nutrition at ESALQ/USP. In the coming year, we are planning to publish two articles derived from the master's thesis.

2 – Subproject: the student submitted a proposal to FAPESP to undertake a sandwich internship at the University of Florida, Marianna – USA. During the internship, it is intended to take samples from integrated farming systems collected in Brazil for more in-depth analyses related to soil carbon and microbiological activities.

3 - Subproject 3: soil chemical characterization, dissolved organic carbon analysis, organic matter fractionation, FTIR spectroscopy, and enzymatic activity assessments will be conducted over the next year. At the conclusion of these evaluations, the impact of ambient temperature changes on enzymatic activity and CO₂ emissions by the microbiota of a medium-textured Oxisol will be assessed, focusing on soil samples collected in degraded pasture, crop-livestock-forest integration, and native forest systems.

Publications and Activities

- Scientific communication:

Mariana Pezzatte Pollo's master's project and Tamires Maiara Ercole's doctoral project were highlighted in the weekly newsletter of SolloAgro, the Program for Continuing Education in Sustainable Agriculture at ESALQ/USP. This publication not only promotes projects related to CCarbon but also highlights the works that have been done to advance sustainability in agriculture, in connection with climate change.

- Master thesis finished:

Pollo, MP. 2024. Master thesis in Soils and Plant Nutrition. **Variations of ambient temperature impacting chemical and biological attributes of a sediment contaminated with zinc and cadmium and remediated with biochar.**

- Poster presented in national scientific event:

Pollo, M. P.; Soares, M. B; Alleoni, L. R. F. **Variation in ambient temperature and immobilization of Zn and Cd in a Technosol amended with sugarcane straw biochar** – 1st CCarbon Symposium. December 8th, 2023, Piracicaba - SP.

Ercole, T. M.; Pollo, M. P.; Stella, B.; Alleoni, L. R. F. **Soil enzymatic activity under conventional pasture and under crop-livestock-forest integration system** - CCarbon Soil Health Symposium: from the field to the socioeconomical & political perspectives, April 24th, 2024, Piracicaba - SP.

Appendix 4 Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote

Main objective:

How changes in the soil microbiome composition and activity can interfere in the capacity of soil to store carbon? Several links can be proposed in this issue, which must be properly investigated to improve soil management, through the best-possible usage and promotion of microbial activities in soils used for agriculture.

Subproject 1 – Understand the differential activity of the soil microbial community with the processes of decomposition of organic matter and consequent stabilization of C in different management systems

Ph.D. Student Nariane de Andrade, FAPESP (2022/09977-6), currently developing a BEPE Project at Rothamsted Institute (FAPESP 2024/01300-2)

Subproject 2 – Understand the effects of management variations on productivity gains (and consequent carbon accumulation) attributed to the use of inoculants

Ph.D. Student Nariane de Andrade, FAPESP (2022/09977-6)

Ph.D. Student Rafael Santana Mendonça, CAPES

Subproject 3 – Determine the participation of microbial necromass in carbon stabilization in soils under different management

Ms Student Alberto Vinicius Sousa Rocha Mestrado FAPESP (2022/10276-2)

Ph.D. Student Rafael Santana Mendonça, CAPES

Subproject 4 - Explore the interaction between nematodes and bacteria in production systems, and their interconnections with carbon emissions from soils

Post-doc. Dr. Felipe Martins do Rêgo Barros, FAPESP (2023/04352-0), with approved BEPE project to be conducted at Indiana University, in the period of Nov/24 to Oct/25 (FAPESP 2024/07113-0)

Highlights

1- Results from subprojects 1 and 2 indicate the role of soil management (integrated systems compared to pastures and natural areas), coupled with the use of inoculants (*Azospirillum brasilense* and arbuscular mycorrhiza), in the promotion of differential composition of the soil microbiome in different Brazilian regions (Cerrado and South), what might be connected to the differential carbon cycling in these systems (undergoing analyses).

2- Subproject 3 revealed the most ground-broken result for this project target, with the first measurements of the microbial necromass contributions to the soil organic carbon (SOC) in Brazilian soils. We analyzed an experiment to determine in Pará, where it was observed that necromass contribution to SOC, with values ranging from 10 to 28%. It was also determined that Fungal necromass is more responsive to land use change than bacterial necromass.

3- The subproject 4 started with a sampling of a long-term experiment in Sinop, MT. Nematode extractions were performed, and portions of extracts were sent taxonomic

identification of plant-parasitic nematodes. Out of the 57 samples collected, the 18S rRNA was successfully amplified from 50 samples. The PCR products of the 50 positive samples are ready to be sent for sequencing.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

- Subproject 1 will focus on the data analyses, focusing on the correlation of microbial communities with carbon fractions in soils under different managements. We will target the precise identification of microbial players or patterns related to the generation of stable forms of carbons, supporting the proposal of soil management based on these findings.
- Subproject 2 is very much aligned with the previous, where microbial data is being generated and might be used for similar purposes described above.
- Plans for the Subproject 3 encompass a roader soil samples analyses, to obtain numbers of bacterial and fungal necromass contributions for SOC in different biomes and in soils under different managements. It might support a more robust and well-established quantification of this SOC fraction, leading to the development of soils managements considering this active component of the soils.
- Subproject 4 will focus on description of nematodes communities from samples under analyses. In addition, the BEPE fellowship will be used to conduct an experiment under controlled conditions, manipulating the nematode community in soil samples with preserved physical structure, aiming to indicate the role of manipulated nematode communities on soil characteristics, mainly connected to C cycling.

Publications

- *Master thesis finished:*

Rocha, AVS. 2024. Master thesis in Soils and Plant Nutrition. **Microbial necromass, carbon and agriculture: combining living and dead microbes to reveal carbon dynamics under agroforestry in the Amazon.**

- *Scientific paper to be submitted:*

Rocha, AVS, Buckeridge KM, Alves, AF, Barros, FNR, Melo, ATM, Pimpinato, RF, Tornisielo, VL, Cerri, CEP, Cherubin, MR, Andreote, FD. **Microbial necromass, carbon and agriculture: combining living and dead microbes to reveal carbon dynamics under agroforestry in the Amazon.** Soil Biology and Biochemistry, *in final preparation*.

- *Abstract in international scientific event:*

Rocha, AVS, Alves, AF, Melo, ATM, Buckeridge, KM, Cherubin, MR, Andreote, FD. **Necromass, carbon and agriculture: how microbial death is related to persistent carbon in Amazon agroforestry?** 19th ISME Meeting, Cape Town, South Africa, August 2024.

Appendix 5 Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Research Question:

Are there synergies between soil carbon sequestration and soil health and other ecosystem services?

Main objective:

We hypothesize that intensified and diversified agricultural systems that enhance C sequestration (the main focus of CCARBON), improve soil health and have a synergic effect on the provision of other key ecosystem services and of human wellbeing. Although a variety of conceptual frameworks and models have been proposed around the world, a universal approach for evaluating soil health and soil-related ecosystem services under different environmental conditions is still inexistent. In this context, in the CEPID timeframe we will design and develop a multilevel framework for assessing soil health and selected ecosystem services in agricultural systems under contrasting conditions across the country.

Research lines

3.1 Effect of land use change and sugarcane management on soil C changes, GHG emissions, soil health and associated ecosystem services

Subproject 3.1.1 – Effect of land use change and sugarcane management practices on soil C, soil health and associated ecosystem services: an evidence synthesis.

Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior (Postdoctoral – FAPESP # 2023/11337- 8)

Increasing biofuel production to accelerate the energy transition has been widely recognized as the main pathway to achieving net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Given this scenario, Brazil stands out as the world's largest producer of sugarcane and the second-largest producer of bioethanol. Many studies have evaluated the impact of land use changes and sugarcane management practices in Brazil, however, most of them are local studies and are scattered in the literature, making a more robust evaluation difficult. Thus, evidence synthesis studies are fundamental to ensure the elaboration of well-founded policymaking, as they access, evaluate, and synthesize scientific information. This project aims to evaluate the effect of land use changes and sugarcane management practices on soil carbon, soil health and associated ecosystem services, from an evidence synthesis study. So far, the project has compiled data from the studies found in the literature. The results of the project's first work package were published in the journal *Global Change Biology - Bioenergy* (Pinheiro Junior et al., 2024), where we provided the soil organic carbon stock change factors (SOCscf) for the different land use change scenarios (native vegetation, annual crop, and pasture), and the main management practices (straw removal, vinasse application, and reduced tillage). In another of the project's work packages, the impact of sugarcane straw management (low, moderate, and high removal levels) for bioenergy production on eight soil-related ecosystem services (C storage; water regulation and erosion control; pest control; weed control; GHG emission mitigation; nutrient cycling; maintenance of soil biodiversity; and provision of food and bioenergy) has been evaluated using a quali-quantitative approach (advanced draft). From our database we were able to generate a cause-and-effect matrix that provides the

direction of the effects (negative, neutral, or positive) and the associated confidence level. Overall, the lowest impact on SES occurs under low straw removal with a neutral effect on C storage, nutrient cycling, weed control, GHG mitigation, and provision of food and bioenergy. Water regulation and erosion control and maintenance of soil biodiversity were the most negatively affected SES to straw removal management. Moderate and high levels of straw removal have a negative impact on the maintenance of SES and compromise the sustainability of sugarcane cultivation areas, except for pest control, and soil GHG emission mitigation. Ultimately, we hope that these findings will be useful in guiding decision-making by farmers, investors, stakeholders, and policymakers, promoting progress toward sustainable bioenergy production that contributes to a low-carbon economy and climate change mitigation.

Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Canisares, L. P., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). **Soil carbon stocks in sugarcane cultivation: An evidence synthesis associated with land use and management practices**. *GCB Bioenergy*, 16, e13188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.13188>.

Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Canisares, L. P., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. **Bioenergy production from sugarcane straw: Implications for soil-related ecosystem services** (Advanced draft).

Subproject 3.1.2 – Regional N₂O emissions factors in bioethanol crops in Brazil
Graciele Angnes (Postdoctoral - FUSP)

The challenge of assessing greenhouse gas (GHG) impacts to mitigate emissions in Brazil is particularly significant for the agricultural sector. In Brazil, most life cycle assessment (LCA) studies typically rely on default (Tier 1) factors from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to estimate GHG emissions. However, recent research suggests that these default factors do not accurately reflect Brazil's climatic diversity, potentially leading to overestimations of emissions from key agricultural crops. We conducted a systematic review, analyzing data from 322 measurements across 56 field studies on sugarcane and corn crops in various regions of Brazil, to identify the average N₂O emission factors (EF) and provide a comprehensive overview of EF studies in the country. Our findings indicate that N₂O EFs for corn and sugarcane were consistently below 1%, which challenges the adequacy of the standard EF value of 1.6% proposed by the IPCC (2019) for estimating N₂O emissions. Additionally, our results revealed that supplementing mineral nitrogen fertilizer with organic sources led to an increase in average N₂O emission factors compared to using mineral fertilizer alone. Conversely, a significant reduction in EF was observed when nitrification inhibitors were applied to mineral nitrogen. The global EF values (sugarcane and corn) observed in our study were lower than those reported in other countries, such as India, Costa Rica, Australia, China, and Thailand.

Angnes, G., Carvalho J.L.N., Cherubin, M.R. **Regional N₂O emissions factors in bioethanol crops in Brazil: A review**. Advanced draft.

3.2 Biodiversification of cropping production systems (cover crops and integrated systems)

Subproject 3.2.1 – Soil health and soil-related ecosystem services provision in Brazilian subtropical cropping systems

Martha Lustosa Carvalho, PhD Candidate (FAPESP Project - #2022/13531-3)

Conventional agricultural systems simplify natural ecosystems to prioritize the production of a single ecosystem service (food, feed, fiber, or fuel production), often at the expense of other services. Over the past few decades, conservation agriculture practices have been developed as a set of management strategies aimed at preventing, mitigating, and reversing the depletion of SOC stocks and other ecosystem services in agroecosystems. These practices are rooted in both innovative and traditional nature-based solutions (NBS) that have been adopted to varying extents in modern agroecosystems, including organic fertilization, biological control, integrated systems, no-till farming, and plant diversification. Our goals in this project are to assess the impact of crop intensification and diversification on soil health and soil-related ecosystem service provision in subtropical Brazil. Two experiments were selected for evaluation - both first planted in 2018 - in Itaberá (São Paulo state) and Carambeí (Paraná state). We monitored greenhouse gas emissions for two years, measured water dynamics, and collected soil samples for the soil health framework evaluation. We used Cornell University's CASH framework as a guideline for sampling and evaluation of soil samples. So far, preliminary results indicate that systems with cover crops during wintertime presented higher cumulative GHG emissions overall, however, we aim to compare treatments by a ratio of total emissions per yield and total energy produced. Preliminary analysis of soil health data did not indicate a significant difference between treatments for Carambeí, with slight differences detected only for the autoclaved-citrate extractable (ACE) soil protein index. Soil physical and chemical indicators did not detect statistically significant differences between treatments.

Carvalho, M.L., Scholten, R.S., Canisares, L.P., Cherubin, M.R. **Cover crops biomass and nutrients inputs in Brazilian agriculture.** (Advanced draft)

Subproject 3.2.2 – *Balanço de carbono e saúde do solo em resposta às plantas de cobertura no Cerrado brasileiro*

Victória Santos Souza (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2022/16368-6)

Mitigating climate changes and combating food insecurity are the main challenges for humankind in the next decades. In Brazil, land use change and agricultural activities are the main source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and therefore, the adoption of best management practices that increase soil carbon (C) stocks (CO₂ removal) and reduce GHG emissions is the foundation for designing more sustainable cropping systems in Brazil. Our overall objective is to evaluate the medium- and long-term impact of crop diversification using cover crops after soybean cultivation on soil C balance, soil health and crop yields in two key regions of the Brazilian Savannah (Cerrado region). Two experimental plots were evaluated, namely a 5-year-old experiment located in Rio Verde - Goiás, and a 9-year-old experiment located in Rondonópolis - Mato Grosso. The experiment includes cover crop treatments after soybean (main crop) cultivation. So far, we quantified eight indicators of soil health, where soil organic carbon (SOC) content and potential activity of beta-glucosidase composed the biological soil health index (SHI), the

aggregate stability, bulk density and water filled pore space composed the physical SHI, and pH, P and K composed the chemical SHI. The treatment with cover crop mix planted after soybean harvest resulted in SHI higher than treatments with maize and maize intercropped with ruzigrass when considering 0-10 and 0-30 cm layers for soil health assessment. In the 0-30 cm layers the treatment effect resulted in higher biological SHI index for the treatment with cover crop mix compared to the treatment with maize planted following soybean. We also related the different indexes with soybean grain yield and found that the biological and chemical indexes positively correlated with the soybean grain yield, being the SOC scores the major driver of the correlation (explaining 20% of the grain yield variation). When considering whether increasing soil health could increase the yield stability, we observed that increasing the biological SHI index decreased the coefficient of variation (CV) of the yield over the years, and the potential activity of beta-glucosidase explained alone 35% of the variation of the CV. These findings emphasize the role of diversified agroecosystems in improving soil health through soil biological processes with consequences for yield and yield stability in the Brazilian Savannah.

Souza, V. S., Canisares, L. P., Schiebelbein, B. E., Santos, D. de C., Menillo, R. B., Cherubin, M. R. **Biodiversification enhances soil health, crop yield and resilience.** Advanced draft.

Souza, V. S., Vanolli, B. S., Schiebelbein, B. E., Bortolo, L. S., Carvalho, M. L., Mendes, I. C., Cherubin, M. R., 2024. **Cover crops and soil health in Brazilian agricultural systems.** In *Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil* (3rd ed., Vol. 3, pp. 1-432). John Wiley & Sons.

Subproject 3.2.3 – The role of soil macrofauna in regulating carbon dynamics in integrated agricultural systems

Beatriz da Silva Vanolli, PhD Candidate, FAPESP Project - 2022/14212-9

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the role of soil macrofauna in regulating carbon dynamics in integrated agricultural systems (IAS) across various regions of Brazil. This study aims to uncover the mechanisms by which soil macrofauna—such as earthworms, ants, and termites—contribute to the stabilization of soil organic carbon (SOC). Specifically, we seek to quantify the abundance and diversity of these organisms in different integrated systems, understand their role in the formation of biogenic soil aggregates, and assess the impact of these processes on overall soil health. In our study of sandy soils in the municipality of Caiuá-SP, we established a significant relationship between soil health and carbon storage. Using the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF), we found that the Soil Health Index (SHI) was strongly correlated with carbon stocks ($r=0.621$, $p<0.001$). This correlation underscores the crucial role that healthy soils play in enhancing carbon sequestration, with practices such as crop rotation and vegetative cover being essential for improving soil structure, fertility, and biodiversity. Our broader investigation, encompassing 370 sampling points in Manduri-SP, Brotas-SP, Valparaíso-SP, Ipaussu-SP, Caiuá-SP, Jataí-GO, and Ipameri-GO, highlighted the crucial role of soil macrofauna in maintaining soil health. The study covered a range of soil textures, from clayey to sandy. We observed that macrofauna, such as earthworms, ants, and termites, are vital for sustaining soil processes. In clayey soils, positive correlations were found between soil health indicators and the presence of earthworms ($r=0.137$, $p=0.094$) and millipedes ($r=0.208$, $p=0.011$). Conversely, sandy

soils showed significant positive correlations for ants ($r=0.285$, $p=0.092$) and ecosystem engineers ($r=0.366$, $p=0.021$), with an overall increase in macrofauna abundance correlating with greater soil health.

In the sandy soils of Rancharia and Caiuá, Crop-Livestock Integration (CLI) systems exhibited lower macrofauna diversity compared to pasture and native forest areas. For instance, in Rancharia, the Shannon index for the CLI system was 0.148 at a depth of 0-10 cm, while pasture reached 0.375. This suggests that in sandy soils, where water retention and nutrient availability are limited, macrofauna survival and proliferation are likely hindered, with these organisms thriving better in more complex and diverse agricultural systems. On the other hand, in the clayey soils of Ipameri and Naviraí, CLI systems showed more promising performance. In Naviraí, for example, the CLI system achieved a Shannon index of 0.194 and an abundance of 65.78 individuals per square meter at a depth of 0-10 cm, surpassing pasture, which had a Shannon index of 0.101 and an abundance of 28.44 individuals per square meter. The higher water and nutrient retention capacity of clayey soils provides a more stable and favorable environment for biodiversity, allowing CLI systems to effectively promote soil macrofauna diversity. This indicates that the efficacy of CLI systems in improving biodiversity may be more pronounced in clayey soils, where conditions are more suitable for sustaining the complexity of integrated agricultural practices.

These findings highlight the importance of considering soil texture, along with other abiotic factors such as seasonal variations, soil temperature, and moisture, which can significantly influence the presence and diversity of macrofauna. The remaining field and laboratory analyses have been completed, and we are currently in the data processing and statistical analysis phase. From these data, we intend to deepen our understanding of the role of macrofauna in soil aggregation, aggregate formation, and carbon storage. These final results, to be completed next semester, will provide additional insights into the complex role of macrofauna in soil carbon sequestration within integrated systems. This will enable a multifactorial approach that considers both edaphic conditions and climatic and seasonal variables, resulting in a more comprehensive and robust understanding of the contribution of macrofauna to the sustainability and improvement of soil health in integrated agricultural systems.

Subproject Subproject 3.2.4 – Assessment of Soil Carbon Stocks in Integrated Agricultural Systems in Brazil: A Geoinformatics Approach
Chukwudi Nwaogu - Pós-doc FAPESP - 2021/11757-1

The soil organic carbon (SOC) has the highest terrestrial carbon stock with approximately 1550 Pg of C, equivalent to more than two times the quantity of C stock in vegetation or in the atmosphere. The soils store approximately 47 Pg of C in the first 100 cm, and 44% of this C is in the topsoil layer where many anthropogenic activities dominate. This SOC is vulnerable to diverse activities and land use changes which can either increase or decrease its stock in Brazil due to diverse human activities coupled with the issues of environmental changes. Deforestation, conversions, and agriculture are the primary land use and human operations that can critically affect the balance between carbon inflows and outflows in the soil, which hinders SOC sequestration and storage. Poorly managed livestock production system through extensive pasture is the major agriculture in Brazil, which takes ca 53% of the land mass, and related risks of degradation. A sustainable system is needed to enhance SOC stocks, increase food security, minimize GHG emissions and mitigate climate change. Integrated agricultural systems (IAS) such as climate-smart agriculture (CSA) including integrated crop-livestock (iCL), and integrated

crop-livestock-forestry (iCLF)] are promising agricultural conservation practices for recovering the degraded pasture areas, increase C sequestration, and reduce conversion of native vegetation to agriculture.

This work is **aimed** at quantifying the potentials of integrated agricultural systems (IAS) on soil C sequestration. To achieve this key aim, the following **specific objectives** are applicable:

- (i) Mapping the distribution of IAS in Brazil and other regions globally.
- (ii) Elucidating the potential of IAS as a nature-based solution to environmental, economic, energy, and sustainability challenges.
- (iii) Crop-Livestock-Forest System as Nature-Based Solutions to Combating Climate Change, and Achieving SDGs in Brazil
- (iv) To quantify the dynamics in soil C storage in different land use in the greater part of Cerrado biome, Brazil.
- (v) To appraise the effects of agriculture and environmental drivers' in relation to soil C stocks using various modelling methods including Remote sensing, GIS, MLA, and geospatial-statistics.

Main results/advances achieved:

The study has achieved the following results through the published and ongoing review papers:

(a) **Integrated agricultural systems: The 21st century nature-based solution for resolving the global FEEES challenges.** published in *Advances in Agronomy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2024.02.003>

(b) **Crop-Livestock-Forest System as Nature-Based Solutions to Combating Climate Change and Achieving SDGs in Brazil.** Published in *Springer Nature*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98067-2_124-1

(c) **Integrated Agricultural Systems for Enhancing Carbon Stocks and Climate Change Mitigation: Nigeria and Brazil.** Published in *Springer Nature*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98067-2_91-1.

(d) Mapping the research landscape of conservation agriculture as a panacea for achieving soil health and sustainable development goals using scientometrics. Submitted to *Discover Sustainability* (*under review*).

(e) Soil organic carbon stocks as driven by land use in Mato Grosso State: The Brazilian Cerrado agricultural frontier. Submitted to *Discover Sustainability* (*under review*).

(f) Land use and Soil C stock changes: a 3-decade State-scale appraisal in São Paulo, Brazil. Submitted to the *International Journal of Environmental Research* (*under review*).

Subproject Subproject 3.2.5 – The MONS Project: Mechanisms of Nitrous Oxide Emission in Tropical Soil aims to address critical issues related to the sustainability of tropical agriculture.

Lucas Pecci Canisares (Postdoctoral - FAPESP # 2023/04329-9)

The focus is on the importance of increasing food production sustainably, with a particular emphasis on mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The MONS project is dedicated to understanding and mitigating nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions in tropical soils, a potent GHG and the largest source of GHG emissions in agroecosystems. Thus, the MONS project will significantly contribute to the research areas of nutrient cycling and GHG emissions, by improving the understanding of biological processes and providing tools for modeling and developing climate change mitigation strategies. So far, the project compiled data from multiple experiments found in the literature. This study examined how the composition of cover crops determines the abundance of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) and archaea (AOA) in agroecosystems, and how different abundances alter N₂O emissions. Analysis of published studies revealed that grass cover crops generally reduce AOB and AOA abundance, while legumes enhance AOB abundance. Brassica and the mix of cover crops had inconclusive effects due to limited data. A linear regression indicated a significant correlation ($R^2 = 0.44$) between legume coverage and elevated N₂O emissions, which were associated with higher AOB abundance. Grasses did not show a significant relationship between AOB abundance and N₂O emissions. These findings suggest that cover crop selection influences key microbial groups and N₂O emissions, emphasizing the importance of considering cover crop species in agroecosystems to optimize nitrogen cycling and improve sustainability.

Canisares, L.P., Hazard, C., Nicol, G., Bouskill, N., Cherubin, M.R. **Cover crop groups influence the abundance of ammonia-oxidizing microorganisms of agricultural soils.** Advanced draft.

3.3 Soil health in the semi-arid environment (desertification, restoration, integrated systems)

Subproject 3.3.1 – Soil health assessment in desertified drylands in Brazil
Antonio Yan Viana Lima (PhD student – FAPESP # 2024/03722-1)

The doctoral project "Soil health assessment in desertified drylands in Brazil" is part of the soil research program at the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON) and addresses the degradation of drylands in northeastern Brazil, particularly in desertification nuclei, due to land use changes and the advance of climate change. Focusing on four desertification nuclei: Iraçuba-CE, Cabrobó-PE, Gilbués-PI, and Cariris Velhos-PB, the study aims to quantify and compare soil health in areas of native vegetation, advanced desertification, and restoration. Using chemical, physical, and biological soil indicators, as well as molecular techniques like metatranscriptomics, the project seeks to understand the microbial dynamics of soils in the Brazilian Semiarid region. The results will provide valuable data to develop strategies and policies against desertification, reducing climate vulnerability and improving food security. Aligned with the CCARBON initiative, the project addresses soil degradation in carbon stocks and promotes sustainable practices for the restoration of Brazilian dryland ecosystems, contributing to the research, innovation, and dissemination goals of CCARBON. Previous studies have shown that reclaimed areas in the Iraçuba desertification nucleus have seen a significant increase in soil health to levels similar to those in areas of native Caatinga vegetation, indicating that the adoption of techniques adapted to the reality of the Brazilian Semiarid region is the key to increasing the productivity and sustainability of these areas.

Lima, A.Y.V., Cherubin, M.R., Silva, D.F., Mota, J.C.A., Silva, F.G.M., Araujo, A.S.F., Melo, V.M.M., Verma, J.P., Pereira, A.P.A. **Grazing exclusion restores soil health in Brazilian drylands under desertification process**, *Applied Soil Ecology*, v. 193, 105107, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2023.105107>

Araujo, A.S.F., Pereira, A.P.A., Pereira, A.P.A., Lima, A.Y.V., Melo, V.M.M., Medeiros, E.V., Mendes, L.W. **A desertificação e a saúde do solo no bioma Caatinga**. In: Nogueira, T.A.R., Cherubin, M.R., Pereira, A.P.A., Tiecher, T. (Org.). *Tópicos em Ciência do Solo (XII)*. 1 ed. Viçosa: Sociedade Brasileira de Ciência do Solo, 2023, v. 1, p. 7-23.

Lima, A.Y.V., Cherubin, M.R., Greschuk, L.T., Muniz, G.A.M., Cavalcante, D.M., Pereira, A.P.A. **Unrevealing soil health research in the Brazilian Semiarid region: a bibliometric approach**. *Experimental Agriculture*, 2024 (under review).

Lima, A.Y.V., Greschuk, L.T., Villela, J.M., Muniz, G.A.M., Cherubin, M.R. **Effectiveness of degradation recovery techniques in drylands: a meta-analysis approach**. *Advanced draft*.

Subproject 3.3.2 – Soil carbon sequestration under integrated agricultural systems in Brazilian drylands

Lucas Tadeu Greschuk (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2023/00438-8)

Land use change and soil organic matter (SOM) loss in agricultural areas are the activities that contribute most to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Brazil. In this sense, the adoption of management practices that reduce GHG emissions, such as integrated agricultural systems (IAS), is fundamental to mitigating climate change and ensuring sustainable agricultural development. However, although the benefits of IAS have been proven in some regions, such as Cerrado and Atlantic Forest biomes, the potential of these systems are almost unexplored in the Brazilian drylands (Caatinga biome). Therefore, the objective of this project is to evaluate the change in soil C stock in integrated agricultural systems in the Brazilian dryland region, providing recommendations for land management and the development of public policies. Soil samples were collected up to 1 m depth in the states of Ceará (CE), Piauí (PI), and Pernambuco (PE). The treatments comprised areas with different levels of intensification of integrated systems, degraded and non-degraded pasture, native forest, and monoculture. Variations in total soil organic carbon (SOC) and nitrogen (N) stocks were quantified, and soil organic matter (SOM) fractions were obtained by the physical fractionation method. The data will be submitted to variance analysis and, when significant, to Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$). Further, multivariate techniques will be applied to identify the relationship between the soil health indicators and the evaluated systems. A literature review was submitted in the *Catena* journal (attached file) about SOC and N stock variations in different land uses, including IAS in drylands. The main findings were that there is a possibility of increasing SOC stock through the recovery of degraded pastures in the study region. There are no observations of studies that evaluated SOC stock in semi-arid climate areas. Future results will be derived from analyzing data collected in the field and modeling for future scenarios.

3.4 Methodological advances in soil health for application in agriculture

Subproject 3.4.1 – Development of on-farm and computational tools for assessing soil health in Brazilian croplands

Bruna Emanuele Schiebelbein (PhD candidate - FAPESP # 2023/10897-0)

Evaluating and enhancing soil health is essential for ensuring agricultural systems are more productive and resilient. To conduct comprehensive soil health assessments in Brazil, it is imperative to develop on-farm and advanced computational approaches. On-farm methods can be included as a promising tool for assessing soil health directly in the field as long as it is associated with appropriate computational techniques to encompass its complexity. These methods should be simple and affordable, enabling producers and technicians to conduct their on-site assessments backed up by computational approaches for translating the measurements into valuable information. This allows stakeholders to obtain insights to pursue more sustainable land management practices. In combination with on-farm methods, computational approaches further enhance the scalability of the soil health assessments. However, to ensure precise assessments, it is crucial to improve interpretation curves and develop region-specific algorithms that account for diverse conditions in terms of soil types, climate, topography, parent material, land use, and management practices. This is especially significant for Brazil, as it is a major player in global food production and ranks fourth worldwide in publishing soil health studies. In this project, our goal is to develop tools (on-farm and computational approaches) to assess soil health in Brazilian agricultural areas. To achieve this, we have organized the project into five work packages: 1. Develop an on-farm Soil Health Kit for assessing soil health in the field by farmers and managers. 2. Utilize a large dataset of Brazilian agricultural lands to generate the "Status of Soil Health" using the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF). 3. Develop algorithms for soil health indicators (such as pH, P, K, C, and Bd) specific to Brazil (SOHMA Tool). and 4. compare the SOHMA Tool with algorithms used in the SMAF Tool. Finally, 5. Integrate the SOHMA Tool into an interactive web-based platform. We have completed Work Package 1 by launching a method for assessing soil health directly in the field. This method includes sampling guidelines, a step-by-step procedure for evaluating 7 soil health indicators (infiltration, aggregate stability, visual analysis of soil structure, pH, biological activity, macrofauna assessment, and visual separation of aggregates), and the generation of a soil health index. This evaluation system has been validated against standard methodologies and across different uses and management practices (advanced draft). Additionally, a patent application has been filed with the INPI. Preliminary results were obtained in Work Package 2, 'Status of Soil Health,' using the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF) (data analysis). The analysis revealed significant variances in soil health indicators across different Brazilian biomes, based on the integration of five soil health indicators: soil carbon, phosphorus, potassium, bulk density, and pH. In general, the 0-10 cm soil layer operates at over 80% of its peak potential, indicating room for improvement in soil health through sustainable practices. SMAF's findings underscore the inherent influence of climate and soil characteristics on soil health. These insights highlight Brazil's central role in promoting soil health and advocating for sustainable agricultural practices globally.

Schiebelbein, B. E.; Cherubin, M. R. **Method for assessing soil health and its use.** Application Number: BR 10 2024 015629 3. Filing Date: 30 Jul. 2024.

Schiebelbein, B. E.; Cherubin, M. R. **Field User Guide for the SOHMA Soil Health Kit**. University of São Paulo. Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391557>. 2024. Available at: <https://www.livrosabertos.abcd.usp.br/portaldelivrosUSP/catalog/book/1311>

Subproject 3.4.2 – Avaliação da saúde do solo em áreas agrícolas no Sul do Brasil: uma abordagem utilizando múltiplas metodologias e escalas de aplicação
Viviana Meneghini (MSc student – FAPESP # 2024/02508-6)

Climate change adaptation management solutions that improve soil health are key strategies for achieving production stability and making the productive environment more resilient. Metrics representing soil health in large areas and in a simple way should be studied to facilitate management practices and sustainable land use. In this sense, the Soil Health Index (ISS) represents a robust quantitative basis that has been explored throughout the world. On the other hand, there is the Management Quality Index (IQM), which consists of a potential qualitative metric of production practices and lacks research to investigate its use. The SOHMA Soil Health Kit is a simple tool that can be applied in the field. This study seeks to evaluate soil health in agricultural areas in southern Brazil with contrasting management systems using multiple methodologies and application scales. For this purpose, soil samples will be collected in 12 areas in contrasting management systems in the state of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil. Management quality indicators will be calculated to obtain the IQM. The soil health indicators investigated include chemical, physical and biological attributes and the calculation of the ISS (field and laboratory). In addition, the SOHMA Soil Health Kit will be applied, generating a field ISS. It is expected that changes caused by management practices will be detected by both IQM and ISS. In addition, management practices that improve soil health are expected to result in greater productivity.

Subproject 3.4.3 – Stratification of soil sampling using spatio-temporal soil and plant mapping technologies: bases for defining the uncertainties and scalability of the assessment (baseline and monitoring) of soil carbon stocks
Dr. Guilherme Martinelli Sanches (Post Doc candidate - FAPESP # 2024/11109-8)

Assessing soil carbon stocks (SCE) to characterise the baseline and then monitoring (MRV - monitoring, registration and verification) the impacts of the management practices adopted is a process that requires intensive soil sampling in the field, making the process time-consuming, expensive and not very scalable. Therefore, finding solutions to optimise field sampling without increasing the uncertainty of SCE measurements has become a technical and scientific challenge that needs to be overcome in the coming years. The main objective of this research project is to assess whether the design of homogeneous management zones (HMZ) allows for adequate stratification of the crop for characterising the soil C stocks (baseline and monitoring), bringing improvements in estimates (reduction of uncertainties) and economic advantages compared to traditional sampling methodologies in dense grids. We hope to find (technical and economic) indicators that justify and guide an accurate and reliable diagnosis of the SCE baseline, contributing to the advancement of science in this area.

Appendix 5.1

Received: 22 March 2024 | Revised: 16 July 2024 | Accepted: 19 July 2024

DOI: 10.1111/gcb.13108

RESEARCH ARTICLE

WILEY

Soil carbon stocks in sugarcane cultivation: An evidence synthesis associated with land use and management practices

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Abstract

Biofuels are essential to ensure the energy transition and mitigating of climate change. However, understanding the impact of land use change (LUC) and management practices on soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks is fundamental to ensuring well-founded policymaking and assessing the sector's carbon footprint. Here, we conducted a meta-analysis (511 pairwise observations) to obtain Brazil's SOC stock change factors (SOC_{scf}) for LUC and management practices in sugarcane fields. Our results showed that converting native vegetation to sugarcane reduced

Appendix 5.2

Chapter 4

Cover Crops and Soil Health in Brazilian Agricultural Systems

Victória Santos Souza, Beatriz da Silva Vanoli, Bruna Emanuèle Schiebelbein, Larissa de Souza Bortolo, Martha Lustosa Carvalho, Ieda Carvalho Mendes, Mauricio Roberto Cherubin

Book Editor(s): Ieda Carvalho Mendes, Mauricio Roberto Cherubin

First published: 06 March 2024 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch4>

Book Series: ASA, CSSA, and SSSA Books

Chapter One - Integrated agricultural systems: The 21st century nature-based solution for resolving the global FEEES challenges

[Chukwudi Nwaogu](#) ^{a, b} , [Mauricio R. Cherubin](#) ^a

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[Chukwudi Nwaogu](#) , [Oluwatosin A. Fagbami](#), [Babatunde Olushola](#) & [Mauricio R. Cherubin](#)

Appendix 5.4

Applied Soil Ecology 193 (2020) 103107

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Applied Soil Ecology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/apsoil

Grazing exclusion restores soil health in Brazilian drylands under desertification process

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
 Soil management
 Soil quality
 Land degradation
 Brazilian aridland
 Invertebrate restoration

ABSTRACT

The Brazilian drylands (Catinga biome) are facing accelerated soil desertification due to human activities (e.g., overgrazing). However, restoration practices (e.g., grazing exclusion), are promoting to curb soil desertification and, eventually, increase soil functioning. However, the understanding of soil health (SH) changes, induced by desertification and restoration in the Catinga biome remains, poorly understood. Here, the SMAF (Soil Management Assessment Framework) was applied to assess the impact of desertification and long-term grazing

Appendix 5.5

Catena
Soil carbon storage in Brazilian drylands: A review
 –Manuscript Draft–

Manuscript Number:	CATENA25842R2
Article Type:	VSI: Carbon inventories in agriculture and forestry
Keywords:	semi-arid; soil organic carbon; Land use; integrated agricultural systems
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Appendix 5.6

Appendix 6 Principal Investigator: Tiago Osório Ferreira

BLUE CARBON

Research Question:

How will climate change and deforestation impact blue carbon soil dynamics?

Main objective:

To investigate the nature and stability of interactions between iron and organic matter in preserved mangroves and mangroves impacted by extreme climate events.

Subproject 1 – “Impact of Extreme Weather on Iron-Mediated Organo-Mineral Interactions in Mangrove Soils”

Dr Francisco Ruiz (post-doctoral researcher) / grant: FAPESP 2023/06841-9)

Progress:

Laboratorial analyses

All laboratory analyses have been completed, including carbon and nitrogen determination, isotopic analyses, wet-chemical fractionation, differential calorimetry, Rock-Eval thermal analysis, and pyrolysis coupled with gas chromatography and mass spectrometry.

Modelling

Dr. Ferreira's group has compiled a comprehensive dataset on iron (Fe) and soil organic carbon (SOC) variables from mangroves across the Brazilian coast. Modeling efforts have been undertaken to elucidate the relationship between Fe biogeochemistry and SOC in mangrove soils.

Results

Fe-SOC associations account for an important pool of total SOC, estimated at 10-40%, through empirical and modelled data. The SOC associated with reactive Fe represents *a priori* labile pool, that is likely subject to constant recycling in mangrove soils. However, these associations are highly vulnerable to the impacts of land use changes, which can alter Fe geochemistry and consequently reduce the Fe-SOC pool.

Scientific Publications

One paper is currently under review in Nature Communications (doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4650556/v1). Two additional papers are in the final stages of editing and will be submitted soon (targeted journals: Nature Communications/ Nature Geoscience/ STOTEN).

Highlights

- 1- Random Forest regression analysis of the extensive dataset revealed that Fe biogeochemistry plays a significant role in controlling SOC variability (Fe relative importance: 46%; $R^2 = 0.49$).
- 2- Although Fe-SOC associations represent an important SOC pool, they are highly susceptible to land-use change and extreme climatic events.
- 3- New experiments are planned to explore the microscale processes underlying Fe-SOC associations.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

The next steps include writing and submitting papers based on the results already obtained, as well as conducting new laboratory experiments to further investigate the nature, stability, and significance of Fe-SOC associations in mangroves.

How to transform degraded soils into climate-smart solutions?

CLIMATE SMART SOILS

Main objective:

To evaluate different types of waste for the restoration of degraded areas, aiming to restore soil functioning, including plant production and soil carbon sequestration.

Subproject 1 – “Iron mining tailings as a soil amendment and in the construction of smart-C soils: smart agriculture against climate change and soil degradation” (FAPESP

Subproject 1.1 – “The use of mining waste and construction waste for the creation of smart soil: a sustainable approach to mitigate climate change.”

Douglas Gomes Viana (Post-Doctorate FAPESP 2023/16382-1)

Subproject 1.2 – “Technosols as a nature-based solution: integrating solid waste for regenerative agriculture and climate change mitigation”

Beatriz Marchese Silva (Dr student CAPES 88887.902748/2023-00)

Project Progress Summary: The project aims to evaluate the initial establishment of organic matter stabilization mechanisms in Technosols constructed from a mixture of iron mining tailings and civil construction waste in different proportions where the tropical grass species *Urochloa brizantha* cv. Marandu was cultivated. The Technosols were compared to natural soil (Haplic Ferralsol) to assess the ability of the artificial soils to promote ecosystem services. Significant progress has been made in the following areas:

1. Introduction and Context:

- Addressed the significant production of solid waste in Brazil and the inadequate disposal of it, as well as how this issue significantly impacts the country.
- Highlighted the importance of using Technosols (artificial soils) for the recovery of degraded areas, carbon sequestration, and improving soil sustainability.
- Evaluated the growth capacity of the tropical grass in the solid waste and the plant's ability to add carbon to the system.

2. Experimental data:

- Conducted a field experiment in Piracicaba, São Paulo, where Technosols were constructed with different amounts of iron mining waste and civil construction waste, and where the species *Urochloa brizantha* cv. Marandu was also cultivated.
- The field experiment was conducted over 120 days (the tropical grass cycle) to evaluate aboveground biomass. After the first cut, the plants regrow, and an additional 3 cuts will be performed on the same plants according to this 120-day cycle.

3. Methodology and Analysis:

- Characterized the chemical, physical, and mineralogical properties of the different solid wastes (iron mining tailing and construction waste) to understand the potential of these materials to be transformed into a productive and healthy soil.
- After 120 days of conducting the experiment, the plants (*Urochloa brizantha* cv. Marandu) were harvested and analyzed, as well as the different Technosols.
- Chemical, physical, and biological analyses were performed. Analyses were also conducted to evaluate the mechanisms of organic matter stabilization (organo-mineral interactions).
- All analyses were conducted on both the Technosols and the control soil (natural soil).

4. Results:

- In the first cycle, the plants grew significantly more in the Technosols than in the natural soil.
- The Technosols proved to be effective in supporting plant growth and demonstrated great potential for carbon sequestration when cultivated with tropical grasses.

5. Publications:

The group has already submitted a manuscript in Land Degradation and Development.

The project has established a robust basis for understanding the potential of Technosols as an effective nature-based solution for waste management and the restoration of degraded areas. Future efforts will concentrate on further investigating the mechanisms of organic matter stabilization (organo-mineral interactions), validating the results with additional field data, and developing strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change on the mining and construction sectors.

Subproject 2 – “Exploring the organic carbon stabilization mechanisms of remineralizers: strategies to sequester carbon and benefit soil organic matter in agricultural systems”

Thomas dos Santos Trentin (Dr student CNPq 400761/2021-1)

Project Progress Summary: The project aims to explore the processes of organic carbon stabilization via organo-mineral interactions with different rock powders (RPs) in order to outline their uses in agricultural systems as enhancers of carbon sequestration in the soil, through two experimental approaches. The first consists of measuring, in laboratory, the nature and potential of RPs to promote carbon stabilization and the impact of the rhizosphere in this context of rock weathering and carbon sequestration, and the second tests, in greenhouse, the potential for increases in the stabilization of C in soils of different textural classes conditioned RP. Thus, an update on the conduct of the work follows:

6. Introduction and Context:

- The project addresses the context of the use of ground silicate rocks on the global and national stage, and how the process of enhanced rock weathering presents potential co-benefits for agriculture, in addition to the already explored geological sequestration of CO₂ from this practice.
- Although it is a nature-based solution, little is known and studied about the potential of these comminuted materials to promote interactions with soil organic matter and stabilize and sequester it.
- With the rhizosphere driving weathering processes, it is believed that agricultural systems in tropical climates have the capacity to intensify these possible relationships between rock powders and soil organic carbon.

7. Experimental data:

- An experiment was carried out in a greenhouse in Piracicaba, São Paulo, where soils of contrasting texture, one clayey and the other sandy, were conditioned with different rock powders and kept vegetated with the species *Urochloa brizantha* cv. Marandu.
- After 10 months of cultivation and frequent mowing to simulate agricultural management, the rhizospheric soil was collected for subsequent physical fractionation and elemental and organic carbon readings.

8. Methodology and Analysis:

- The rock powders chemical and mineralogical properties were characterized, through X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and X-ray diffraction (XRD), respectively, to help perceive their potential and capabilities of changing the soil environment and its interaction with carbon.
- To address organo-mineral interactions and organic matter stabilization mechanisms, the bulk soil carbon content was measured, as well as the carbon of the particulate and the mineral associated organic matter fractions, the latter of which had its exchangeable elemental and dissolved organic carbon content analyzed.

9. Results:

- In clayey soil, there is an increase in the organic carbon content allocated to the mineral associated organic matter fraction when conditioned with diabase powder.
- Through multivariate analysis, a multilevel paired comparison, post-Permanova, showed that clayey soil conditioned with granite differs statistically from the control (without rock powder), but not from soils conditioned with diabase or phonolite.

The project has already generated innovative data and information on the rock powder potential, in tropical climate and agriculture, to establish interactions with soil's organic matter, through the mineral associated fraction. Subsequent work are expected to narrow the knowledge gap regarding carbon stabilization mechanisms derived from rock powder use in soil, and then providing insights to develop effective strategies on mitigating the impacts of climate change and boosting agricultural productivity

Highlights

- 1- Technosols showed significant potential to support plant growth and carbon sequestration through tropical grasses, positioning them as a promising nature-based solution for waste management and area restoration.
- 2- Organomineral interactions will be described and a soil quality index will be developed to highlight the capacity of climate-smart soils to promote ecosystem services.
- 3- Rock powder demonstrated potential to establish interactions with organic carbon and promote its stabilization in the mineral associated fraction of organic matter when added to soil as an amendment, within tropical agricultural conditions.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

For the Technosol project, the priority will be to thoroughly investigate the mechanisms of organic matter stabilization, particularly those related to organo-mineral interactions, and to develop the soil quality index using the SMAF tool to understand the capacity of these soils to promote ecosystem services. The team plans to conduct more precise and sensitive analyses to characterize organo-mineral interactions, such as FTIR, TGA, and XANES. Additionally, the project aims to create a nature-based solution through the use of Technosols for climate change mitigation and the restoration of degraded areas.

As for the rock powder approach, the laboratory described experiment will be installed and conducted to assess the modulating factor that the rhizosphere can have in promoting rock weathering and subsequently its effect in interacting with carbon. Although data was collected in a greenhouse experiment, a new one with higher doses will be conducted according to the methodology of the already made. Furthermore, organo-mineral interactions of the collected experiment (and future ones) will be further investigated with FTIR and TGA approaches.

Appendix 6.1

Preprints are preliminary reports that have not undergone peer review.
They should not be considered conclusive, used to inform clinical practice,
or referenced by the media as validated information.

Iron's role in soil organic carbon (de)stabilization in mangroves under land use change

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Submission Overview

Initial Submission

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This manuscript has been submitted to the editorial office for review. Changes cannot be made during editorial review, but you can view the information and files you submitted, below.

Article Type

Research Article

Title

Technosols made of iron mine tailings and construction and demolition waste as an alternative for sustainable solid waste management

Manuscript Files

Name	Type of File	Size
Silva et al 2024 - submission.docx	Main Document - MS Word	14.2 MB
Supplementary file1.docx	Supplementary Material for Review	5.3 MB
Cover letter11.docx	Cover letter / Comments	69.1 KB

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Appendix 7 Principal Investigator: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo

Research Question:

How to measure the carbon consumed by enhanced weathering (EW) of silicate rock powders (SRP) applied to soil with sufficient certainty for the C capture certification/ carbon credit market?

Main objective:

Improve Measurement, Report and Verification (MRV) in the Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW) path for inorganic Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR). In addition, increase the public awareness for climate change and carbon economy via the establishment of an Educational Station, the Educarbon Project, both in formal (schools) and non-formal environments.

Subproject 1 – “Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) using Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW) of in basic rocks”

- *Luis Fernando Vieira da Silva (DR student, CAPES)*
- *Juliana C. do Nascimento (Dr Student, CAPES)*

Subproject 2 – “Increase of the resilience of sandy soils towards the climate change using K-clays from mine waste”

- *Raissa Razera MSc, FAPESP 2022/15186-1; BEPE 2023/12915-5 University of Newcastle – UK)*

- *Aline Vitti Secco (MSc. CAPES)*
- *Leonardo Fontoura Trivelim (IC, FAPESP 2024/05622-4)*

Subproject 3 –“EDUCARBON: expanding public awareness about climate change and carbon economy”

Highlights

- 1- Successfully measured carbon concentration in soil solution samples.
- 2- Estimate potential inorganic carbon capture during weathering stages using a saprolite profile.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

- Advance the use of thermal methods to quantify and discriminate inorganic and organic carbon in soil and other geomaterials. The GPMSO research group recently acquired a TG-DSC equipment and is adapting the lab to install it.
- Conclude the Project “Verification and validation of enhanced rock weathering in tropical soils” funded by the Grantham Foundation. The project is being developed in partnership with the University of Newcastle (UK) and the German Startup InPlanet.
- Finish the renewing of the installations in the EDUCARBON Station and deploy the activities.
- Organize the V Brazilian Congress of Rock Dust.

Published Papers

Manning, D. A. C., de Azevedo, A. C., Zani, C. F., & Barneze, A. S. (2024). **Soil carbon management and enhanced rock weathering: The separate fates of organic and inorganic carbon.** *European Journal of Soil Science*, 75(4), e13534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13534>

Santos, R. A., Reis, B. R., Azevedo, A. C., & Sermarini, R. A. (2023). **Potential Errors in Cation Exchange Capacity Measurement in Soils Amended with Rock Dust: Two Case Studies.** *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 55(3), 329–342. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00103624.2023.2268650>

Azevedo, A. C.; Manning, D. A. C.(2024) **A proposal to clarify the use of Sum of Bases in the Brazilian Remineralizer Regulation and in Soil Science.** *Rev. Bras. Ciênc. Solo*.2023;47:e0220053. DOI: 10.36783/18069657rbc20220053

Invited abstracts in American Geophysical Union (AGU) Congress:

- Azevedo, A. C.; Silva, L. F. V. 2024. **What if rock dust would weather like a regolith profile**
- Azevedo, A. C.; Silva, R. C. 2024. **Quantification of the precipitated phases during the artificial weathering of basalt in a tropical soil: an exploratory experiment.**

Events

- Selecionado pelo GT Remineralizadores para realização do V Congresso Brasileiro de Rochagem 8-11 Julho 2025.
- Convidado para co-autoria no minicurso “**Agrominerais silicáticos no Brasil**”, durante 51º. Congresso Brasileiro de Geologia, em Belo Horizonte.

Organizations

- Member of the Technical Council of ABREFEN (Brazilian Association for the Remineralizers and Natural Fertilizers)
- Member of the Work Group of the Cascade Initiative (Phyllanthropic NGO) for catalyzing a community-driven “Community Standard for Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW)”.

Appendix 7.1

Received: 20 December 2023 | Revised: 17 June 2024 | Accepted: 21 June 2024

DOI: 10.1111/eggs.13534

OPINION

European Journal of
Soil Science WILEY

Soil carbon management and enhanced rock weathering: The separate fates of organic and inorganic carbon

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Abstract

Soil carbon (C) management has been promoted as one of the few readily available strategies to mitigate the rising concentration of atmospheric CO₂ and its associated impacts on climate change. One of these carbon management strategies is enhanced rock weathering (ERW) which involves adding crushed silicate rocks to the soil. These rocks weather and remove atmospheric CO₂ by converting it into bicarbonate in solution. The approach requires careful interpretation of the differences between soil organic carbon (SOC) and soil inorganic carbon (SIC) and their measurement, with implications for land management and C credit accounting. In this Opinion, we emphasise the distinct nature and fates of SOC and SIC, advocating for their separate management, particularly in C credit schemes. It is imperative that protocols for soil C management explicitly recognise the difference between SOC and SIC to prevent any ambiguity. Farmers should be able to claim credits for increases in SOC alongside and independently of any claim for credits for ERW (i.e. SIC). Despite the potential of

Potential Errors in Cation Exchange Capacity Measurement in Soils Amended with Rock Dust: Two Case Studies

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ABSTRACT

The use of rock dust in agriculture has increased worldwide and particularly in Brazil since its regulation by Law 12.890 (2013). However, some inconsistent results in standard chemical analysis of soils amended with rock dust have drawn attention, and among them, cation exchange capacity (CEC). This paper evaluates the increase in sum of bases (SB) and CEC of two soils amended with commercial rock dust (magnesium silicate), measured by four methods: ion exchange resin, potassium chloride (KCl), compulsive exchange and cesium adsorption. The maximum possible increase of SB in the soil was estimated based on the total chemical analysis of the rock dust and compared to the measured CEC results. We concluded the resin method inflated the results, due to the dissolution of rock dust particles by the acid extraction used to recover the adsorbed cations in resin beads. These extra cations caused overestimation of the sum of bases and consequently, of the estimated CEC. Among the methods used, direct CEC methods were more appropriate, as well as the KCl, since it does not employ acid extractions at any step. In addition, calculations based on the total chemical analysis of the

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 4 October 2022
Accepted 4 October 2023

KEYWORDS

Agrominerals; methods of soil analysis; remineralizers; rock weathering

Division - Soil Use and Management | Commission - Soil Fertility and Plant Nutrition

A proposal to clarify the use of Sum of Bases in the Brazilian Remineralizer Regulation and in Soil Science

Antonio Carlos de Azevedo ²

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Appendix 8 Principal Investigator: Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez

Research Question:

This study aims to answer the question: to what extent do restoration and commercial tree plantations mitigate GHG emissions from agriculture?

Main objective:

The main objective is to understand the processes underlying agriculture's greenhouse gas emissions and determine whether restoration and commercial tree plantations contribute positively to the net balance as a carbon sequestration subsystem.

Subprojects

One doctoral student and one post-doc researcher are being recruited to work on subprojects directly funded by CCARBON. Two parallel research strategies have been used to examine related questions regarding the role of forest plantations as provisioners of ecosystem services: supplementary studies financed by FAPESP, and related studies supported by other funding sources.

- *Directly funded by CCARBON.*

<p>Subproject 1 <i>Development of Decision Support Systems for Conflicting Objectives to Improve Governance of Production, Conservation, Restoration, and Sustainable Ecosystem Services:</i> The project aims to evaluate global multicriteria forest plantation management approaches that identify consensus solutions for diverse stakeholders and adapt these decision support systems to Brazilian contexts, emphasizing ecosystem services and carbon sequestration.</p>	<p>PD researcher In recruiting phase</p>
<p>Subproject 2 <i>Using Active and Passive Sensors from Ground and Orbital Platforms for Estimating Aboveground Biomass and Carbon:</i> the main objective is to evaluate the potential of remote sensing approaches to derive precise estimates of the aboveground biomass of forest plantations.</p>	<p>DR student In recruiting phase</p>

- *Supplementary studies funded by FAPESP.*
 Linked to Thematic Project 2021/00833-9 (DecisionES-BR) Decision Support for the Supply of Ecosystem Services under Global Change

<p>Subproject 3 <i>New approaches to support the decision-making process for stakeholders and policymakers involving forests, water, and biodiversity:</i> the main objective is to model decision-support systems capable of dealing with the interaction between forests and hydrological processes under the impacts of climate and land-use change, mainly in the State of São Paulo, Brazil.</p>	<p>PD researcher Jomil Costa Abreu Sales (2024/14444-2) 15/Oct/2024 a 14/Jun/2028</p>
<p>Subproject 4 <i>Accounting for hydrological services on the design and development of decision support systems for forest managers and policymakers:</i> the</p>	<p>DR student Giulia Domingues</p>

main objective is to model decision support systems capable of dealing with the interaction between forests and hydrological processes under the impacts of climate and land-use change, mainly in the State of São Paulo, Brazil.	Pedro (2024/13393-5) 01/Sep/2024 a 29/Feb/2028
Subproject 5 Modeling Decision Support Systems for Ecosystem Services of Forests Under Global Change: the doctoral candidate awarded this grant will focus on modeling decision support systems to manage the complexity of large-scale restoration program planning across various ecosystems, primarily in the state of São Paulo, Brazil.	DR student In recruiting phase Link to the call for candidates

- *Related studies supported by other funding sources.*

Subproject 6 Identifying Hotspots for Afforestation, Reforestation, and Regeneration Projects in Brazil: this master student work seeks to identify the most favorable types of forests and locations in Brazil for developing afforestation, reforestation, and regeneration projects, driven by a clear market demand for high-quality credits.	MSc student Davi Faiani D’Lippi 14/Jul/2023 a 15/Set/2025
Subproject 7 Using Unconventional Methods and LiDAR for Calculating Planted Tree Volume: The work of this master student aims to test the following hypotheses: Can models that estimate tree volume using cross-sectional area at heights above breast height (DBH) provide results that are statistically equal to or better than conventional models? Are LiDAR data reliable estimators of dendrometric variables and volume in commercial plantations?.	MSc student Leonardo Costa Peres 15/Jul/2022 a 16/Set/2024
Subproject 8 Impact of Precipitation Pattern Changes on Total Area and Biomass of the Atlantic Forest and Caatinga: This master's student uses publicly available GEDI LiDAR data from the International Space Station, multispectral data from Sentinel-1 and -2 satellites, and precipitation data to evaluate how above-ground vegetation structure varies with rainfall changes, transitioning from Atlantic Forest to semiarid regions.	MSc student Jose Jorge Monteiro Junior 08/Fev/2022 a 14/Out/2024

Highlights

- Subprojects 1 and 2 directly funded by CCARBON have not yet recruited the doctoral student and post-doctoral assistant. Therefore, it is too early to expect any highlight. Meanwhile, though, I have co-authored two papers (list at the end of this report) that provide important contributions to our future work.
- Subprojects 3 and 4 are at the very beginning with both beneficiaries of the assistantships still in the phase of signing their respective contracts with FAPESP. Subproject 5 still depends on whom will be selected among the candidates who have submitted their applications from the FAPESP call, which is still open. Anyhow, their prospective scientific advisors have already interacted with members of the European version of the DecionES project in the Symposium on Systems Analysis in Forest Resources (SSAFR) hosted in Spain from May 13th to 17th 2024. In that event we

shared common research interests and results, contributing with the presentations listed at the end of this report.

- The master student implementing subproject 6 is still in the data-gathering phase of his work.
- Master students implementing subprojects 7 and 8 are about to defend their dissertations. Promising results are expected in both works. Leonardo has found a good correlation between cross-sectional areas measured by LiDAR drones above DBH and individual tree biomass, which opens excellent opportunities to improve the efficiency and efficacy of Carbon measurements in the future. In Jorge's dissertation, the results are promising as well. His work opens the possibility of integrating LiDAR measurements collected by a LiDAR sensor on board the International Space Station and satellite multispectral images to remotely estimate biomass and its distribution as a function of rain precipitation.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

Next year will effectively allow for the implementation of the activities proposed in subprojects 1 to 5. Specifically, we expect to advance on the following actions:

- Subproject 1: Identify the most important conflicting interests that stakeholders manifest when managing planted forests and agriculture, and ways to produce consensual solutions supported by multicriteria decision support systems.
- Subproject 2: Evaluate biomass and carbon assessment strategies that integrate the use of terrestrial, aerial, and space LiDAR platforms.
- Subproject 3: Identify the most promising multicriteria forest plantation decision support systems developed worldwide that include, among other ecosystem services, carbon sequestration, and contact their scientific developers to start a scientific exchange collaboration network.
- Subproject 4: Identify the importance of hydrological processes in how riparian forests and planted forests contribute to carbon sequestration and the sustainable provision of other ecosystem services.
- Subproject 5: Identify the importance of biological diversity in how riparian forests and planted forests contribute to carbon sequestration and the sustainable provision of other ecosystem services.

Scientific publications

Papers

- Nobre, Silvana, Marc McDill, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez, and Luis Diaz-Balteiro. 2023. "**A General Rule-Based Framework for Generating Alternatives for Forest Ecosystem Management Decision Support Systems**" *Forests* 14, no. 9: 1717. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14091717>
- Nobre, Silvana, Marc McDill, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez, and Luis Diaz-Balteiro. 2024. "**Reframing the Model I, II and III harvest scheduling formulations in the context of managing forests for ecosystem services**". *In review*

Participation in an international conference

- McDill M; Nobre SR; Rodriguez LC; Diaz-Balteiro L (2024) Model N: A New Linear Programming Formulation for Forest Ecosystem Management Planning. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 62.
- Nobre SR; Guerin N; Zakia MJ; von Glehn HC; Rodriguez LCE (2024) Simulation and multicriteria analysis to generate multispecies combinations to support ReflorestaSP program: An Essential Component of São Paulo's Climate Action Plan. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 67.
- Nobre SR; McDill M; Rodriguez LC; Diaz-Balteiro L (2024) Evaluating Formulations and Efficacy of Models I, II, and N in Ecosystem Services Management. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 68.
- Ferraz SFB; Franzoni A; Rodriguez LCE; Nobre SR (2024) Sustainable Management of Eucalyptus Plantations in Brazil: Balancing Economics and Water-Related Ecosystem Services. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 38.
- Ferreira MP (2024) Estimating aboveground biomass of individual urban tree with hyperspectral and LiDAR data. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 39.
- Nascimento N; Brancalion P (2024) Assessing Fire Risk in the Brazilian Atlantic Forest: A Bayesian Spatial Analysis Approach. SSAFR 2024 Abstracts, p. 66.

These contributions were orally presented at the *20th Symposium on Systems Analysis in Forest Resources (SSAFR 2024)* held in Hondarribia, Basque Country, Spain, and can be accessed at <https://decisiones.ctfc.cat/SSAFR2024/program-map-abstracts/>

Appendix 8.1

Article

A General Rule-Based Framework for Generating Alternatives for Forest Ecosystem Management Decision Support Systems

Silvana Nobre ^{1,*}, Marc McDill ², Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez ³ and Luis Diaz-Balteiro ¹

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Abstract: Linear programming formulations of forest ecosystem management (FEM) problems proposed in the 1960s have been adapted and improved upon over the years. Generating management alternatives for forest planning is a key step in building these models. Global forests are diverse, and a variety of models have been developed to simulate management alternatives. This paper

Appendix 9 Principal Investigator: Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion

Research Question:

How to restore and measure tropical forest multifunctionality and resilience?

Main objective:

To understand the socio-ecological drivers of forest multifunctionality recovery by different reforestation approaches

Students: PD researcher Juliano van Melis, PD researcher Laura Vedovato (2024/03424-0), PD researcher Fábio Matos (2024/07707-7), DR student Ana Paula Ferez and IC student João Paulo Oliveira (2024/09791-5).

Highlights

- 1- conclusion of field data collection, analysis, and organization of nearly 800 30x30m plots established in forests restored by different methods (natural regeneration, restoration plantations, agroforestry, monocultures with regeneration, monocultures without regeneration, degraded forests, conserved forests, agropastoral land uses);
- 2- conclusion of lidar data collection, analysis, and organization of nearly 500.000 ha
- 3- DAG models (example Fig.1) prepared preliminary results obtained for different research lines (carbon, water, soil, timber production, biodiversity)

Rationale

1. higher soil water infiltration, which is associated with soils with lower bulk density and higher organic matter content, is associated with higher water availability to trees and better rooting, which favor their growth (the higher is soil water infiltration the higher is the biomass)
2. soils with higher clay content have higher nutrient stocks and higher water holding capacity, which favor tree growth (the higher is soil clay content the higher is the biomass)
3. soils with higher sum of bases, which have higher availability of nutrients to plant growth, favor biomass accumulation (the higher is sum of bases the higher is the biomass)
4. soils in steeper slopes are shallower and more susceptible to erosion and, then, to landslides. It thus may limit water and nutrient availability (lower tree growth and higher mortality) and increase disturbances (higher tree mortality) (the higher is the slope the lower is the biomass)
5. landscapes with higher proportion of agricultural land uses, which are associated with flatter terrains that favor mechanization and soils with higher sum of bases that enhance productivity, have higher frequency of disturbances (fires, soil erosion, herbicide drift) and, then, higher tree mortality (the higher is the % agriculture the lower is the biomass)
6. landscapes with higher proportion of native forest, which are associated with lands with lower value for agro-pastoral production, have a more intense and qualified dispersal of native tree seeds (recruitment of more individuals and of important species and functional groups for biomass accumulation) (the higher is the % native forest the higher is the biomass)
7. larger forest patches, which are associated with landscapes with higher native forest cover, have a more intense and qualified dispersal of native tree seeds (recruitment of more individuals and of important species and functional groups for biomass accumulation) (the higher is the forest patch the higher is the biomass)
8. plots located farther from forest edges, which are more common in larger forest patches, are exposed to lower levels of disturbances associated to edge effects, which impacts tree recruitment, mortality, and competition with ruderal plants (the higher is distance from the edge the higher is the biomass)
9. higher fire frequency, which is associated with landscapes with higher proportion of agricultural land uses, increases tree mortality and the proliferation of competitive ruderal plants, reducing biomass accumulation (the higher is fire frequency the lower is the biomass)
10. plots located farther from water courses may have lower water availability due to deeper water tables, and less intense and qualified dispersal of native tree seeds, as riparian buffers are important ecological corridors to seed dispersers, which may constrain the recruitment and growth of native trees (the higher is distance from water courses the lower is the biomass)
11. regions with higher climatic water deficit, which are associated with lower levels of precipitation, have lower water availability and higher frequency of fires, which reduces tree growth and increase mortality (the higher is climatic water deficit the lower is the biomass)
12. regions with higher temperatures favor tree growth, in spite of the increase of climatic water deficit in regions with lower precipitation (the higher is temperature the higher is the biomass)

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

Advance with data analysis and preparation of papers. We aim to have by the next year a paper submitted or published for the following topics:

- (1) Carbon stocking across tropical reforestation methods and conditions
- (2) Soil carbon recovery by tropical reforestation
- (3) Reforestation-specific models for estimating aboveground biomass with Lidar
- (4) Tree diversity recovery by different tropical reforestation methods
- (5) Tree composition recovery by different tropical reforestation methods
- (6) Soil water infiltration recovery by different tropical reforestation methods

Appendix 10 Principal Investigator: Helaine Carrer

Research Question:

How to boost the efficiency and rate of carbon fixation by plants?

Main objective:

The overall goal of this project is to manipulate and exploit the biochemical potential of plants to improve efficiency of photosynthesis to increase crop yield while maintaining atmospheric carbon balance.

Subproject 1 – Functional Genomics of genes related to the Light-dependent reactions (Photosystems I and II) to improve photosynthesis efficiency

Student Name: *Not yet designated*

This subproject has not been initiated yet since it depends on a student who will be selected to analyse the data produced by Prof. Marcos Buckeridge (IB-USP) who agreed with the use and continuation of his experiment of sugarcane and soybean plants under

high CO₂ in open chamber (De Souza et al., 2008; Bencke-Malato M et al., 2019) . The transcriptome of both plants was prepared and as a result identified genes related to photosynthesis with differential expression level. The functional genomics analysis of key genes is expected to improve photosynthesis efficiency.

Subproject 2 - Point mutations in the *rbcL* gene in the chloroplast genome aiming to improve photosynthesis efficiency.

Student Name *Felipe Georgete Scola (MSc student-Capes) and Pedro Boscarior Ferreira (post-doc Fapesp 2022/09094-7)*

Ribulose-1,5-Bisphosphato (RuBP) carboxylase/ oxygenase (RuBisCO) is the key enzyme for the fixation of atmospheric carbon and productivity of plants. At the moment, no single solution to optimize the CO₂ fixing process has been shown in higher plants. The availability of chloroplast transformation protocol allows the manipulation of the large subunit of RuBisCO (Whitney et al., 2011). We are proposing to test the point mutation of an alanine (Ala) 378 substituting a valine (Val) (A378V) in the tobacco chloroplast based on the results on *Synechococcus* (Satagopan et al., 2009). We used two *rbcL*-synthetic genes, pTT633 with the amino acid alanine changed to a valine (A378V) and another one without the replacement (pTT632). The transgenic plants obtained with both vectors are yellow and have slow growth under tissue culture. Considering that these vectors had some additional nucleotide changes beside the point mutation, new vectors are under construction.

Subproject 3 – Genetic Pathways from extremophile plants to improve abiotic stress tolerance and photosynthesis efficiency in cultivated plants

Student Name: *Giovana Carolyn Domingues Saito (MSc student-Capes and Pedro Boscarior Ferreira (post-doc Fapesp 2022/09094-7)*

This subproject is a continuation of the Fapesp project 2020/07578-1 “Genetic pathways from extremophile plants: new approach for crops genetic engineering to abiotic stress tolerance” in collaboration with Prof. León Bravo Ramirez, Universidad de La Frontera, which finished in May 2024. Also, this project is related to the post-doc project of Pedro Boscarior Ferreira-Fapesp 2022/09094-7. In order to study genes associated to the capacity of outlier species to tolerate stress with limited compromise of photosynthetic capacity, RNAseq were prepared of extremophile plants *Deschampsia antarctica*, *Deschampsia cespitosa*, *Prosopis tamarugo*, *Prosopis alba*, *Prosopis tamarugo*, *Prosopis chilensis* and two ecotypes of *Colobanthus quitensis*, ecotype *Antarctica* and *Conguillio*. De Novo transcriptome assembly was accomplished, and differential expression analysis (Love et al., 2014) identified distinguish important genes associated to outlier traits such as five genes from *P. tamarugo* (*PtPIF3*, *PtPLGG1*, *PtHB7*, *PtANR*, and *PtBBX32*), three from *Deschampsia* (*DaBT2*, *DaCIPK4*, and *DaHIPPI1*) and four from *Colobanthus* (*CqUF3GT*, *CqROF1*, *CqERF27*, and *CqSGS1*). These genes were cloned into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* vector and are under genetic transformation in *Nicotiana tabacum*. Up to this moment, seven genes were successfully transformed and are under RT-qPCR analysis.

Subproject 4 – Duckweed Biomass Production

Student Name: *Pedro Adolfo Andretto Repache (Agronomy Student – IC Fapesp 2024/05716-9)*

Given their fast growth and aquatic lifestyle, duckweeds are promising alternative for genetic manipulation to improve photosynthesis efficiency for biomass production. Although several protocols have been published for different duckweed species (Acosta et al., 2021), transformation efficiency is highly genotype-dependent. We transformed calli of *Lemna japonica* using *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* EHA105 harboring the UBQ:RUBY plasmid (HE et al., 2020).

Highlights

- 1- The efficiency of photosynthesis may be improved by genetic engineering of genes encoding enzymes responsible for light dependent reaction (photosystems II and I) and CO₂ fixation.
- 2- In modern agriculture, high-yield crop cultivars often exhibit a significant tradeoff between productivity and stress tolerance. Extremophytes are non-crop plant species, which manage to maintain high productivity while thriving in adverse conditions. The Chilean species *Strombocarpa tamarugo*, and Antarctic species *Deschampsia antarctica*, and *Colobanthus quitensis* ecotype Antarctica fall into this category. They are promising models for discovering stress tolerance mechanisms.
3. Duckweed comprises some of the smallest and fastest growing angiosperms known on Earth. Their tiny size and rapid growth by clonal propagation demand high rate of CO₂ fixation. Biotechnology approaches will improve the potential of duckweed to provide feedstocks for biofuel and biogas production.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

Subproject 1 and 2: Genes related to light-dependent-reactions will be selected and cloned for functional genomics; Vector for *rbcL* mutant will be prepared and used for tobacco chloroplast transformation.

Subproject 3: Homozygous plants will be tested under water stress conditions for physiological parameters such as chlorophyll fluorescence, leaf CO₂ assimilation rate (A) and stomatal conductance (gs) by an infrared gas analyzer (IRGA) (LI-COR, USA). Selected genes will be used to genetic transformation of sugarcane aiming water deficit tolerance and higher photosynthetic efficiency.

Subproject 4: Considering tissue culture takes 3 to 4 months to regenerate duckweed plants, new protocols will be tested in different genotypes. New vectors will be designed to improve efficiency of transformation.

It is expected to bring new students to the project and produce two publications.

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Appendix 11 Principal Investigator: Fernando Luis Cônsoli

Research Question:

How to exploit the interplay of soil plant insect pest microbiomes in pest management to enhance carbon accumulation, mineralization and sequestration?

Main objective:

Identify how pest management strategies can affect carbon accumulation, mineralization and sequestration

Subproject 1 – Interação multinível da microbiota do solo - planta - herbívoro no sistema milho e lagarta-do-cartucho sob o efeito de inseticidas com atividade antimicrobiana
Student Name: Tatiane Aparecida Domingues da Silva (Dr student FAPESP 2023/16516-8) - started 01/02/2024

Subproject 2 – A interferência de inseticidas contaminantes do solo na diversidade e abundância das comunidades de solo e no pool de carbono associado
Student Name: Ana Flávia Freitas Gomes (Post-doctorate FAPESP 2024/10455-0) – started 01/08/2024

Highlights

I have 4 subprojects (2 PhD and 2 PD), but only 2 have been initiated, and both this year (see above). So, I have not collected data yet to report.

Subproject 1

- Determination of the water retention capacity of the artificial soil
- Development of laboratory experiments, data collection and data analysis

- Renovation of greenhouse for experiment set up in collaboration with researchers of the Department of Byosystems
- Set up of greenhouse experiments and data collection

Subproject 2

- Experiment set up and sample collection

Appendix 12 Principal Investigator: Thais Maria Ferreira de Souza Vieira

Main objective:

Development of processes for the recovery of bioactive compounds from agro-industrial waste, considering all stages of the process—from the extraction of bioactive compounds using environmentally friendly technologies to the application of novel ingredients in food systems.

Subproject 1 – The objective of the overall project is to develop sustainable processes for recovering active compounds from avocado processing waste.

Student: Camila Maria Gonzales (Post-doctorate FAPESP)

Progress:

Laboratorial analyses

All laboratory analyses have been completed, including the extractions conducted using only water in a bath system with agitation, with and without ultrasound, employing central composite rotatable design (CCRD) experimental designs. The optimal conditions for the aqueous and ethanolic extraction of phenolic and antioxidant compounds from the residues were defined and microparticles were produced and applied in model systems.

Results

The phenolic compounds present in the extracts after optimization were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The identified compounds were gallic acid, catechin, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, 3,4-hydroxybenzoic acid, caffeic acid, and p-coumaric acid. The extracts obtained under the previously described conditions were microencapsulated and analyzed for their physicochemical, morphological, and antioxidant capacity characteristics. Application tests in lipid systems indicated the efficiency of the microparticles in preventing the progression of oxidation in the samples during accelerated tests. The results obtained indicate that the aqueous optimization strategy followed by the encapsulation of the extracts allowed for the adjustment of process parameters that enabled the protection of active compounds using sustainable and low-cost technologies.

Scientific Publications

Optimizing byproduct processing for clean label foods: Avocado and MSM-Tambaqui with a focus on zero waste. *Journal of Food Safety*. DOI: 10.1111/jfs.13160

Highlights

- Efficient Extraction: Ethanolic-water extracts from avocado byproducts were obtained with minimal solvent and energy use.

- Sustainable Application: Avocado byproduct extracts were effectively used to enhance the shelf life of food products, demonstrating a sustainable use of agricultural waste.
- Eco-Friendly Innovation: The study underscores the potential of using agricultural byproducts for natural preservation, contributing to a cleaner and more sustainable food industry.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

The integrated approach developed in this project is currently being tested on a pilot scale. Data from the pilot scale are essential to generate indicators of material and energy flows so that the carbon balance of the process can be presented. Thus, the research group continues to develop studies for the utilization of waste from vegetable oil processing and the application of new low carbon products in food systems.

Appendix 12.1

The screenshot shows the Wiley Author Services interface. At the top, there are navigation links: "Wiley Author Services", "My Dashboard", "Find a journal", and "Resources". Below this is a "Back to Dashboard" link. The main heading is "Manage this article".

The article details are as follows:

- Journal: Journal of Food Safety
- Title: Optimizing byproduct processing for clean label foods: Avocado and MSM-Tambaqui with a focus on zero waste
- DOI: 10.1111/jfs.13160
- Status: In Production

Below the article details, there are two main sections:

- Grow the impact of your research:** This section promotes "Feature your article with a Cover Image". It states: "This journal accepts artwork submissions for Cover Images. This is an optional service you can use to help increase the visibility of your research. For more information, including artwork guidelines, pricing, and submission details, please refer to our Cover Image resource page."
- Publication History:** This section shows a vertical timeline of the article's progress:
 - Submitted: May 19, 2023
 - Final revisions submitted: August 7, 2023
 - Accepted: August 11, 2023
 - In Production: (indicated by a circle at the end of the timeline)

Appendix 13 Principal Investigator: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira

Main objective:

To better understand the impact on GHG emissions and C sequestration in the intensive ruminant production systems, including improved pasture management practices.

Subproject 1 – Resilience of integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems to climate change in the Amazon Biome

Dra Alyce Raiana Monteiro dos Santos (Pós doc - FAPESP 2024/00033-0)

This project is linked to the Animal as a “Projeto Balcão”, and we will use data from a field experiment conducted in the Amazon biome, evaluating four systems: livestock, livestock-forestry, crop-livestock, and crop-livestock-forestry. Global circulation models and Representative Concentration Paths will be used to create climate change scenarios. The APSIM model will be used to simulate forage, soybean, and maize production scenarios. System resilience will be evaluated considering aspects of productivity and production resistance. With model validation and simulations of future climate scenarios, we will propose practical guidelines that can inform new public policies for the agricultural sector.

Highlights

- 1- The subproject was initiated in April 2024. For the resilience analysis, we are currently in the phase of organizing a 3-year database, gathering the information to perform simulations using APSIM.
- 2- A new analysis has been included in the project: Ecological Network Analysis (ENA). We aim to evaluate the agroecological performance of integrated systems in terms of efficiency, resilience, productivity, and dependence on N flow networks.
- 3- We conducted the ENA and observed that the crop-livestock-forest system presented the greatest intensity of N flows. The crop-livestock system shows greater self-sufficiency. An abstract was submitted for the ASA, CSSA, SSSA International Annual Meeting, which will take place in November 2024, to present these results.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle:

For the next year, climate change scenarios and productivity simulations of the system components (forage, soybean and maize) will be conducted to evaluate resilience. The BEPE project at CSIRO, Australia, is also planned. Additionally, preliminary ENA data will be presented at the ASA, CSSA, SSSA International Annual Meeting in November 2024.

Appendix 14 Principal Investigator: Adibe Luiz Abdalla

Main objective:

To evaluate the potential of innovative strategies involving the use of biomass, tropical algae, and biochar in reducing the environmental impact of ruminant livestock production by mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, enhancing feed efficiency, conserving ecosystems, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices

Subproject 1 – Stable isotopes in the determination of greenhouse gases from integrated systems: in vivo and in vitro approaches

Thaynã Gonçalves Timm (PD FAPESP 2024/06301-7): The objective of this project is to evaluate, in vitro, the production of enteric CH₄ from substrates containing biomass suitable for ruminant grazing in various silvopastoral systems (SPS), incorporating legumes, tropical macroalgae, and biochar. The study aims to assess both the short- and long-term contributions to CH₄ emissions, isotopic compositions, and the impact on the rumen microbiome.

The postdoctoral researcher began her research activities in June 2024 and has since collaborated closely with MSc student Jeraldine B. Vasconez (PPG CENA/USP) on the project titled “*Impact of tithonia diversifolia inclusion on ruminant rumen microbiota: an approach using in vitro continuous rumen fermentation technique*”. Together, they have been developing a long-term in vitro incubation system, with progress presented at the 58th Annual Meeting of the Brazilian Society of Animal Science (August 12–16, 2024).

The main objective of a comparative study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the in vitro gas production technique (IVGPT) versus the long-term in vitro rumen fermentation simulation (IVRFS) in assessing dry matter degradability (DMD), gas production (GP), and CH₄ production per unit of degraded dry matter in sheep. The study identified significant differences in DMD and GP per degraded dry matter between the two in vitro methods (IVGPT and IVRFS), although no significant differences in CH₄ production were observed. These findings suggest that the choice of method significantly influences the determination of DMD and GP per gram of incubated organic matter.

Subproject 2 – Forage biomass of *Tithonia diversifolia* associated with different agro-industrial co-products in sheep feed: potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions

Laura Bertolaso De Vecchi (DR FAPESP 2024/03777-0): The objective of this research is to evaluate nutritional strategies that mitigate greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) and improve animal diet quality using sustainable biomass sources in tropical livestock grazing systems. The study will test different diet formulations, focusing on reducing the carbon footprint by utilizing locally suitable agro-industrial by-products for nitrogen and energy supplementation. Additionally, it will assess the forage plant *Tithonia diversifolia* intercropped with grass pastures to enhance protein and energy balance in sheep diets and reduce enteric methane production. The research will also explore how changes in rumen biodiversity impact its functioning in response to methane mitigation feed additives.

This research has been partially financed supported by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA RC 25088 - Diversified tropical biomass associated to non-human edible feeds and co-products could reduce the GHG in dairy cattle?) since the start of Laura’s MSc program at PPG-ESALQ/USP in 2022. Her dissertation, concluded in November 2023 and intitled “*Evaluation of agro-industrial by-products associated with Tithonia diversifolia in ruminant feeding on ruminal degradability parameters, fermentative kinetics, and in vitro methane production*”; the study concluded the feasibility of formulating diets using selected agro-industrial by-products without compromising animal productivity and the nutritional quality of the provided diet.

Laura’s DR project at the PPG-CENA/USP will be evaluating the biomass mixes chosen

in her MSc project based on optimum IVDOM and CH₄ to be tested at long-term incubations. For those, the long-term in vitro rumen fermentation simulation (IVRFS) will be used to determine long-term IVDOM and CH₄ production and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of ¹³CH₄. Each fermenter will be outfitted with an input port for infusion of buffer and an outlet port to collect effluent. Fermenters will be housed in a circulating water bath at 39°C and fermentation will be carried out for 21. A subsample of gas produced during the fermentation process will be collected every 24h from the gas-tight collection bags to determine concentration of CH₄ and analyzed by gas chromatography. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CH₄ fraction will be also determined. The DNA extracted from the liquid effluent of each fermenter will be separated for 16S rRNA sequencing using Illumina MiSeq for identification and quantification (qPCR – mcrA, pmoA, mmoX genes) of the methanogenic and methanotrophic communities.

Subproject 3 – Manipulation of rumen fermentation through supplementation with cultivated seaweeds

FEALQ 896 Research project: The objective of this research is to investigate tropical macroalgae cultivated along the Brazilian coast for their potential use in ruminant production systems. The aim is to enhance forage quality and facilitate the development of agricultural products that reduce the greenhouse gas (GHG) and carbon footprint of these systems.

This research is financially supported by Instituto BKK (iBKK) under the Cooperation Agreement “Acordo de Cooperação Acadêmica Nacional entre a Universidade de São Paulo e o Instituto Bkk – Bonfarto Kaj Konservado.” The project hypothesizes that integrating tropical macroalgae from the Brazilian coast into ruminant production systems can improve forage quality while reducing the carbon and GHG emissions of these systems. By incorporating these macroalgae into ruminant diets, the project aims to mitigate methane emissions and promote the sustainability and efficiency of the national livestock sector.

The methodology involves in vitro assays to screen various macroalgae species for their effects on rumen fermentation parameters. The research progresses through several stages, including the determination of nutritional composition, evaluation of rumen fermentation effects, and assessment of impacts on rumen microbiota and animal performance. The project ultimately seeks to identify the most effective macroalgae species for ruminant diets, optimizing their potential to contribute to sustainable livestock production. The project will also focus on characterizing the nutritional quality of these algae, identifying species with anti-methanogenic properties, and evaluating their potential for reducing methane emissions and developing agricultural products based on the analyzed macroalgae.

Highlights

- 1- Setting up the long-term in vitro rumen fermentation system at the LANA-CENA/USP which will be incorporated in the USP Multi facility “CIPENBA - Central Integrada de Pesquisa e Experimentação em Nutrição e Biotecnologia Animal”.
- 2- The successful demonstration of the feasibility of formulating diets using selected agro-industrial by-products and *Tithonia diversifolia* in sheep feeding, which

effectively reduces enteric methane production without compromising animal productivity and nutritional quality.

3 - The studied algae have a nutritional composition comparable to control hay and significantly affect net gas production in in vitro fermentation trials. When used to replace hay, these algae do not impair the degradability of fermented organic matter and tend to reduce the intensity of enteric methane production.

4 - The above-mentioned research emphasizes the potential of dietary strategies to mitigate GHG in tropical livestock systems, with further exploration planned through long-term incubations and in vivo assays to assess the sustainability and effectiveness of these approaches in enteric methane reduction.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

1 – To conclude the MSc program of student Jeraldine B. Vasconez (PPG CENA/USP) and include an additional MSc student to work with postdoctoral researcher Thaynã Gonçalves Timm (PD FAPESP 2024/06301-7).

2 – To continue Laura's DR project by using the two selected diets from the in vitro assays in a metabolism trial, aiming to quantify in vivo enteric CH₄ production in relation to individual animal performance.

3 – Next steps will involve 48-hour in vitro assays to assess the effects of macroalgae on rumen parameters, including organic matter degradability (OMD), enteric methane (CH₄) production, and microbial mass (MM). The most promising macroalgae will then be used in a 21-day in vitro assay to evaluate potential negative impacts on rumen microbiota. Following this, in vivo trials will be conducted to assess the digestibility and performance of macroalgae-supplemented diets in dairy and beef cattle, sheep, and goats, including nutrient metabolism trials and in vivo CH₄ production.

Appendix 15 Principal Investigator: Flávio Augusto Portela Santos

Main objective:

The main objective of this project is to evaluate if and how strategies to increase the energy density of diets for finishing beef cattle, such as the feeding of flint corn ethanol byproducts, the feeding of genetically modified flint corn grain high in alpha amylase and grain processing methods, affect the efficiency of nutrient utilization, the performance of beef cattle and the emissions of GEE.

Subproject 1 – Inclusion of dried distillers' grains with solubles (DDGS) in feedlot diets containing flint corn: metabolism and performance of finishing Nellore bulls.

Student Name: Larissa de Melo Coelho (Dr student FAPESP 2023/16439-3)

It is well documented in the literature that starch from dent corn, cultivated in North America, is more digestible than from flint corn cultivated in Brazil and that several byproducts from the US corn ethanol industry contains greater energy content than dent corn, when included in diets for finishing cattle. However, there is limited information about the relative energy value of these byproducts produced from flint corn and compared with flint corn. A performance (400 Nellore bulls) and a metabolism (20 rumen cannulated Nellore bulls) study was conducted to evaluate levels (0; 15; 30; 45; 60 % of diet DM) of DDGS in diets for finishing cattle containing dry ground flint corn and whole cottonseed. Feeding DDGS up to 30% of diet DM reduced DMI linearly with no negative

effect on cattle ADG (average daily gain) and HCW (hot carcass weight), indicating greater energy value of this byproduct compared with the respective mixtures of ground corn plus whole cottonseed. Feeding DDGS caused a linear decrease in rumen propionate and despite the reduction in DMI, ruminal methane production was not decreased. Data related on nutrient intake and digestibility and microbiota are still being analyzed.

Subproject 2 – Inclusion of dried distillers' grains with solubles in feedlot diets containing flint corn and citrus pulp: metabolism and performance of finishing Nellore bulls.

Student Name: Livia Marques Benez (MS student)

Given the increasing availability of dried distillers' grains with solubles (DDGS) in Brazil and the scant research on its use in conventional confinement diets in the Southeast region—where diets typically include flint corn, citrus pulp, and whole cottonseed—there is a compelling need to investigate the optimal levels of DDGS inclusion in these diets. The objective of the study was to compare the performance (Experiment 1) and metabolism (Experiment 2) of Nellore bulls finished with diets containing 0, 10, 20, 30, or 40% DDGS in dry matter (DM) in total replacement of whole cottonseed and partial replacement of ground flint corn and citrus pulp. In Exp. 1, 368 Nellore bulls blocked by initial shrunk body weight (SBW=420±30 kg) were allocated in 60 experimental pens for 125 d ($n=12$ pens per treatment) to evaluate their growth performance, observed diet net energy for maintenance (NEm) and gain (NEg), and carcass characteristics. In Exp. 2, 30 rumen-cannulated Nellore bulls (503±46 kg BW) were kept in individual pens for 21 days ($n=6$ animals per treatment), to evaluate ruminal parameters and apparent digestibility of nutrients in the total tract. Both experimental designs were randomized blocks, and the data were analyzed using R (ver. 4.3.1). From Exp. 1, linear increases were observed in carcass-adjusted final BW ($P=0.013$), carcass-adjusted average daily gain (ADG; $P=0.024$), carcass-adjusted feed efficiency (G:F; $P<0.001$), hot carcass weight (HCW; $P<0.001$), and dressing percentage (DP; $P<0.001$) with an incremental inclusion of DDGS in the diets. For every ten percent unit inclusion in this type of diet, HCW was increased by 2.55 kg. Additionally, the inclusion of DDGS resulted in linear increases in observed NEm ($P=0.001$) and NEg ($P=0.001$) of the diets. From Exp. 2, digestibility exhibited linearly decreasing effects with the inclusion of DDGS for DM ($P=0.004$), organic matter (OM; $P=0.004$), neutral detergent fiber (NDF; $P=0.01$), acid detergent fiber (ADF; $P=0.04$), and total digestible nutrients (TDN; $P=0.004$). We also observed linear increases for isobutyrate ($P=0.004$) and isovalerate ($P=0.002$) as the DDGS level in the diet increased. The inclusion of DDGS up to 40% in the diets to replace mixtures of whole cottonseed, flint ground corn and citrus pulp increases diet contents of net energy and the performance of *Bos indicus* bulls. Studies of nutrient digestibility and rumen fermentation are not able to demonstrate the energetic superiority of DDGS compared to the mixtures of whole cottonseed, flint ground corn and citrus pulp.

Subproject 3 – Comparison of genetically modified high amylase flint corn (Enogen Flint Corn) with conventional flint corn on “*in vitro*” rumen fermentation, dry matter disappearance, gas and methane production.

Student Name: Daiana dos Santos Oliveira (Dr student)

According to several studies conducted in North America with dent corn, the genetically modified flint corn grain high in alpha amylase (Enogen Feed Corn) has the potential to

increase dent corn starch digestion and improve the performance of finishing beef cattle, more consistently when dent corn is processed as dry grinding. No data is available in the literature about the benefits of this technology for the flint corn produced in Brazil. So, 10 *in vitro* studies were conducted to evaluate the effects of feeding Enogen Flint Corn compared with conventional flint corn on ruminal fermentation, dry matter disappearance, gas and methane production. Independent of the grain processing method (dry ground or high moisture), grinding particle size or moisture content of the high moisture corn, the Flint Enogen was an effective technology to improve rumen fermentation and dry matter disappearance. Despite the increase of rumen propionate production and reduction of acetate, rumen methane production was not decreased.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

For next 1-year period the planned activities are:

1. To determine the ideal inclusion level of the DDGS from São Martinho industry, in diets containing ground flint corn for finishing cattle. Performance, metabolism and methane emission.
2. To test a product which stimulates IGF-1 secretion in finishing cattle fed diets low and high in DDGS.

Appendix 16 Principal Investigator: Fabio Ricardo Marin

Research Question:

Which are the possible impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops?

Main objective:

To analyze and quantify the potential impacts of climate change on the main Brazilian crops, identifying key vulnerabilities and adaptation strategies to ensure sustainable agricultural productivity in the future.

Subproject 1 – Impact assessment of climate change on sugarcane yield in Brazil

Emily Leite (MSc student – CAPES)

Project Progress Summary:

The project aims to analyze the global sensitivity of genotype and soil parameters in a sugarcane model across diverse production environments in Brazil. Significant progress has been made in the following areas:

1. **Introduction and Context:**
 - Addressed the escalating demand for food and energy and the role of sugarcane in meeting these demands while reducing greenhouse gas emissions.
 - Highlighted the importance of sugarcane due to its high biomass production and potential for biofuel and biomaterial production.
2. **Literature Review:**

- Explored the impact of climate change on tropical agriculture, specifically sugarcane.
- Discussed the C3 and C4 photosynthetic pathways and their relevance to sugarcane.
- Reviewed the economic significance of sugarcane in Brazil and its role in promoting sustainability.

3. **Modeling and Methodology:**

- Utilized the SAMUCA model to simulate sugarcane growth under various conditions.
- Incorporated the CENTURY model to assess soil organic matter and nutrient dynamics, focusing on N₂O emissions.
- Established representative areas and homogeneous agroclimatic zones in Brazil for accurate modeling.

4. **Experimental Data:**

- Conducted field experiments in Piracicaba, São Paulo, to gather data on sugarcane growth and emissions under different management practices.
- Simulated future climate scenarios using the SAMUCA and CENTURY models to predict yield, water productivity, and greenhouse gas emissions for the years 2020-2039, 2040-2069, and 2070-2100.

5. **Results and Analysis:**

- Evaluated the accuracy of N₂O emission simulations.
- Analyzed the variation in rainfall, temperature, and crop productivity across different climate models and scenarios.
- Identified the yield risk and potential impacts of extreme weather events on sugarcane production.

The project has laid a solid foundation for understanding the interactions between genotype, soil, and climate in sugarcane production. Ongoing efforts will focus on refining the models, validating the results with additional field data, and developing strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change on sugarcane yield and sustainability.

Subproject 2 – Impact assessment of climate change on pastures growth and development in Brazil

Dr Henrique Baubab Brunetti (Pós-Doc – FAPESP 2024/02021-0)

Not yet started, but the scholarship holder has been hired and began activities in September 2024.

Subproject 3 – Impact assessment of climate change on maize growth and development in Brazil

Tais Souza (MSc student – CAPES)

The project aims to assess the potential impacts of climate change on the primary crops in Brazil, focusing on maize as a case study. Here's an update on the progress made so far:

1. **Introduction and Context:**

- The study highlights the critical relationship between food security and climate change, emphasizing the need for increased agricultural production without expanding agricultural lands.
- The maize crop, being one of the most significant in terms of volume, is used as a focal point for this study, with Brazil being one of the top producers.

2. **Methodology:**

- The project utilizes the Ceres-Maize/DSSAT model to simulate maize growth, development, and yield under different climate scenarios.
- Climate data for Brazil, including temperature, precipitation, wind speed, and relative humidity, were sourced from the Science Data Bank's CLIMBra dataset.
- Field experiments were conducted in Piracicaba, São Paulo, to gather data on maize development under various conditions. These data are used to validate the simulation models.

3. **Determination of Climatic Zones:**

- Eleven climatic zones representing maize production in Brazilian municipalities were identified based on the Global Yield Gap Atlas (GYGA) and statistical data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE).

4. **Simulation and Analysis:**

- The project simulates future climate scenarios (SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5) for maize yield and water productivity across 19 climate model projections.
- Preliminary results indicate the potential impacts of climate change on maize productivity, highlighting the need for increased irrigation, the use of cultivars resistant to high temperatures and drought, and adjustments in crop cycles.

5. **Statistical Evaluation:**

- The accuracy of the simulated data is evaluated using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and the concordance index (d-statistic), ensuring the reliability of the models.

Conclusion: The project has made significant strides in understanding the impacts of climate change on maize production in Brazil. The ongoing simulations and analyses are expected to provide valuable insights for developing effective adaptation strategies to ensure sustainable agricultural productivity in the face of climate change.

Highlights

Advanced Climate Simulations:

- Refined models for maize and sugarcane to simulate growth and emissions under various climate scenarios.

Field Data Validation:

- Collected and integrated extensive field data to enhance the accuracy of climate impact simulations.
- **Adaptation Strategies Development:**
- Identified adaptation strategies for resilient crop cultivars and sustainable management practices in response to climate change.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

For the maize project, the next steps involve refining the Ceres-Maize/DSSAT model simulations by incorporating the latest and more detailed climate data. It will be crucial to validate these models with new field data collected from various regions in Brazil to ensure accuracy. The team will also explore adaptation strategies, such as developing cultivars more resistant to water and heat stress, and improving management practices to enhance productivity and sustainability.

For the sugarcane project, the priority will be the continuous calibration of the SAMUCA and CENTURY models with additional experimental data, focusing especially on N₂O emissions and water productivity. The team plans to conduct global sensitivity analyses to identify the most influential parameters, providing a better understanding of the interactions between genotype, soil, and climate. Furthermore, mitigation and adaptation strategies will be developed to address the challenges posed by climate change, ensuring the sustainability of sugarcane production.

Appendix 17 Principal Investigator: Heitor Cantarella

Research Question:

Can crop rotation schemes reduce GHG emissions, increase C storage, and improve overall system sustainability?

Main objective:

Study the effect of crop rotation in Bioenergy crops and its contributions fo overall system sustainability

Subproject 2. No-tillage for Sugarcane-Peanut Crop Rotation System

Denizart Bolonhezi (researcher in charge)

Peanut is the second cash crop cultivated in the renovation of sugarcane fields. Despite the many benefits of peanuts, soil erosion is the most important challenge in this rotation because of soil disturbance at planting. However, machines are available to plant peanuts under sugarcane straw, and research and commercial experience have shown good results. On the other hand, little information is available about the impact on the following sugarcane crop regarding stalk yield and soil organic carbon. Understanding the interaction between four soil management strategies performed in the peanuts cycle and two tillage treatments before planting sugarcane is of utmost interest.

The field experiment was installed in 2019/20 in a commercial sugarcane field in soil classified as Oxisol (Soil Survey) or Yellow-Red Latosol (Brazilian Soil System) in Planalto, São Paulo. The experimental design was a randomized complete block. The peanuts treatments consisted of conventional, minimum tillage with chisel, strip-tillage,

and no-tillage, with five replications. After the peanut crop was harvested, each plot was divided into two treatments before planting sugarcane (var. RB966928): no-tillage and deep tillage (with and without application of CaO-300 kg/ha). Data was collected in both peanuts and sugarcane cycles.

In the peanuts cycle, the highest soil strength values were observed in no-tillage measured before planting, at flowering, and before and after harvesting, compared with conventional tillage. No differences were verified in soil bulk density and porosity. The differences in soil penetration resistance among the treatments diminished from planting to the end of the cycle. Furthermore, conservation practices with low soil disturbance and maximum straw soil cover significantly increased available water capacity and reduced the incidence and severity of virus (GRSV) on peanut plants. Consequently, both minimum-tillage and no-tillage increased pod yield on average by 695 and 991 kg/ha more than strip-tillage and conventional tillage, respectively, with no effect on grain quality and pod losses.

Figure 1. Peanuts pods and kernel yields affected by methods of soil preparation. Planalto, Sao Paulo State, Brazil. 2021,

Figure 2. Soil penetration resistance (MPa) under different soil management. Planalto, Sao Paulo State, Brazil. 2021,

For the plant cane cycle (Figure 3), the association of strip tillage in peanuts and no-till in sugarcane caused an increase of 12 Mg/ha in stalk yield without affecting the root system. In the first ratoon, an increase in stalk yield was verified with the application of CaO.

Figure 3. Stalk yield of plant cane (RB966928) cultivated under different soil tillage methods before peanuts and before sugarcane. Planalto, Sao Paulo State, Brazil. 2021,

Highlights

- 1- Conventional tillage caused lower resistance to soil penetration at the beginning of the peanuts cycle, but conservation tillage with less soil disturbance and preservation of soil mulch significantly increased yields, available water, and reduced virus diseases.
- 2- The lack of tillage in the previous peanut crop did not affect the yield of the succeeding sugarcane crop.

- 3- The lack of tillage in both the peanuts and sugarcane cycles implies less diesel consumption and, therefore, fewer GHG emissions.

The effect of crop rotation on soil C stocks will be the focus of the next cycle of the present project. Ongoing field experiments and soil samples already collected will be used for that.

Publications:

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De Lima, C.C.; De Maria, I.C.; Guimarães Júnnyor, W. S.; Figueiredo, G.C.; Dechen, S.C.F.; Bolonhezi, D. (2022). **Root parameters of sugarcane and soil compaction indicators under deep strip tillage and conventional tillage**. *Scientific Reports*, v. 12, p. 18537.

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Cherubin, M. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Cerri, C. E. P., Nogueira, L. A. H., Souza, G. M., and Cantarella, H. (2021). **Land use and management effects on sustainable sugarcane-derived bioenergy**. *Land* **10**, 72.

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Oliveira, B. G., Lourenço, K. S., Carvalho, J. L. N., Gonzaga, L. C., Teixeira, M. C., Tamara, A. F., Soares, J. R., and Cantarella, H. (2023). **New trends in sugarcane fertilization: Implications for NH₃ volatilization, N₂O emissions and crop yields**. *Journal of Environmental Management* **342**, 118233.

Rossetto, R., Ramos, N. P., Pires, R. C. d. M., Xavier, M. A., Cantarella, H., and Landell, M. G. d. A. (2022). **Sustainability in sugarcane supply chain in Brazil: Issues and way forward**. *Sugar Tech* **24**, 941-966.

Presentation in International Conferences:

Bolonhezi, D.; Cantarella, H.; Betiol, O.; Ruiz, F.F.; Oliveira, I.N.; Noronha, R.H.; Souza, Z.M.; Furlani, C.E.A. (2024). Direct transplanting of pre-sprouted seedlings under straw of soybean and cover crop: impact on yield and soil organic carbon. In: 9th. World Congress On Conservation Agriculture, **Abstract** Western Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa (21-31 July 2024).

Betiol, O.; Bolonhezi, D.; Ruiz, F.F.; Michelotto, M.D.; Leal, E.R.P.; Valochi, R.; Cantarella, H.; Furlani, C.E.A. (2024). No-tillage for sugarcane-peanut crop rotation system. In: 9th. World Congress On Conservation Agriculture, **Abstract...Western Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa (21-31 July 2024). Best Poster Award**

Planned activities for the next cycle

Research Activities:

Plant and soil samples for yield, soil attributes and soil C stocks

- **Root system:** 1500 soil samples before harvesting in different depth (0-0,20; 0,20-0,40; 0,40-0,60; 0,60-0,80 and 0,80-1,00 m) and different position (row, 35 and 75 cm from row, in both sides). The samples will be analyzed at the Sugarcane Research Center (IAC) to evaluate the root biomass and other characteristics (volume, diameter, length, and area).
- **Agronomic characteristics: Plant** Samples (3 points per plot). All stalks will be sampled (1,0 meter) to determine the biomass. Number of stalks per meter, number of internodes, and length of stalk will be measured, as well as their technological characteristics.
- **Soil Organic Carbon and nutrients:** Soil samples will be taken (0-0,05; 0,05-0,10; 0,10-0,20; 0,20-0,40; 0,40-0,60 e 0,60-1,00 m) to determine total carbon and nitrogen in the soil, as well as the content of macro and micronutrients.
- **Soil Physical Attributes:** After harvesting, undisturbed soil samples will be taken to determine bulk density, porosity, and soil strength. Part of this data will be used to determine the carbon stock affected by soil management.
- **Soil Health:** Soil enzymes and soil quality index will be determined according to EMBRAPA-SoilBio methods

Outreaching:

Field Day

- May 10th Conservation Agriculture on Sugarcane-Peanut Crop System, Planalto/SP. Main focus: transfer the results to technicians and farmers

Participation in Congress and Meetings

- EUROSOIL – 8 -12 September, 2025 – Sevilla, Spain

Appendix 17.1

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Dr. Denizart Bolonhezi

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The best poster

Title: No-tillage for sugarcane-peanut crop rotation system

Co-authors: Mr Cláudio Bettiol, Mr Fábio Fiori Bulz,
Dr Marcos Donisetti Michelotto, Mr Elcio Rios Perez Leal,
Mr Rodrigo Valachi, Dr Heitor Cantarella, Dr Carlos Eduardo A. Furlani

PROF JOHANN STRAUSS
CHAIR: 9WCCA

24 JULY 2024

NO-TILLAGE FOR SUGARCANE-PEANUT CROP ROTATION SYSTEM

Olavo Betiol², Denizart Bolonhezi¹, Fábio Fiori Ruiz², Marcos D. Michelotto¹, Elcio Ríos Perez Leal², Rodrigo Valochi⁴, Heitor Cantarella^{1,4}, Carlos Eduardo Angeli Furlani²

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INTRODUCTION

For each 1,0 Mg/ha of peanut pods is estimated 6,6 Mg/ha of soil erosion.

Objectives: To study the interaction between four soil management strategies performed in the peanuts cycle and two tillage treatments before planting sugarcane on agronomic characteristics and soil properties.

Is it feasible the adoption of C.A. principles for sugarcane-peanut crop system?

MATERIAL and METHODS

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

CONCLUSIONS

- Penetration Resistance: greatest values were observed in no-tillage, but tillage has diminishing effect as the season goes on.
- Minimum tillage and No-tillage have produced pods on average 535 and 591 kg ha⁻¹ more than strip-tillage and conventional.
- Maximum residue plus minimum soil disturbance have significantly reduced the incidence and severity of groundnut ringspot virus.
- Sugarcane stalk yield in no-tillage was 12 Mg ha⁻¹ higher than conventional tillage, regarding the average of tillage for peanut.

Betiol, O.; Bolonhezi, D.; Leal, E.R.P.; Fiori, F.; Michelotto, M.D.; Furlani, C.E.A.; Ruiz, F.F. Conventional agriculture practices in a peanut cropping system: Effects on soil yield and soil penetration resistance. *Rev. Bras. Ciênc. Solo*. 2022;47:e20210008. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s151689542021010008>

Appendix 18 Principal Investigator: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho

Main objective:

Develop an integrated economic model of the Brazilian economy to assess the impacts of new technologies linked to carbon management.

Subproject 1 – Double cropping system in the Brazilian agriculture

Student Name : not yet designated.

The project is in the first stages. Literature was checked, and the methodological strategy is already defined. The model coding is underway. We expect to allocate a doctoral student later this year, after the selection process for the doctoral program in Applied Economics at Esalq.

Subproject 2 – Land use change and carbon storage in soils in Brazil.

Student Name : not yet designated.

This subproject is not initiated. The data source detailed carbon stock in soils was already located, and will be processed to the required format.

Highlights

- 1- How the second crop system in Brazil (initially for soybean/corn) can contribute to the fulfillment of the Brazilian commitments of the INDC.
- 2- How economic policies can affect carbon storage in soils in Brazil, as well as the potential for this mechanism to help Brazil fulfill the INDC targets.

Planned activities for the next 1-year project cycle

For the next year students will be allocated to the two research lines proposed, and the model will be developed. Two studies will be produced, aiming for papers for publication.

Appendix 19 Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Main objective:

Quantify and map, in high spatial resolution, all soil properties by geotechnologies, and gain knowledge of its impact on carbon dynamics

During the period, the geotechnologies line developed a series of subprojects. The focus of the activities is to generate the largest number of thematic maps of soil attributes and organic matter throughout Brazil by means of remote and field sensors, associated with artificial intelligence. The data will form the basis for all other lines of research at CCARBON. In addition to mapping, the fundamentals of these attributes and their relationship to carbon are also being studied. See activity reports below:

- -A knowledge base of different disciplines and their impact on carbon was created, such as pasture management, mineralogy and carbon sequestration, the relationship between total phosphorus and microbiological enzymes.

- - Development of thematic maps of soil properties in Brazil that may have an impact on carbon dynamics, such as pH, CTC, texture and mineralogy.
- - Development of techniques and strategies for spatialization of all soil attributes throughout the country.
- - Development of a comparison of carbon content and carbon stocks between native and cultivated forest areas. We obtained data from 20 states.
- - Development of cloud-based soil carbon analysis strategies.
- - Evaluated disasters in terms of environmental impact and soil carbon.
- - Started work on mapping soil CO₂ emissions and spatialization in Brazil.
- - Mapping of organic matter fractions of the entire national territory
- - Temporal carbon mapping of the entire national territory
- - Impact of carbon on agricultural productivity

During the period, trips were made to sign agreements with: Aristotle University (Greece), University of Florida (USA), University of Prague (Czech Republic), GFZ Spatial Science (Germany), University of Sydney (Australia), Tel Aviv University (Israel).

Upcoming activities:

- Create connections with institutions in China, Morocco, Iran, among others.
- Strengthen the partnership with EMBRAPA-AGROTAG, an integrated field data system at the farmer level.
- Create new subprojects related to soil degradation, especially carbon in different biomes and crops.
- Relate agricultural productivity to soil properties.
- Verify the impact of anthropogenic management on chemical properties and carbon impact.
- Create a national database with all soil properties in high spatial resolution, 30 or 20 meters.
- Create mechanisms to transfer soil information to the scientific community and farmers.

THESE ARE THE DETAILS OF THE SUBPROJECTS

Subproject 1 – Carbon Balance Mapping of the Brazilian Agricultural Areas by Geotechnologies: A New Approach

Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín (Post-doc– FAPESP 2023/17508-9)

Soil regulates carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and influences climate change through carbon (C) sequestration. The dynamic interplay between C sequestration and CO₂ emissions determines the net carbon storage potential. While numerous studies focus on soil CO₂ emissions and C sequestration potential independently, comprehensive assessments of soil C balance remain scarce. At the national scale, Brazil lacks maps detailing soil CO₂ emissions or C sequestration potential, especially in agricultural areas associated with greenhouse gas emissions. This project aims to bridge this gap by assessing the C sequestration potential and CO₂ emissions balance in Brazilian agricultural soils, providing insights into the potential net C storage of these areas. Our methodology integrates soil data, Vis NIR SWIR reflectance spectroscopy analysis, geographic information systems, remote sensing techniques, and digital soil mapping (DSM) approaches, employing machine learning to generate the first-ever maps of potential net C storage, C sequestration potential, and soil CO₂ emissions in Brazilian

agricultural soils. This holistic approach enhances our understanding of agroecosystem opportunities to combat climate change by reducing atmospheric CO₂ levels.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the work plan, indicating the methodological approach to the challenges proposed.

Main advances achieved.

1. An analysis of basal respiration was performed using the municipality of Piracicaba (São Paulo) as a pilot area, considering the bands of the Vis-NIR-SWIR spectrum reported for this variable in the study by Zornoza et al (2008). Additionally, the correlation between this basal respiration and the CH₂ index proposed by Tavanti et al (2023), which is related to soil CO₂ emission, was analyzed in order to explore possible soil CO₂ emission models.
2. The data set was consolidated at the Brazilian level for the selection of samples that will be subjected to soil organic matter (SOM) fractionation analysis, in order to adjust the models of soil CO₂ sequestration potential.
3. A Latin hypercube cluster model was developed for the selection of the most contrasting samples, considering the Vis-NIR-SWIR and Mid-IR spectra.
4. A first data set of soil CO₂ measurements in the state of Mato Grosso was constituted.
5. Climate and relief covariates were consolidated to perform a pilot exercise in Mato Grosso, in order to map basal respiration from Vis-NIR-SWIR spectroscopy and the CH₂ index by Mid-IR spectroscopy.

Subproject 2 – Levantamento de dados e avaliação detalhada da qualidade do solo em áreas piloto: bases para a validação do mapa de qualidade dos solos do Brasil
Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais (Post-doc– FAPESP 2022/14935-0)

Brief description of the project,

Soil Health (SH) refers to the soil's capacity to perform its essential functions, which are fundamental to life on Earth. In this context, developing strategies for the use and management of soils are essential. SH has been identified as a key component in addressing major global challenges, such as food and water security, combating climate change, controlling erosion, and preserving biodiversity. However, due to the complexity of interactions between soil formation factors and anthropogenic interventions, no universal method for SH assessment exists. As a result, there is a growing number of initiatives worldwide aimed at developing methods and tools to quantify and monitor SH at local scales. However, any effort to spatialize it at large-scale. The project in development will result in the first national-scale SH and multilayer map for Brazil with high resolution. We expect that the SH map enhances agricultural production, environmental preservation, and serves as a foundation for public policies. The project's main stages—data collection on soil quality indicators, detailed assessment in pilot areas, and validation of the national SH map—were successfully completed. The current stage, we are utilizing legacy databases, to map the soil quality indicators to calculate the SH and validate and reduce the uncertainties in the SH map. We expect that the project generated innovative and applicable information essential for decision-making at the local level and for formulating regional and national public policies. The main results/advances achieved by the project could be divided into three main sections:

1. Data Collection and Soil Quality Indicators - a comprehensive database and maps of Brazil has been completed.
2. Soil Health Assessment - laboratories analyzing soil samples and field teams that completed the sample collections in strategically important regions of Brazil.

3. Soil Health Brazil Mapping - the soil quality indicators map will derive the 5-layer map of soil health map by the map algebra in cloud computing environment;
4. Validation of the National-Scale Map - the SH map will be reclassified in five categories of soil conditions, from poor to very good, which will have colors representing different levels of SH and analyzed under several socioeconomic perspectives.
5. Completion of the first national SH map for Brazil, establishing a new benchmark for the country.
6. Creation of a comprehensive database with soil quality indicators, available for use in further research and policy development.
7. Part of the data processed were made available in the Dokuchaev Soil Bulletin <https://doi.org/10.19047/0136-1694-2024-119-261-305>
8. Production of novel information can be used to support public policies and soil management decisions at various scales, with a positive impact on agricultural sustainability and environmental preservation.

Figure 1. Flowchart of dynamics of project and its implication in society.

Subproject 3 – Mapa de perdas de solo, P, N e C do mundo
 Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas (Post-doc– FAPESP 2023/17876-8)

Brief description of the project

This postdoctoral project aims to map the losses of phosphorus (P), carbon (C), and nitrogen (N) from soil due to water erosion on a global scale. To achieve this objective, an integrated approach combining remote sensing, geotechnologies, and advanced machine learning techniques will be employed. The proposed methodology includes utilizing remote sensing data to obtain detailed information on soil and vegetation, while geotechnologies will be used to analyze and integrate these data. The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) will be applied to calculate soil loss rates, and these rates

will be used to estimate the losses of P, C, and N. Machine learning algorithms will be employed to model and predict the concentrations of these elements in the soil, enhancing the accuracy of the maps and understanding of erosion dynamics. This project will provide a comprehensive view of nutrient losses at a global level, contributing to the sustainable management of natural resources and soil conservation.

Main advances achieved.

Development of a comprehensive database containing global concentrations of C, P, and N;

Development of environmental covariates that can be utilized for predicting soil maps;

Implementation of a script capable of applying geotechnologies and digital soil mapping techniques within an integrated system using Python programming language and Google Earth Engine (GEE) for digital soil mapping;

Implementation of the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) within the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment.

Subproject 4 – The Global Soil Health Map: Implications for Global Society
Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino (Post-doc– FAPESP 2021/05129-8)

Brief description of the project, and the main results/advances achieved.

Sustainable land management and the enhancement of agricultural productivity critically depend on the understanding and continuous monitoring of soil health. This project introduces an innovative and comprehensive methodology for spatially assessing soil health across the Globe. Leveraging remote sensing data, advanced data science techniques, and the Python API of Google Earth Engine, our approach will employ Random Forest algorithm to map individual soil attributes. These attributes will be integrated using a weighted model based on six distinct soil functions, resulting in the creation of a comprehensive and detailed soil health map. The efficacy of the methodology will be demonstrated through its ability to provide valuable insights for informed decision-making in crucial areas such as land-use planning, environmental management, and sustainable development within the many global regions. This research significantly contributes to the advancement of soil science and has far-reaching implications for policy-making and land management practices on both regional and global scales.

Subproject 5 – Mapeamento de locais propensos à erosão do solo através de SIG e sensoriamento remoto

Uemeson José dos Santos (Post-doc– SEM BOLSA)

Brief description of the project, and the main results/advances achieved.

Soil erosion is one of the main land degradation processes, negatively impacting ecosystem productivity and food security. In addition, erosion interacts with climate change, affecting the biogeochemical cycles of the elements. Considering the diversity of soils, relief and climates in Brazil, the project has a special focus on gullies, which are responsible for soil degradation in different regions of the country. Gullies are a serious type of soil degradation, causing considerable soil loss, producing large volumes of sediment and affecting water quality and water security. Despite its importance, gully erosion is often underestimated in soil loss assessment programs, highlighting the need for monitoring, experimental and modeling studies to predict the effects of environmental changes on erosion rates of this type. Therefore, the project aims to contribute to the understanding and mitigation of soil erosion in Brazil, especially in gullies, using advanced remote sensing and computer modeling techniques, with a view to promoting sustainable development and preserving natural resources. The project has yet to produce any results, as it is still in the initial stages of implementation.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the postdoctoral program's work plan, indicating the methodological approach to the proposed challenges.

Subproject 6 – MAPEAMENTO ESPAÇO-TEMPORAL 2.5D DO ESTOQUE DE CARBONO ORGÂNICO DOS SOLOS DO BRASIL

Nicolas Augusto Rosin (PhD student – FAPESP 2021/10063-6)

Brief description of the project, and the main results/advances achieved.

Digital mapping of soil information is key for soil health and food security. The soil organic carbon (SOC) is a key soil attribute, having direct relation with physical, chemical, and biological properties. The soil could be sink or drain of C to atmosphere depending on management and the loss of C reduces the soils functions. Brazil has an expressive agricultural production area and a great potential for SOC sequestration. However, the spatio-temporal distribution of the SOC stock in the territory is poorly known, making difficult to implement public policies for low-C agriculture. The objective of this research is to map the 2.5D spatio-temporal distribution (present, past and future) of the SOC in Brazilian soils with detailed resolution for layers 0-5, 5-15, 15-30, 30-60 and 60-100 cm, and identify the main factors controlling their dynamics through the use of different covariates derived from remote sensing and modeling strategies. The SOC stock maps at detailed scale for the Brazilian territory can serve as subsidy for public policies for low C agriculture and climate change mitigation.

We obtained preliminary results, in which the spatio-temporal distribution of the SOC stock in Brazilian soils for the superficial layer were mapped. For it, we obtained a temporal database with soil observation and environmental covariates (static and dynamic) for Brazilian territory. The 0-20cm layer SOC stock was mapped with high resolution (30m) from 1984 to 2023 for 5-year periods by digital soil mapping framework. Terrain attributes (static), vegetation indices (dynamic) land use and land cover (LULC) (dynamic) and a soil-vegetation image (dynamic) were used as covariates. A unique Random Forest model was calibrated and used to predict the SOC stock by use of dynamic covariates of each period. The SOC stock predictive model reached R^2 of 0.86, RMSE of $14.77 \text{ ton ha}^{-1}$ and RPIQ of 1.63. The most important covariates were some terrain attributes and LULC. The Brazilian soils in superficial layer had 33.42 Gt of SOC in the first period (1984-1998) and now have 32.95 Gt of SOC in the last period (2019-2023), which represents a loss of 0.47 Gt of C (-1.43%). The losses were of 0.40 Gt (-2.36%) in Amazon, of 0.04 Gt (-0.39%) in Cerrado, of 0.03 Gt (-3.50%) in Pampa and of Mata Atlântica 0.03 Gt (-0.61%). In the other hand, the soils from Caatinga (0.01 Gt / +0.39 %) and Pantanal (0.01 Gt / +1.38%) gained SOC. The losses of SOC are associated manly with LULC changes and the gains with several factors. The use multitemporal machine learning model based in remote sensing covariates was an efficient way to access the SOC stock in the past and present. The preliminary results can be found in the figures below:

Figure 1: Initial and final period maps and map of the difference in SOC stock between periods.

Subproject 7 – Mapeamento Digital da Produtividade de Soja com ênfase em Solos inseridos via Sensoriamento Remoto em Modelos de Simulação (Regiões Sudeste e Centro-Oeste do Brasil)

Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim (PhD student – FAPESP 2022/11034-2)

The demand for food is the greatest pressure of this century. Determining production potential (PP) targets is a key factor in any management agency. In addition to climate, PP should emphasize soil attributes. Soil texture, depth, water and fertility have been the most frequently used factors. On the other hand, subsurface soil attributes and organic matter contents are rarely considered. The objective of this work is to develop a digital technique that allows determining the production potential of soybeans in agricultural areas, using remote sensing and machine learning. In addition, climatological variables and biophysical parameters of the crop will be analyzed to determine spatially explicit estimates of soybean PP in the southeast and central-west regions. In parallel, the impact of soil organic matter on soybean PP will also be evaluated. Soil and climate data will be obtained via SR. This spatial information on soil and climate, together with soybean crop parameters, will be used as inputs for productivity modeling in the DSSAT program. Thematic maps with 250 m resolution will be generated, with subsequent validation.

Spatial simulations will be performed with different organic matter contents to verify their impact on PP. Simulations will also be performed with different future climate scenarios to verify how the crop behaves and how the soil influences this process. Based on the PP maps and soil information, production environments for soybeans will be created. It is expected that the work will contribute with an agile and low-cost methodology for more accurate mapping of PP, assisting in decision-making for environmental, agricultural, economic and public policy management in Brazil.

Figure 1. Work flowchart showing the study area, materials and methods proposed for the development of this project. BESB: Brazilian Spectral Soil Library. FEBR: Brazilian Free Repository for Open Soil Data. GEOS3: Geospatial Soil Sensing System.

Main advances achieved:

1. Definition of the most important soil attributes that contribute to the soybean productivity, over the central region of Brazil, in surface and subsurface;

2. Development of a methodology to predict the soybean productivity over large areas, with remote sensing;
3. Evaluation of the behavior of soil production environment for soybean agricultural municipalities.

Subproject 8 – Global mapping of hydromorphic soils via machine learning
Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch (PhD student – FAPESP 2023/11350-4)

This study will explore the application of machine learning and remote sensing data as predictive covariates for mapping hydromorphic soils on a global scale. The aim is to generate a product that addresses the urgent need to understand and characterize wetlands, which play a crucial role in greenhouse gas flux and ecosystem services. The increasing degradation of wetlands due to human activities highlights the need for more detailed approaches. Although remote sensing tools have been developed to assess hydromorphic soils, a global approach is still required. The proposal encompasses mapping hydromorphic soils in both agricultural and non-agricultural areas. This will be achieved through the use of data from Synthetic Soil Exposed Imagery (SySI) and terrain attributes, with the development of a model based on the Random Forest algorithm. Additionally, the intention is to distinguish hydromorphic areas concerning biomes and land use types. The study area will cover the entire Earth's surface where exposed soil pixels exist. The research will include a global database with pedological information, soil attributes, and spectral signatures in the VIS-NIR-SWIR range, which will be used to validate the SySI. Thus, it is anticipated that this approach will be capable of mapping hydromorphic soils, demonstrating the potential to enhance monitoring in agricultural areas for decision-making and guiding public policies on a global scale.

Main advances achieved.

1. Development of an outlier filtering protocol in hyperspectral data and soil attributes. The protocol is already in the paper writing phase.
2. Obtaining SySI through Landsat and Sentinel sensor systems, for the time intervals 1984/2023 and 2017/2023 respectively.

Figure 1. Flowchart of materials and methods for chapters 1 and 2 of PhD thesis.

Subproject 9 – Projeto Carbono Brasil (CABRAL)

Borges Marfrann Dias Melo (PhD student – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00)

There is a limitation to understand the diversity in carbon content between native forests and adjacent agricultural areas on the same soil types. In this regard, the CaBral Project consists in a voluntary initiative aligned with CCARBON which addresses the knowledge gap by monitoring soil C. This project operates without external funding and is situated at the forefront of remote and proximal sensing analysis for both agricultural and natural soils across Brazil. Therefore, we aimed to demonstrate the dynamic of soil organic carbon (SOC) prediction, enabling the identification of anthropogenic impacts on national, regional, and local scales. Samples collected from all Brazilian states followed a specific protocol for traditional and spectral analyses within the ranges visible, near-infrared and short-wave infrared (Vis-NIR-SWIR) (350-2500 nm) as well as mid-infrared (Mid-IR) spectrum (4000-600 cm^{-1}). Cubist machine learning algorithm modeled the SOC content, with covariate extraction and spatial prediction performed by Google Earth Engine. Modeling performance is evaluated by the coefficient of determination (R^2) and root mean square error (RMSE) for both training and validation datasets. The preliminary results served to compile a soil spectral library with 1400 samples from the north, northeast, southeast and south regions of Brazil, from twenty-one Brazilian states. We expect the model to demonstrate high correlation and low errors with observed data. There is perspective for huge participation of all Brazilian states, fostering collaborations and contributing to the intern carbon credits market. Knowing the SOC dynamics in agricultural and natural environments in extensive areas such as Brazilian territory when coupled with Earth observation data from satellites. This approach brings the potential to enhance production capacity of soils, supporting carbon sequestration, improving food production efficiency, and contributing to environmental preservation while mitigating global warming.

Figure 1. Flowchart Cabral Project.

The main results/advances achieved:

- 1- End of collection and receipt of data with collaborators.
- 2- Start of data processing and modeling.

Subproject 10 – Digital mapping of water available in the soil in agricultural areas in Brazil
Letícia Guadagnin Vogel (Master student – CAPES 88887.907957/2023-00)

Brazil stands out in world agricultural production in volume and productivity, but population growth has impacts on the consumption of natural resources, such as water. It is essential to understand the process and storage of water in the soil, especially the fraction of available water (AW) for plants. AW is a relevant parameter in the agronomic and agricultural areas. Different methods are used to obtain soil water values, direct or indirect, however, specific methods are costly and time-consuming. The diversity of soil cover in the country must be considered in agricultural planning, as well as its effect on soil water availability, requiring spatial and temporal understanding. Pedotransfer functions, combined with remote sensing, allow digital mapping of AW in the soil, using geospatial technologies and computational models. However, there is a scarcity of studies dedicated to mapping AW in the soil, especially for large areas in tropical regions. Therefore, the objective of this work is to develop a methodology for spatialization of soil water retention, via satellite data, in agricultural areas in Brazil. Soil water

capacity values will be estimated using laboratory-determined soil characteristics and pedotransfer functions. Satellite spectral data will be acquired, as well as exposed soil data, and a model will be validated against the database. Therefore, it is expected that exposed soil satellite images can be used to map soil water availability in different agricultural areas of Brazil.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the work plan carried out.

The main results/advances achieved:

1. Use of soil attributes and point data to generate digital maps of available soil water for agricultural areas in Brazil, at 5 different depths.
2. Obtaining data on total and easily available water, field capacity and permanent wilting point.
3. First test map of total available soil water (0-100 cm), with point data specialized for agricultural areas in Brazil.
4. The initial map has already shown correlation with some soil types.
5. Piecewise Linear regression with high R^2 (0.87 and 0.93) between clay data and total available soil water (TAW), both for the surface layer (0-20 cm) and for the last layer evaluated (80-100 cm).

Subproject 11 – Soil health as a factor in the analysis of anthropogenic pedosphere degradation
Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa (Master student – CAPES 88887.823854/2023-00)

The degradation of soil health (SH) presents itself as a global trend in the scenario of anthropogenic use of the landscape. Whatever the objective of extracting and using a natural resource, human action causes, has caused and will cause significant impacts on the functioning of an ecosystem. SH refers to the soil's ability to perform its ecosystem functions, for instance, food production, water and climate regulation, nutrient cycling, and carbon sequestration. The evolution of awareness of the need to understand the situation of soils is considerable. However, there is a gap between scientific production on soil health and proposals for improving agricultural production in a sustainable way. This is due to the individualized analysis of the current soil situation without considering economic and management factors in the current context of agricultural production and future perspectives. A definitive understanding of the current anthropic scenario lacks the interdisciplinary union of factors that

make ideological transitions plausible. Therefore, the work presented developed a sustainable growth index on a regional state scale that correlates economy, nature, and management. From this, the analysis of the resulting index will potentially be capable of promoting a comprehensive view of current and future scenarios of agricultural production, stimulating a new perspective on food management and promotion.

Subproject 12 – Mapeamento detalhado de hematita e goethita de solos brasileiros através de dados espectrais e aprendizado de máquina

Fernando Yutaro Makino (Scientific initiation – FAPESP 2023/13708-3)

The study aims to create a detailed map of the distribution of hematite and goethite in Brazil, essential for developing a comprehensive soil quality map. The methodology involves database organization, spectral processing, determination of iron oxide content, and data spatialization using Random Forest. The goal is to provide novel and crucial information for soil quality indicators and the creation of a detailed soil quality map for the country. It resulted in the creation of a detailed map of the distribution of hematite and goethite in Brazil, which will serve as an essential foundation for developing the country's soil quality map.

Subproject 13 – Biblioteca Brasileira de Espectros de Solos via Satélite para Avaliação e Monitoramento da Saúde do Solo

Matheus Carraco Cardoso (Scientific initiation – CNPq PIBIC -2023)

The systematization of electromagnetic reflectance patterns of soils results in a Soil Spectral Library (SSL) that records the pedological variety of a given location and, for that reason, constitutes a legacy for society. Despite the relevance of the topic, there is a scarcity of studies focused on the compilation of spectra obtained at the orbital level, which are as suitable for deriving information as data in hyperspectral resolutions. In this regard, the objective is to compile an SSL representative of Brazilian pedodiversity through orbital remote sensing (RS). For this purpose, the Brazilian Soil Spectral Library (BSSL) will be the database for the selection of more than 22,000 representative soil points in terms of class proportion. Machine

learning algorithms such as cluster analysis and principal component analysis in an R environment will assist in clustering soil spectral signatures. The selected points will serve as criteria for collecting average spectra in a time series of exposed soils (2017-2023) from Landsat and Sentinel satellite sensors built using the GEOS3 algorithm on the Google Earth Engine platform. The set of points will be systematized in a spectral database associated with the attributes of the soils under study. It is expected that the multispectral database will group soil patterns of large areas such as Brazil. From this perspective, an SSL of this extent has various applications ranging from attribute prediction to digital soil mapping, which reduces survey costs, speeds up results, and minimizes the generation of waste from laboratory analyses.

Subproject 14 – Mapeamento de Voçorocas (SySI)

Matheus Fatori (Scientific initiation – without scholarship)

Gullies are advanced erosive processes resulting from natural events and human activities, with rain being the primary agent. The occurrence of these phenomena is a product of the physical-chemical characteristics of the soils, edaphoclimatic conditions, biotic agents, and time (JOSÉ et al., 1996). The consequences include losses in both the physical-chemical quality of the soil and its economic potential (PIMENTEL et al., 1995), and are also related to environmental issues such as flooding, siltation, and pollution of water bodies (WANG et al., 2016), making it a significant event for soil science.

The objectives of this work are to identify and map gullies using the Synthetic Soil Image (SySI) for the Piracicaba-SP region.

Subproject 15 – Avaliação da saúde do solo na região de Piracicaba via geotecnologias

Miguel Neves (Scientific initiation – PUB 2973/2023)

Understanding the soil and constantly monitoring its health are essential pillars for sustainable land management and increased agricultural productivity (Sarkheil et al. 2023). This project proposes an innovative approach, using machine learning techniques, earth observation data and information obtained in the field to map soil health on a global scale. Through the application of the Random Forest algorithm, using remote sensing data and the Python API of the Google Earth Engine platform, it will be possible to spatialize soil attributes. The resulting

maps will be integrated into a weighted model based on six distinct soil functions, generating a global map of soil health with a spatial resolution of 30 meters. The effectiveness of this methodology will be demonstrated through cross-validation, highlighting the cartographic product's ability to provide accurate information for strategic decision-making in areas such as land use planning, environmental management and sustainable development in various global regions (Bandyopadhyay and Maiti , 2021). This research represents a significant contribution to the advancement of soil science, with relevant implications for the formulation of land management policies and practices at regional and global scales.

Subproject 16 – Projeto Carbono Brasil (CABRAL)

Samuel Silva de Moraes (Scientific initiation – without scholarship)

During my time working on the Carbono Brasil Project (Cabral), I took on a variety of roles that allowed me to apply and expand my technical skills while contributing to a significant environmental research initiative. My work primarily focused on the separation of soil and plant samples, conducting spectral readings, and analyzing data within a supervised database, all under the guidance of postgraduate students.

One of my key responsibilities was separating soil and plant samples. This task was crucial because the accuracy of sample separation directly impacted the reliability of the research data. I approached this task with great attention to detail, ensuring that each sample was carefully handled and prepared for further analysis. This foundational work was essential to the success of the project, as it ensured that subsequent analyses would be based on precise and uncontaminated samples.

In addition to sample separation, I was also responsible for conducting spectral readings. This involved using advanced equipment to measure the reflectance of various samples across different wavelengths. The spectral readings were a critical component of the project, as they provided valuable insights into the chemical and physical properties of the samples. I quickly became proficient in operating the spectral equipment, following established protocols to ensure that the data I collected was both accurate and consistent. This aspect of my work allowed me to engage deeply with the technical side of environmental research, enhancing my understanding of how spectral data can be used to analyze ecological conditions.

Data analysis was another important part of my role in the Carbono Brasil Project. After collecting the spectral data, I was involved in processing and analyzing it within a supervised database. Managing and analyzing large datasets required a strong grasp of data structures and analytical techniques, which I developed further through this experience. Working closely with postgraduate students, I learned how to approach complex data analysis problems and refine my skills in this area. Their supervision not only ensured the quality of the analysis but also provided me with valuable mentorship, helping me to grow as a researcher.

Subproject 17 – Soil Health Diagnosis in Brazilian Pastures: A Spatial and Temporal Analysis by Biome.

Aron Müller de Oliveira (Scientific initiation – PUB 3128/2023 Benefício: 83-1)

Pastures cover about 70% of the national territory, playing a crucial role in food production, income generation, and biodiversity maintenance. However, improper management of pastures can lead to soil degradation, loss of biodiversity, and greenhouse gas emissions.

In this context, the aim is to conduct a temporal analysis of over 30 years of Brazilian pasture areas and diagnose their current condition using various attributes. The study aims to analyze data on soil organic carbon, vegetative indices, textural classes, and the productive potential of pasture areas classified by biomes, using machine learning tools and statistical analyses.

Through long-term data analysis covering the entire Brazilian territory, the study provides valuable information on carbon dynamics—an essential indicator of soil health—and pasture productivity. This enables a better understanding of the impacts of pasture management on the environment and national-scale production.

To analyze the productive potential of pasture areas in Brazilian biomes in 2022, the results obtained from the cross-referencing of pasture area maps and the SoilPP index map were considered. This combination corresponded to an area of approximately 1,000,000 km² or 100 Mha. In 2022, the land use in Brazil destined for pasture was 164 Mha.

Analysis of the productive potential of pasture areas in Brazilian biomes in 2022:

In 2022, about 10% (11 Mha) of the land used for pastures in Brazil had a high productive potential, classified as "A" by the SoilPP index, indicating good drainage, depth, and nutrient availability for plants. Additionally, slightly over 12% (13 Mha) of Brazilian agricultural soils used for pastures exhibited a clayey texture.

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Poster presentation

V Encontro paulista de ciência do solo - V EPCiS

Consistency assessment of the open-access Brazilian soil spectral library

Jean Jesus Macedo Novais; Nicolas Augusto Rosin; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim; Leticia Guadagnin Vogel; José Alexandre de Melo Demattê

Spatial distribution and agricultural implications of phosphorus stocks in Brazilian biomes: a machine learning approach

Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; José A.M. Demattê; Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch; Nicolás Augusto Rosin; Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa; Paulo Sergio Pavinato.

Revealing the spatio-temporal dynamic of soil organic carbon stock in Brazil by earth observation

Nicolás Augusto Rosin; José A. M. Demattê; Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Raul Roberto Poppiel; Heidy Soledad Rodriguez-Albarracín

Antarctica soil characterization by proximal sense

Miguel Neves Magalhaes de Paula Mendes; José Alexandre Melo Demattê; Borges Mello Marfrann; Danilo César de Mello; Marcio Rocha Francelino; Tiago Osório Ferreira; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Carlos Ernesto Gonçalves Reynaud Schaefer

Soybean yield productivity modelling by remote sensing data, in-situ soil attributes, machine learning and human experience association

Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim; Danilo César de Mello; Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa; Letícia Guadagnin Vogel; Andre V. Zabini; José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Mapping soil health in germany: towards a sustainable agricultural development index

Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa; Sabine Chabrilat; Robert Milewski; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Maurício Roberto Cherubin; José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Soil health assessment through remote sensing: a systematic review

Borges Marfrann Dias Melo; Gabriel Nogueira Bonelli; Luiza Pecci Canisares; Yuri Soares de Mello⁴, José Alexandre Melo Demattê¹, Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Oral Presentation V Encontro paulista de ciência do solo - V EPCIS

is it possible to detect and map enzyme activities from the whole agriculture Brazilian area by a sensor located 800 km from the target?

Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín; José A. M. Demattê; Nicolás Augusto Rosin; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Fernando Dini Andreote; Nariane de Andrade; Alberto Vinicius S. Rocha; Elaine Reis Pinheiro Lourente; Letícia G. Vogel; Matheus C. Cardoso. First place award in the category of best oral presentations at the “V ENCONTRO PAULISTA DE CIÊNCIA DO SOLO V EPCiS ” realized in Botucatu, SP, August 13 and 14, 2024.

Poster presentation CCarbon Soil Health Symposium – 24 april 2024

Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, Vagner Fernando Nolasco Junior, Letícia Guadagnin Vogel, Asa Gholizadeh, Borůvka Lubos, Lucas Tadeu Greschuk, Maurício Roberto Cherubin, José Alexandre Melo Dematte. **A strategy to determine the Czech Republic's soil health from space.** 24/04/2024, Piracicaba, São Paulo, Brazil. CCarbon Soil Health Symposium 2024. (First place award in the category of best oral presentations)

Miguel Neves Magalhaes de Paula Mendes; José Alexandre Melo Demattê; Borges Mello Marfrann; Danilo César de Mello; Marcio Rocha Francelino; Tiago Osório Ferreira; Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas; Carlos Ernesto Gonçalves Reynaud Schaefer. **Antartic soil**

characterization by proximal sensing 24/04/2024, Piracicaba, São Paulo, Brazil. CCarbon Soil Health Symposium 2024.

Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch; Gabriel Pimenta Barbosa de Sousa'; Letícia Guadagnin Vogel'; Borges Marfrann Dias Melo'; Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim'; Matheus Carraco Cardoso'; Jean de Jesus Novais'; José Alexandre Melo Demattê. **Carbon determination from space** 24/04/2024, Piracicaba, São Paulo, Brazil. CCarbon Soil Health Symposium 2024.

Appendix 19.1

Article

Estimation of Biochemical Compounds in Tradescantia Leaves Using VIS-NIR-SWIR Hyperspectral and Chlorophyll a Fluorescence Sensors

Renan Falconi ^{1,*}, Roney Berti de Oliveira ¹, Marcelo Luiz Chicati ¹, Werner Camargos Antunes ¹, José Alexandre M. Demattê ² and Marcos Rafael Nanni ¹

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Abstract: An integrated approach that utilises hyperspectral and chlorophyll a fluorescence sensors to predict biochemical and biophysical parameters represents a new generation of remote-sensing research. The main objective of this study was to obtain a detailed spectral profile that correlates with plant physiology, thereby enhancing our understanding and management of plant health, pigment profiles, and compound fingerprints. Leveraging datasets using non-imaging or passive hyperspectral and chlorophyll fluorescence sensors to collect data in Tradescantia species demonstrated significant differences in leaf characteristics with pigment concentrations and structural components. The main goal was to use principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least squares regression (PLS) methods to analyse the variations in their spectra. Our findings demonstrate a strong correlation between hyperspectral data and chlorophyll fluorescence, which is further supported by the development of hyperspectral vegetation indices (HVIs) that can accurately evaluate fingerprints and predict many compounds in variegated leaves. The higher the integrated analytical approach and its potential application in HVIs and fingerprints, the better the selection of wavelengths and sensor positions for rapid and accurate analysis of many different compounds in leaves. Nonetheless, limitations arose from the specificity of the data for the Tradescantia species, warranting further research across diverse plant types and compounds in the leaves. Overall, this study paves the way for more sustainable and informed agricultural practices through breakthroughs in the application of sensors to remote-sensing technologies.

Keywords: biochemical compounds; HVI; hyperspectral sensors; partial least squares regression; principal component analysis; purple leaves

Citation: Falconi, R.; Oliveira, R.B.d.; Chicati, M.L.; Antunes, W.C.; Demattê, J.A.M.; Nanni, M.R. Estimation of Biochemical Compounds in Tradescantia Leaves Using VIS-NIR-SWIR Hyperspectral and Chlorophyll a Fluorescence Sensors. *Remote Sens.* **2024**, *16*, 1910. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16111910>

Academic Editors: Jueghuan Ku, Wei Xie and Ximeng Li

The Brazilian Soil Spectral Library data opening

doi: <https://doi.org/10.19047/0136-1694-2024-119-261-305>

Journal: Dokuchaev Soil Bulletin, 2024, № 119, p. 261-305

Publisher: V.V. Dokuchaev Soil Science Institute

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| 6. A. S. S. Pava | 12. D. C. MeMello | |

Abstract

Among the various repositories of soil spectral data, the Brazilian Soil Spectral Library (BSSL, <https://bibliotecaespectral.wixsite.com/english>), created and maintained by the GeoCIS research group, is representative of the pedodiversity of the region, since it combines soil spectra from agricultural and environmental research. The BSSL database contains 16,064 observations with soil-harmonized surface layer physicochemical and spectral data in the visible, near-infrared, short-wave infrared (Vis-NIR-SWIR, 350–2,500 nm) and mid-infrared (MIR, 4,000–800 cm^{-1}) ranges from all 26 Brazilian states and the Federal District. The idea of creating the BSSL was born in 1995, completed

Geoderma 638 (2023) 119619

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Geoderma

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/geoderma

Chemical weathering detection in the periglacial landscapes of Maritime Antarctica: New approach using geophysical sensors, topographic variables and machine learning algorithms

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Badriana Misener

Keywords

Geospatial spectroscopy
Weathering intensity
Periglacial Process

ABSTRACT

The chemical weathering intensity in Antarctica is underestimated. As the chemical weathering intensity increases, hydrological, geochemical and geophysical changes occur in the different environmental spheres and at their interfaces through reactions and energy flows. Thus, once chemical weathering rates are understood and estimated, they can be used to predict and assess changes and trends in different environmental spheres. Few studies on the chemical weathering intensity have been performed in Antarctica. We used radiometric and magnetic susceptibilities associated with terrain attributes and the chemical degree of alteration of the igneous rock

Radiometric and magnetic susceptibility characterization of soil profiles: Geophysical data and their relationship with Antarctic periglacial processes, pedogenesis, and lithology

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Soil magnetic susceptibility
Gamma-ray spectrometry
Periglacial environment
Pedogenomorphology
Antarctic soils

ABSTRACT

Maritime Antarctica is still pedologically unexplored by proximal geophysical sensors. In-depth soil geophysical characterizations in depth can provide comprehensive information regarding how weathering, pedogenesis, and periglacial processes operate in periglacial environments, with advantages like non-invasive methodology, fast and precise data acquisition, practical equipment operation, and cost-effectiveness. This research aimed to carry out the first proximal gamma-spectrometric and magnetic geophysical characterization of soil profiles in maritime Antarctica and to relate the geophysical variables analyzed with periglacial processes, weathering, pedogenesis, geology, and landscape dynamics. The study was carried out in the Kåker Peninsula (King George Island, Maritime

Geoderma Regional 27 (2024) e80813

Texture prediction of natural soils in the Brazilian Amazon through proximal sensors

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
pDRF
Vis-NIR
Biodomes forest

ABSTRACT

Proximal sensors provide fast, low-cost, environmentally friendly, and reliable analysis for the characterization of soils and other materials. Numerous studies have been conducted on soils in temperate regions, but there are knowledge gaps regarding the use of these devices in tropical soils, especially in the Amazon region. In this regard, this study utilized portable proximal sensors of X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (pDRF) and diffuse reflectance spectroscopy in the visible to near-infrared region (Vis-NIR) for predicting the texture of natural soils in 61 municipalities in the state of Pará, Amazon region, Brazil. The objectives were: i) to investigate the accuracy of soil texture prediction based on data from sensors separately and sensor fusion (pDRF and Vis-NIR data)

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Science of the Total Environment

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/scototenv

Geotechnologies on the phosphorus stocks determination in tropical soils: General impacts on society

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Digital soil mapping techniques have overcome the challenges associated with phosphorus mapping
- Fertilizers have significantly increased Available P stocks in agricultural areas
- Available P stocks strongly influence Brazil's agricultural production, especially soybeans.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Catena 248 (2024) 107988

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Catena

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/catena

Spatializing soil elemental concentration as measured by X-ray fluorescence analysis using remote sensing data

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Soil mapping
Mineralogy

ABSTRACT

Spatial soil information has significantly contributed to public policy and planning. The use of X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF) in soil science, primarily in laboratory settings or for isolated point analysis, has been well documented. This study broadens the application of XRF data by integrating it with remote sensing data for a

Research

Analysis of organic and mineral nitrogen, total organic carbon and humic fractions in Ferralsols: an approach using Vis-NIR-SWIR, MIR and X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy

Bruna Coelho de Lima¹ · Carlos H. dos Santos¹ · Carlos S. Tiritan¹ · José A. M. Demattê² · Andres M. R. Gomez² · Heidi S. R. Albarracín² · Bruno A. Bartsch²

Received: 4 March 2024 / Accepted: 31 May 2024

Published online: 16 July 2024

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Abstract

This work aimed to develop suitable predictive models for ammonium, nitrate, total nitrogen, total organic carbon and soil humic fractions, for Ferralsols, using Vis-NIR-SWIR, MIR and X-ray fluorescence spectroscopic techniques in conjunction with machine learning algorithms, Cubist, PLSR, Random Forest and Support Vector Machine. Chemical analyzes were carried out to determine nitrate, total nitrogen, total organic carbon and chemical fractionation of soil organic matter, as well as spectral analyzes using Vis-NIR-SWIR spectroscopy, MIR and X-ray fluorescence. The spectroscopy results were processed using RStudio v. 4.1.3, applying Cubist, PLSR, Random Forest and Support Vector Machine machine learning algorithms to create predictive models and describe spectral curves and Pearson correlation. Of the prediction models developed for nitrogen, total organic carbon and humic fractions, the PLSR and Support Vector Machine algorithms presented the best predictive performances. The descriptive analysis of the spectra identified the main absorption bands and the location of the bands sensitive to the attributes of interest. The correlation analysis proposed that the use of Vis-NIR-SWIR, MIR and XRF spectroscopic techniques were effective in predicting the contents of nitrogen, total organic carbon and humic fractions in soil with a medium sandy texture. However, it is important to highlight that each technique has its characteristic mechanism of action, Vis-NIR-SWIR and MIR detect the element based on overtones and fundamental tones, while XRF is based on the atomic number of the elements or elemental association.

Keywords Supervised machine learning · Spectroscopic techniques · Accurate fertilization Sandy soil · Ammonium and nitrate quantification · Organic matter quantification · Soil health · Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Sustainable soil use is an indispensable practice for the longevity of tropical agricultural soils, due to the difficulty in maintaining the stock and quality of organic matter in production systems [1]. The Oxisols, as they are called in the USA by soil taxonomy [2], are considered by the Brazilian soil classification system as Ferralsols, are weathered, low-fertility

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Catena

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/catena

Pedogenesis on Jurassic formations in the Araripe Basin, northeastern Brazil: Weathering and parent material

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Mudstones
Cairn Valley Group
Soil profiles
Mg saturation
Fluvisols
Cretaceous units

ABSTRACT

The Araripe Basin is the largest sedimentary basin in the countryside of Northeast Brazil. Despite the wide diversity of lithostratigraphic, geomorphological, and paleontological studies, little is known about the pedogenesis and weathering. This study aimed to characterize the morphological, physical and chemical attributes, and the spectral behavior of soils in a toposequence over Jurassic formations of the Araripe Basin so as to identify the main pedogenetic processes, as well as their degree of weathering. A toposequence composed of four soil profiles was selected, described, and sampled in a semi-arid depression that is geologically composed of lacustrine (mudstones) and fluvial (sandstones) deposits. The variability of soil attributes such as color, texture, base

Soil Advances 2 (2024) 319021

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Soil Advances

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/soiladvances

Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Remote sensing
Soil degradation
Soil health
Sustainability
Soil management

ABSTRACT

In countries with extensive agricultural practices, there is a significant risk of soil degradation, making it essential to develop techniques for understanding and detecting these changes. In this study, we used an earth observation system to identify the temporal bare soil frequency and thus, relate it with soil tillage and its impact on soil carbon degradation. The work was performed in two important agricultural states of Brazil, São Paulo and Paraná. For that, historical field and Remote Sensing (RS) data were analyzed to identify the relation be-

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Geoderma

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/geoderma

Potential of soil minerals to sequester soil organic carbon

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Jooqil Hong

Keywords:
Spatial regression
Digital soil mapping
Sensibility
Soil security
Soil spectroscopy
Sorption deficit

ABSTRACT

The capacity of soil to sequester carbon (C) is a key process that promotes the reduction of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Soils can absorb as much as 20% of anthropogenic carbon emissions, which can contribute to mitigate climate change. This capacity relies on the organo-mineral association, which includes different minerals, Fe and Al oxides, which have a critical soil organic carbon (SOC) sorption surface. Based on an equation of the potential C sorption deficit of fine soil particles (<20 μm/silt and clay fractions) for tropical regions, this study investigated the SOC sequestration potential of the clay fraction for soils in Piracicaba region, São Paulo State, Brazil as influenced by the clay minerals. This potential was fitted to a spatial regression model for soil depths 0–20 cm and 60 to 100 cm. In the surface layer, the sequestration potential was mostly explained by the relative abun-